

From Galaxies to the Intergalactic Medium

Dissertation

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree Doctor of
Philosophy in the Graduate School of The Ohio State University

By

Molly S. Peeples

Graduate Program in Astronomy

The Ohio State University

2010

Dissertation Committee:

Professor David H. Weinberg, Advisor

Professor Todd A. Thompson

Professor Richard W. Pogge

Copyright by

Molly S. Peeples

2010

ABSTRACT

Deep in dark matter halos, galaxies are large factories that convert gas into stars. Gas is accreted from the expansive intergalactic medium (IGM); stars process this gas by fusing lighter elements into heavier ones. In this Dissertation, I combine both observations and theories from a variety of subfields of astrophysics with analytic and numerical models in an aim for a comprehensive understanding of the underlying physics of star formation feedback, galaxy chemical evolution, and the IGM.

The mass-metallicity relation is an observed tight correlation between the stellar masses and gas-phase oxygen abundances of star-forming galaxies. I show that while the intrinsic scatter in this relation is small, extreme outliers do exist; I argue that these outliers have unusual metallicities for their masses because they have unusual gas fractions for their masses. The low-mass high-metallicity galaxies appear to be nearing the end of their star formation, and thus should have abnormally small gas reservoirs with which to dilute their metals. On the other hand, the high-mass low-metallicity galaxies appear to be undergoing gas-rich galaxy mergers, implying that they have larger-than-normal amounts of gas diluting their metals.

I then show through analytic arguments that while gas fractions can have a large impact on observed metallicities, the low-redshift mass-metallicity relation is dominated by outflow properties because typical galaxies have relatively small gas fractions. Specifically, the mass-metallicity relation implies that the efficiency with which galaxies expel metals should scale steeply with galaxy mass. Combining this model with reasonable models for star formation feedback, I show that the outflow metallicity should likewise vary with galaxy mass; future measurements of wind metallicity can therefore inform models of the physics underlying galaxy winds.

The high-redshift IGM is primarily observed through the Lyman- α absorption of neutral hydrogen along the line of sight to a distant quasar. As samples of close quasar pairs increase, so does the amount of potential information in the Ly α forest transverse to the line-of-sight. Using two cosmological hydrodynamic simulations with different photoionization heating rates and thus different IGM temperature-density relations, I show that the small-scale structure in the Ly α forest along the line of sight is dominated by the current thermal state of the gas. On the other hand, the transverse signal is sensitive to—and thus could be used to place unique constraints on—the thermal history of the gas.

Finally, I investigate how a two-phase medium is treated in a suite of idealized smoothed particle hydrodynamic (SPH) simulations. I show that cold, dense spherical blobs become over-pressured relative to their hot, tenuous surroundings, arguing that this is because of an effective numerical surface tension owing to the

un-resolveable density discontinuity. I then test one proposed modification to how pressure gradients are calculated in SPH, the so-called “relative pressure SPH” (rpSPH); while rpSPH leads to a more uniform pressure across the simulation, I show that it is ultimately unstable because of its lack of momentum conservation.

Dedicated to my grandmothers

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

My mother always said it's important to try to find a place where there are people pulling for me; it's in this light that I know I have a home at Ohio State. I don't have the words to properly thank my advisor and mentor, David Weinberg, in whose steps I can only hope to follow. David has always offered sound advice and constructive criticism, both asked and un-asked for; it is his thorough approach to astronomy as an "observationally-oriented theorist" that I strive to emulate. I have learned much from Rick Pogge, from how to interpret spectra of the ISM to how to taste a glass of wine; though I consider myself primarily a theorist, Rick's lessons have ensured that I won't always be able to take interpretations of data at face value. I'm grateful to Todd Thompson—who somehow manages to always exude energy and momentum—for his insight and advice, and for our many discussions of star formation feedback. While I have learned much from Kris Stanek, I hope that I never forget that difficult problems are not always interesting, and easy does not imply boring. Scott Gaudi has always had an open door and been shrewd enough to ask what's up when I've been in his office stealing chocolate for the fourth time in an hour. As much as I may not have liked it at the time, I'm thankful for all the times Andy Gould pestered me into figuring out my "grand plan"—and for

convincing me to come to Ohio State in the first place. I am also thankful for Paul Martini and Jennifer Johnson for the many times I've wandered into their offices with random questions and actually gotten answers. I am grateful to David Will for all of his computer support, many late-night and weekend computer fixes, and apparently unfailing patience and willingness to try to find solutions that don't require restarting my computer.

Chapter 3 of this dissertation started because of a seemingly simple question from Francesco Shankar several years ago; I am glad to have been able to work with him thus far and I look forward to many more intense discussions about star formation efficiency and the redshift evolution of galaxy populations. Chapter 4 largely grew out of a seminar given at Ohio State by Joe Hennawi; I am grateful for the month spent in Germany this winter trying to apply these techniques to data. I also count myself lucky to have such knowledgeable and responsive collaborators as Romeel Davé, Dušan Kereš, Neal Katz, and Ben Oppenheimer.

I am grateful to my parents, who have managed to find the perfect balance between giving support and giving space, and to my brother, Reed, for simply being there.

The last five years would have been much less interesting and much more lonely without the company of my fellow graduate students, especially Jenn, Roberto, Jason, Jon, Kate, Jill, Subo, and Deokkeun. Finally, I am thankful for the support

and companionship of my close friends Lanya and Oliver, those of -c molly (without whose invaluable decoding skills this dissertation would have been *much* more frustrating), and the many RSI alumni who have been a constant backbone in my scientific and personal lives over the last ten years.

VITA

June 27, 1984 Born – Columbia, South Carolina, USA

1997–2001 Discovery Magnet Program, Spring Valley High School

2000 Research Science Institute

2005 B.S., Physics – Massachusetts Institute of Technology

2005–2009 Graduate Teaching and Research Associate,
The Ohio State University

2010 Presidential Fellow, The Ohio State University

PUBLICATIONS

Research Publications

1. M. S. Peeples, D. H. Weinberg, R. Davé, M. A. Fardal, and N. Katz, “Pressure Support vs. Thermal Broadening in the Lyman- α Forest I: Effects of the Equation of State on Longitudinal Structure”, MNRAS, 404, 1281 (2010).
2. M. S. Peeples, D. H. Weinberg, R. Davé, M. A. Fardal, and N. Katz, “Pressure Support vs. Thermal Broadening in the Lyman- α Forest II: Effects of the Equation of State on Transverse Structure”, MNRAS, 404, 1295 (2010).
3. C. Villforth, K. Nilsson, J. Heidt, L. O. Takalo, T. Pursimo, A. Berdyugin, E. Lindfors, M. Pasanen, M. Winiarski, M. Drozd, W. Ogloza, M. Kurpinska-Winiarska, M. Siwak, D. Koziel-Wierzbowska, C. Porowski, A. Kuzmich, J. Krzesinski, T. Kundera, J.-H. Wu, X. Zhou, Y. Efimov, K. Sadakane, M. Kamada, J. Ohlert, V.-P. Hentunen, M. Nissinen, M. Dietrich, R. J. Assef, D. W. Atlee, J. Bird, D. L. Depoy, J. Eastman, M. S. Peeples, J. Prieto, L. Watson, J. C.

- Yee, A. Liakos, P. Niarchos, K. Gazeas, S. Dogru, A. Donmez, D. Marchev, S. A. Coggins-Hill, A. Mattingly, W. C. Keel, S. Haque, A. Aungwerojwit, and N. Bergvall, “Variability and stability in blazar jets on time-scales of years: optical polarization monitoring of OJ 287 in 2005-2009”, *MNRAS*, 402, 2087 (2010).
4. M. Valtonen, K. Nilsson, C. Villforth, H. J. Lehto, L. O. Takalo, E. Lindfors, A. Sillanpää, V.-P. Hentunen, S. Mikkola, S. Zola, M. Drozd, D. Koziel, W. Ogloza, M. Kurpinska-Winiarska, M. Siwak, M. Winiarski, J. Heidt, M. Kidger, T. Pursimo, J.-H. Wu, X. Zhou, K. Sadakane, D. Marchev, M. Nissinen, P. Niarchos, A. Liakos, K. Gazeas, S. Dogru, G. Poyner, M. Dietrich, R. Assef, D. Atlee, J. Bird, D. DePoy, J. Eastman, M. S. Peeples, J. Prieto, L. Watson, and J. Yee, A. Mattingly, and J. Ohlert, “Tidally Induced Outbursts in OJ 287 during 2005–2008”, *ApJ*, 698, 781 (2009).
 5. M. S. Peeples, R. W. Pogge, and K. Z. Stanek “Outliers from the Mass-Metallicity Relation II: A Sample of Massive Metal-Poor Galaxies from SDSS”, *ApJ*, 695, 259 (2009).
 6. C. J. Grier, B. M. Peterson, M. C. Bentz, K. D. Denney, J. D. Eastman, M. Dietrich, ; R. W. Pogge, J. L. Prieto, D. L. DePoy, R. J. Assef, D. W. Atlee, J. Bird, M. E. Eyller, M. S. Peeples, R. Siverd, L. C. Watson, and J. C. Yee, “The Mass of the Black Hole in the Quasar PG 2130+099”, *ApJ*, 688, 837 (2008).
 7. M. S. Peeples, R. W. Pogge, and K. Z. Stanek “Outliers from the Mass-Metallicity Relation I: A Sample of Metal-Rich Dwarf Galaxies from SDSS”, *ApJ*, 685, 837 (2008).
 8. M. S. Peeples, K. Z. Stanek, and D. DePoy, “A Study of Stellar Photometric Variability Within the Central 4 pc of the Galactic Center with Infrared Image Subtraction”, *AcA*, 57, 173 (2007).
 9. R. Massey, C. Heymans, J. Bergé, G. Bernstein, S. Bridle, D. Clowe, H. Dahle, R. Ellis, T. Erben, M. Hettterscheidt, F. W. High, C. Hirata, H. Hoekstra, P. Hudelot, M. Jarvis, D. Johnston, K. Kuijken, V. Margoniner, R. Mandelbaum, Y. Mellier, R. Nakajima, S. Paulin-Henriksson, M. S. Peeples, C. Roat, A. Refregier, J. Rhodes, T. Schrabback, M. Schirmer, U. Seljak, E. Semboloni, and L. van Waerbeke “The Shear TEsting Programme 2: Factors affecting high precision weak lensing analyses”, *MNRAS*, 376, 13 (2007).
 10. M. S. Peeples, A. Bonanos, D. L. DePoy, K. Z. Stanek, J. Pepper, R. W. Pogge, M. Pinsonneault, and K. Sellgren, “The Nature of the Variable Galactic Center Source GCIRS 16SW Revisited: A Massive Eclipsing Binary”, *ApJL*, 654, 61

(2007).

11. M. S. Peeples and P. Martini “The Connection Between Bar Strength and Circumnuclear Dust Structure”, *ApJ*, 652, 1097 (2006).

FIELDS OF STUDY

Major Field: Astronomy

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Abstract	ii
Dedication	v
Acknowledgments	vi
Vita	ix
List of Tables	xvi
List of Figures	xvii
Chapter 1 Introduction	1
1.1 The Intergalactic Medium and Galaxy Evolution	1
1.2 Scope of this Dissertation	6
Chapter 2 Outliers from the Mass-Metallicity Relation	10
2.1 Introduction	10
2.2 Selecting Low-Mass High-Metallicity Galaxies	12
2.2.1 Main Dwarf Sample Selection	14
2.2.2 Very Low Mass Sample Selection	16
2.2.3 Measuring High Oxygen Abundances	18
2.3 Selecting High-Mass Low-Metallicity Galaxies	22
2.3.1 Measuring Low Oxygen Abundances	25
2.4 Discussion	28

2.4.1	Metal-Rich Dwarf Galaxies are Isolated	30
2.4.2	Star Formation Rates	32
2.4.3	Effective Yields and Gas Fractions	33
2.4.4	Transitional Dwarf Galaxies	36
2.4.5	Observed Metallicity of Merging Galaxies	39
2.5	Conclusions and Implications	43
Chapter 3 Balancing Outflows and Gas Dilution		71
3.1	Introduction	71
3.2	Relevant Observations	78
3.2.1	The observed $z \sim 0$ mass-metallicity relation	78
3.2.2	Observed gas fractions of $z \sim 0$ galaxies	81
3.2.3	Galaxy outflows	86
3.3	The formalism	90
3.3.1	The mass-metallicity relation	90
3.3.2	Connecting galaxies and halos	95
3.4	Models of the Mass-Metallicity Relation	98
3.5	Outflow Metallicity and Entrainment	104
3.6	Summary and Discussion	107
3.6.1	The approach: modeling a system of galaxies	107
3.6.2	Resulting constraints	108
3.6.3	The role of metal-(re)accretion	112
Chapter 4 Pressure Support vs. Thermal Broadening in the Lyman-α Forest		126
4.1	Introduction	126

4.2	Simulations	134
4.3	Physics of the Lyman- α forest	136
4.3.1	The Temperature-Density Relation	136
4.3.2	The Fluctuating Gunn-Peterson Approximation	141
4.3.3	The Ly α forest in the fiducial case	143
4.3.4	Impacts of temperature and pressure on gas evolution	145
4.4	Effects of pressure and thermal broadening on the Ly α forest	146
4.4.1	Spectra of Independent Sightlines	148
4.4.2	The 1-D Flux Power Spectrum	151
4.4.3	Flux Decrement Autocorrelation Functions	154
4.4.4	Flux Decrement Probability Distributions	156
4.4.5	Spectra of Paired Sightlines	159
4.4.6	Cross-Correlation Functions	160
4.4.7	Conditional Flux Probability Distributions	163
4.5	Conclusions	165
Chapter 5 Modeling a Two-Phase Medium in SPH		196
5.1	Introduction	196
5.2	The Momentum Equation and rpSPH	199
5.3	Hydrostatic Equilibrium	202
5.3.1	Fiducial Initial Conditions	202
5.3.2	Dependence on Resolution: N_{blob}	203
5.3.3	Dependence on Initial Over/Under-pressure	205
5.3.4	Dependence on Blob Radius: Surface Tension	205
5.3.5	Successes and Failures of rpSPH	205

Appendix A The nucleosynthetic yield and instantaneous recycled fraction	219
Appendix B Outflows, inflows, and star formation: getting the gas masses	225
Bibliography	235

LIST OF TABLES

2.1	Full sample of low-luminosity mass–metallicity outliers	63
2.1	Full sample of low-luminosity mass–metallicity outliers	64
2.1	Full sample of low-luminosity mass–metallicity outliers	65
2.2	Cuts for Selection of Main Sample of Metal-Rich Dwarf Galaxies	66
2.3	Cuts for Very Low Mass Sample Selection	67
2.4	Low-metallicity mass–metallicity outliers	68
2.4	Low-metallicity mass–metallicity outliers	69
2.5	Cuts for Selection of Massive Low-Metallicity Galaxies	70
3.1	Kewley & Ellison (2008) fits to the mass-metallicity relation	118
3.2	Cold gas fractions $\log F_g = \log(M_g/M_\star)$	123
3.3	Gas fraction relation parameters	124
3.4	Best-fit ζ_w parameters	125
4.1	Mean flux decrements and temperature-density relations	195

LIST OF FIGURES

2.1	Mass-metallicity relation with outliers marked	47
2.2	Metallicity-luminosity relation with low-mass outliers	48
2.3	SDSS images of high-metallicity dwarf galaxies	49
2.4	Cuts used in mass-metallicity plane for finding low-mass outliers . . .	50
2.5	Metallicities of dwarf galaxy outliers as measured with different $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ indicators	51
2.6	SDSS images of massive low-metallicity galaxies	52
2.7	Example cut used in luminosity-metallicity plane for finding high-mass outliers	53
2.8	Emission-line ratios of low-metallicity outliers relative to BPT diagrams of SDSS emission-line	54
2.9	Sample spectra of low-metallicity high-mass outliers.	55
2.10	Pettini & Pagel (2004) mass-metallicity relation with outliers marked	56
2.11	Residuals from the mass-metallicity relation as a function of SDSS fiber fraction	57
2.12	Low-metallicity $z \sim 0$ outliers relative to the evolution of the mass-metallicity relation.	58
2.13	Star formation rates and specific star formation rates vs. stellar masses for mass-metallicity relation outliers	59
2.14	SDSS images of high-metallicity low-mass galaxies with bright and/or blue cores	60
2.15	Mass-metallicity outliers on the color-magnitude diagram.	61

2.16	Residuals from the mass-metallicity relation as a function of specific star formation rate.	62
3.1	Best-fit mass-metallicity relations measured from different metallicity indicators	114
3.2	Gas fractions and gas masses as a function of stellar mass.	115
3.3	Halo mass and virial velocity as a function of stellar mass	116
3.4	Gas fractions required to reproduce the Tremonti et al. (2004) mass-metallicity relation with varying power-law slopes of $\zeta_w(v_{\text{vir}})$	117
3.5	$\Delta\chi^2$ contours and best-fit ζ_w models for the T04 mass-metallicity relation with $\zeta_w = (v_0/v_{\text{vir}})^{-b} + \zeta_{w,0}$	118
3.6	Required ζ_w to reproduce the T04 mass-metallicity relation with varying gas fraction relations	119
3.7	Best-fitting ζ_w for mass-metallicity relations derived from different metallicity indicators	120
3.8	Same as Figures 3.4 and 3.6, but for the Denicoló et al. (2002) mass-metallicity relation.	121
3.9	Wind metallicities for the T04 and D02 mass-metallicity relations	122
4.1	Temperature-overdensity plane for the fiducial simulation at $z = 3$	171
4.2	Temperature-overdensity plane at $z = 2.4$, with distributions of temperature and overdensity in the fiducial and H4 simulations.	172
4.3	IGM temperature-density relation evolution from simulations, observations, and analytic considerations.	173
4.4	Slices of the fiducial simulation at $z = 3$ showing the relative distributions of stars, gas, and dark matter.	174
4.5	H I density-weighted section of the fiducial simulation at $z = 2.4$ with three paired sightlines marked.	175
4.6	Physical quantities and Ly α forest spectra along four sightlines at $z = 3$	176
4.7	Temperature and density distributions of gas at $z = 3$ in the fiducial at H4 simulations.	177

4.8	Distributions of gas and dark matter overdensities at $z = 3$ in the fiducial, H4, and low-resolution simulations.	178
4.9	Comparison of spectra along the sightlines labelled in Figure 4.4, isolating different physical effects.	179
4.10	Comparison of spectra along paired sightlines as a function of transverse separation for the fiducial and H4 simulations	180
4.11	The 1-D flux power spectrum $z = 4.0$ for the fiducial and H4 simulations as compared to observations.	181
4.12	Same as Figure 4.11 but at $z = 3.0$	182
4.13	Same as Figure 4.11 but at $z = 2.4$	183
4.14	The 1-D flux power spectrum at $z = 3$ for fiducial and H4 gas with different imposed T - ρ relations.	184
4.15	Normalized flux decrement autocorrelation functions for different combinations of overdensity distributions and T - ρ relations.	185
4.16	Flux decrement probability distributions in linear bins of D for the fiducial and H4 simulations	186
4.17	Flux decrement probability distributions in logarithmic bins of D for the fiducial and H4 simulations with imposed T - ρ relations.	187
4.18	Flux decrement cross-correlation functions at $z = 2.4$ for the fiducial and H4 simulations at different transverse separations.	188
4.19	Normalized cross-correlation functions for $\Delta v = 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ as a function of the transverse separation at $z = 2.4$	189
4.20	Normalized cross-correlation functions for $\Delta v = 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ as a function of the transverse separation at $z = 4, 3,$ and 2	190
4.21	Normalized cross-correlation functions showing the anisotropy of the Ly α forest as a function of $\Delta v = H\Delta r$ at $z = 2.4$	191
4.22	Normalized cross-correlation functions showing the anisotropy of the Ly α forest as a function of $\Delta v = H\Delta r$ at $z = 4, 3,$ and 2	192
4.23	Flux decrement difference probability distributions at $z = 2.4$ for the fiducial, H4, and low resolution simulations.	192

4.24	Probability distributions for differences in flux decrement rank for the fiducial and H4 gas distributions with imposed T - ρ relations at $z = 4$, 3, and 2.	193
4.25	Probability distributions for differences in flux decrement rank for the fiducial and H4 gas distributions $z = 2.4$	194
5.1	Pressure versus radius at $t = 0$ and 1 Gyr for fiducial blob sampled with Poisson, random-in-cells, and grid initial conditions	208
5.2	Time sequence of pressure as a function of radius for the fiducial case	209
5.3	Pressure versus radius at late times for a range of N_{blob}	210
5.4	$(\rho T)_{\text{amb},i}$ relative to $(\rho T)_{\text{blob},i}$ as a function of time for a range of N_{blob}	211
5.5	$(\rho T)_{\text{amb},i}$ relative to $(\rho T)_{\text{blob},i}$ as a function of time for different $(\rho T)_i/(\rho T)_{\text{eq}}$	212
5.6	$(\rho T)_{\text{amb},i}$ relative to $(\rho T)_{\text{blob},i}$ as a function of R_{blob} in Gadget-2 and rpSPH.	213
5.7	Snapshots at $t = 4$ in Gadget-2 and rpSPH	214
5.8	$(\rho T)_{\text{amb},i}$ relative to $(\rho T)_{\text{blob},i}$ as a function of time and N_{ngb} in Gadget-2 and rpSPH.	215
5.9	Blob mass loss as a function of time in rpSPH	216
5.10	Distribution of temperatures at late times in Gadget-2 and rpSPH for different N_{ngb}	217
5.11	Distribution of the x -component of particle velocities at late times in Gadget-2 and rpSPH for different N_{ngb}	218
A.1	Nucleosynthetic yields and instantaneous recycled fractions for different star-formation histories	224
B.1	Gas accretion rates, star formation rates, and cold gas accretion fractions as a function of stellar mass with varying outflows and specific star formation rates.	232
B.2	Different models for specific star formation rates as a function of stellar mass.	233
B.3	Star formation efficiency as a function of stellar mass.	234

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. THE INTERGALACTIC MEDIUM AND GALAXY EVOLUTION

Galaxies are “island universes” (Kant 1755) in a sea of gas, dark matter, and radiation. The growth of the primordial fluctuations in this sea left over from the Big Bang is set by cosmological parameters, such as the total ratio of dark matter to baryonic matter (Weinberg 1972; Peebles 1993; Tegmark et al. 2004). As the universe ages, it cools and expands; gravitational instabilities arising from the smoothly fluctuating density variations eventually lead to dark matter in the densest peaks collapsing (Silk 1968; Zel’Dovich 1970), bringing gas along with it (Rees & Ostriker 1977; White & Rees 1978). The gas cools at the centers of these newly-born dark matter halos, eventually forming the first stars and galaxies (Silk 1977; Bromm et al. 2002).

At $z \sim 2$ (when the universe was several billion years old), most of the gas in the universe is not yet in galaxies, but rather in the low-density intergalactic medium (IGM, Weinberg et al. 1997b). As galaxies live in deep potential wells, this gas falls

into galaxies' dark matter halos, eventually accreting onto the galaxies themselves (Gunn & Gott 1972). In massive halos, gas may be shock-heated as it is accreted, slowing the rate at which it is assimilated into the galaxy's interstellar medium (ISM) and converted into stars—if it is able to cool at all. In less massive halos, however, gas may be accreted onto the galaxy without any significant heating (Kereš et al. 2005, 2009). The efficiency with which a galaxy is able to convert accreted gas into stars can therefore depend sensitively on the mass of its dark matter halo.

Hence, galaxies are comprised of stars, gas, and dark matter (Slipher 1917; Hubble 1926; Rubin et al. 1985). The ISM is a complex multi-phase medium including hot ionized gas, cold atomic gas, dust, and dust (Goldsmith et al. 1969; McKee & Ostriker 1977; Draine & Lee 1984). As the turbulent ISM cools and clumps, giant clouds of molecular gas are formed; these clouds are the sites of star formation (Larson 1985). Stars fuse hydrogen into helium (e.g., Bethe 1939). When massive stars have burned all of their hydrogen, they explode as supernovae while fusing lighter elements into heavier ones such as oxygen, neon, and magnesium (Hoyle 1954; Burbidge, Burbidge, Fowler, & Hoyle 1957; Aller & Greenstein 1960; Wallerstein 1962). These “metals” (that is, elements made in stars and supernovae rather than in the Big Bang) are returned to the galaxy's ISM and can be locked up in stars after subsequent episodes of star formation. Many supernova explosions in a single galaxy can generate a galaxy-scale outflow, expelling metals back into the IGM. Low mass stars live longer than their massive cousins and generate a

different menagerie of elements in their death throes, leaving a signature of a galaxy’s star formation history in the metal content of its stars and ISM (Tinsley 1979; Matteucci & Francois 1992; McWilliam 1997). For example, α -element (e.g., oxygen) production is from the death of short-lived stars (Wallerstein 1962) and therefore traces star production. Hence, the α -element abundances in stars can be used to set an “age” of the stellar population, while gas-phase abundances are susceptible to subsequent changes in the galaxy’s gas content (Dalcanton 2007). The observed tight correlation between galaxy stellar masses and gas-phase oxygen abundances (the “mass-metallicity relation”; Tremonti et al. 2004) can, for instance, be used to place constraints on how such changes in galaxy gas content vary from galaxy to galaxy. Interpreting observations of galaxies, however, in terms of physical quantities such as “stellar mass” and “metallicity” is not straightforward nor entirely understood (Kewley & Ellison 2008; Conroy et al. 2009).

While generations of stars pass in galaxies, the large scale structure of the universe is still evolving, with gravity dominating the formation of structure (Blumenthal et al. 1984). Structure formation evolves hierarchically, with dark matter collapsing on smaller scales (such as those of galaxies) earlier, and on larger scales (e.g., clusters of galaxies) at later times (White & Frenk 1991). As groups of galaxies are formed, smaller dark matter halos merge into larger ones. Galaxies, therefore, merge as the universe ages (Barnes & Hernquist 1992; Kauffmann et al. 1993), forming descendants that are more massive than could be formed by slow

cosmic gas accretion. Merging galaxies are observed at low (Zwicky 1956, 1959) and high (Conselice et al. 2008) redshifts, with the rate peaking earlier for more massive galaxies. The merging of two—or more—gas rich galaxies is a cataclysmic event, driving massive amounts of gas to the remnant center and inciting huge amounts of star formation in a relatively small region over a relatively short period of time (Barnes & Hernquist 1996; Hopkins et al. 2006; Whitmore et al. 2010). Yet at late times, the most massive galaxies are “red and dead” and have long since ceased forming stars (Baldry et al. 2004; Faber et al. 2007). Furthermore, the overall efficiency with which galaxies form stars over cosmic time is surprisingly low, with only $\sim 10\%$ of available gas converted into stars. Thus some process or processes must not only be slowing star formation, but, in some cases, altogether stopping it.

The most obvious culprit is feedback from supernovae, as these explosions could deposit massive amounts of energy, momentum, and radiation into the ISM (Chevalier & Clegg 1985; Murray et al. 2005). Though the exact mechanisms by which supernovae might couple with the ISM are poorly understood at best, the most actively star forming galaxies (which, likewise, should have the highest supernova rates) are seen to be expelling large-scale winds, suggesting that supernova feedback could be altogether removing the fuel for star formation (Axon & Taylor 1978; Heckman et al. 1990; Strickland & Stevens 2000; Strickland & Heckman 2009). But these arguments don’t hold up in the more massive halos: the velocities with which supernova eject gas are not expected to be enough to allow the gas to escape

deeper potential wells. Moreover, supernova feedback only works while there are still supernovae—some other process is required to prevent subsequent episodes of star formation.

Supermassive black holes, which reside at the centers of all massive galaxies, potentially provide an answer to this conundrum. Black holes grow by accreting matter, but as gas falls into a black hole, some of its gravitational energy is converted into radiation (Salpeter 1964). Since it takes a relatively small amount of fuel to power a growing black hole, or active galactic nucleus (AGN), these energy sources may be responsible for preventing gas in massive galaxies from cooling and forming stars (Di Matteo et al. 2005; Hopkins et al. 2006; Croton et al. 2006). When large amounts of fuel are available—as was common when the universe was younger—AGN can emit enough light to be the brightest objects in the universe. Furthermore, bright AGN are observed at very high redshifts (Fan et al. 2001, 2003). Conveniently, such quasars act as lighthouses, allowing us to observe the IGM even though it does not emit enough light to be observed directly with modern telescopes. Gas in the IGM along the line-of-sight to a distant quasar absorbs light in the strongest transition of neutral hydrogen, the Lyman- α transition; because the IGM is mostly ionized, the resulting spectrum appears as a thick forest of absorption lines, lending it the name of the “Ly α forest” (Gunn & Peterson 1965; Sargent et al. 1980; Rauch 1998). Though hydrodynamic simulations of cold dark matter cosmological models have achieved remarkable success at helping interpret the observed Lyman- α

forest in terms of a cosmic web of physically interesting quantities (Cen et al. 1994; Hernquist et al. 1996; Miralda-Escudé et al. 1996), several aspects of the observed IGM remain difficult to explain. Of these, the most confusing is that the inferred gas temperatures are hotter than can easily be explained by summing the contributions from known sources of radiation (Katz et al. 1996; McDonald et al. 2000; Lidz et al. 2009). Likewise, while hydrodynamic simulations and analytic arguments have shed light on the need and plausibility of star formation and AGN feedback, the underlying physics is not well understood and simulations do not currently have the needed dynamic range and resolution to model feedback directly.

1.2. SCOPE OF THIS DISSERTATION

In this Dissertation, I combine both observations and theories from a variety of subfields of astrophysics with analytic and numerical models with the goal of a comprehensive understanding of the underlying physics of star formation feedback, galaxy chemical evolution, and the intergalactic medium.

In Chapter 2 I identify two populations of galaxies that are extreme outliers from the well-established mass-metallicity relation; by appealing to other physical properties of these galaxies, I argue that they have unusual metallicities for their masses because they likewise have extreme gas fractions for their masses. Specifically, high-metallicity low-mass galaxies have colors, morphologies, and star formation

rates that indicate they are nearing the end of star formation, and therefore have less gas to dilute their metals. Low-metallicity massive galaxies, on the other hand, are all morphologically disturbed with high star formation rates, implying that their observed low-metallicities owe to the recent influx of gas from the merger.

I expand upon this work in Chapter 3, where I construct a new analytic formalism for modeling the mass-metallicity relation by connecting galaxy masses, gas fractions, and outflow properties. By constraining the model with low-redshift observations, I show that $z \sim 0$ gas fractions are low enough that the morphology of the mass-metallicity relation is dominated by the efficiency with which galaxy winds remove metals from star forming galaxies, and that this efficiency must scale steeply with galaxy mass. By combining these constraints with theoretical models for the efficiency with which gas is expelled from galaxies, I show how measurements of outflow metallicity as a function of galaxy mass can be used to gain insight into the underlying physics of star formation feedback.

I turn to higher redshifts and the IGM in Chapter 4. To separate the effects of gas pressure support and thermal broadening on the Lyman- α forest, I compare spectra extracted from two smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) simulations evolved with different photoionization heating rates (and thus different Jeans scales) and from the pressureless dark matter distribution, imposing different temperature-density relations on the evolved particle distributions. I show that the size of structures along the line of sight is primarily set by thermal broadening,

whereas the extent of structures transverse to the line of sight is sensitive to the thermal history of the gas: the coherence along neighboring sightlines is markedly higher for the hotter, higher pressure simulation. Moreover, higher pressure decreases the redshift-space anisotropy of the flux correlation function, while higher thermal broadening increases the anisotropy. In contrast to the longitudinal (line-of-sight) structure of the Ly α forest, the transverse structure on small scales is dominated by pressure effects rather than thermal broadening. With the rapid recent growth in the number of known close quasar pairs, paired line-of-sight observations offer a promising new route to probe the IGM temperature-density relation and test the unexpectedly high temperatures that have been inferred from single sightline analyses.

Finally, in Chapter 5 I show that while SPH may be extremely successful at modeling continuously varying fluids such as the IGM, in its traditional formulation, a numerical surface tension is introduced at strong density jumps, such as would be found for cold gas flowing in or out of a hot halo. This leads to the pressure of cold blobs being much higher than the hot ambient medium, which can lead to overcooling and thus more star formation in astrophysical simulations. I test one proposed solution to this problem, “relative pressure SPH” (Abel 2010); while rpSPH is fairly successful at solving the overpressure problem, I find that it is unstable due to its lack of momentum conservation.

Chapter 2 is published as a pair of papers in *The Astrophysical Journal*, and Chapter 4 is published as a pair of papers in *The Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*. Chapter 3 is to be submitted for publication soon, and Chapter 5 is part of a paper to be submitted for publication.

CHAPTER 2

OUTLIERS FROM THE MASS-METALLICITY RELATION

2.1. INTRODUCTION

Star-forming galaxies fall on a luminosity–metallicity relation such that more luminous galaxies tend to have higher gas-phase metallicities (Lequeux et al. 1979; Garnett & Shields 1987). Tremonti et al. (2004) measured this relation for 53400 star-forming galaxies from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) Data Release 4 (DR4, Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2006), estimating the gas phase oxygen abundance, $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$, from H II region emission lines as the surrogate for “metallicity.” Using estimates of the galaxy stellar masses derived from the techniques of Kauffmann et al. (2003), Tremonti et al. showed that the scatter in metallicity decreases (to, e.g., a $1\text{-}\sigma$ spread of ± 0.15 dex in $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ at $9.5 < \log(M_\star/M_\odot) < 9.6$ at $z \sim 0$), when galaxy stellar mass replaces luminosity. Because most star-forming galaxies *do* lie on a mass–metallicity locus, we can also learn about the gas-phase metallicity evolution of galaxies by studying the properties of galaxies that do *not* fall on the relation. In this Chapter, we show that extreme outliers from the mass-metallicity relation have metallicities that differ drastically

from the mean relation because they have anormal gas reservoirs with which to dilute their metals, indicating that gas fractions can play a crucial role in setting the mass-metallicity relation, a point which we address on more theoretical grounds in Chapter 3.

Despite the locus of galaxies in the mass–metallicity plane having intrinsic scatter, in the absence of good quality spectra it has become an increasingly common practice to deduce or assign metallicities to galaxies based simply on their luminosities. In particular, the idea persists that dwarf galaxies are always “metal-poor,” certainly a fair assumption in the Local Group—and luminous galaxies are always “metal-rich”. In this study however, we will show that there is a significant population of low-mass galaxies with high gas-phase oxygen abundances, and high-mass galaxies with low metallicities, relative to the mass-metallicity relation defined by Tremonti et al. (2004). As shown in Figure 2.1, we find both high- and low-metallicity outliers from the mass-metallicity relation. We find 41 low-mass high-metallicity outliers with $8.6 < 12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) < 9.3$ over a range of $7.4 < \log(M_*/M_\odot) < 10$ and 42 low-metallicity high-mass galaxies with masses ranging from $\log(M_*/M_\odot) \sim 9.4$ to 11.1 and offsets from the central mass–metallicity relation of -0.3 to -0.85 dex.

We explain how we selected these samples and verified the galaxies’ outlier status in § 2.2 and 2.3. In § 2.4 we describe the physical properties of these galaxies. We explain why we predict that the metal-rich dwarf galaxies should have relatively

low gas masses while the luminous metal-poor galaxies are likely merging or post-merging systems. Specifically, in § 2.4.4 we discuss the evidence for metal-rich dwarf galaxies galaxies being so-called “transition” dwarf galaxies. In § 2.4.5, we outline why merging galaxies can provide a natural explanation for why there is a large population of luminous low-metallicity galaxies. We summarize our conclusions and state some implications of these findings in § 2.5.

2.2. SELECTING LOW-MASS HIGH-METALLICITY GALAXIES

We began with the sample of ~ 110000 star-forming galaxies with measured gas-phase oxygen abundances and stellar masses from Tremonti et al. (2004). High-metallicity outliers from the mass–metallicity locus can be due to main three causes, and our cuts were taken with these in mind. First, some galaxies can spuriously appear to be underluminous for their mass. Examples include highly inclined galaxies subject to strong internal extinction and H II regions in larger galaxies that SDSS has mistakenly flagged as a galaxy. Among relatively nearby galaxies (e.g., those in the Virgo cluster) some have large peculiar velocities relative to the Hubble flow, leading to a misestimation of their distance modulus and thus absolute magnitude. Secondly, rogue outliers can have spuriously high estimated metallicities; the galaxy, for example, may not be at high enough redshift to have the strongly constraining [O II] $\lambda 3727, 9 \text{ \AA}$ emission lines in the SDSS bandpass.

Also, the strengths of the [O II] and [O III] lines paradoxically *decrease* with oxygen abundance, so at low signal-to-noise, the metallicity can be overestimated due to underestimated line fluxes. Finally, the object can be an honest outlier; these are the objects we want in our final sample. We found that a large number of cuts in different parameter spaces is useful for automatically rejecting many objects which would otherwise have to be thrown out by visual inspection. We ran two searches on the full Tremonti et al. sample for high-metallicity outliers. For the first, we were very conservative with our cuts so as to be certain that the remaining galaxies are both statistically significant and not spurious. However, due to significant contamination at low luminosities, this “main” sample has no members with $\log M_\star < 9.15$. We therefore did a separate, less stringent search for the lowest luminosity outliers; to distinguish it from the main sample, we refer to this sample of lower mass galaxies as the “very low mass” sample.

Figure 2.2 shows where our sample falls in the $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) - M_B$ plane; all galaxy images are shown in Figure 2.3 and summary information is presented in Table 2.1. For reference, in Figure 2.2 we plot the Small and Large Magellanic Clouds and Milky Way using M_B from Karachentsev (2005). We recalculated $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ for the SMC and LMC using the line ratios reported by Russell & Dopita (1990) of six H II regions in the SMC and four H II regions in the LMC and the relation $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 9.37 + 2.03 \times \text{N2} + 1.26 \times \text{N2}^2 + 0.32 \times \text{N2}^3$, where $\text{N2} \equiv \log([\text{N II}]\lambda 6584/\text{H}\alpha)$ (Pettini & Pagel 2004; Kewley & Ellison 2008). We

then transformed these abundances onto the Tremonti et al. (2004) scale using the formulae given by Kewley & Ellison (2008), resulting in average metallicities of 8.21 and 8.39 for the SMC and LMC, respectively. The Milky Way is also plotted for reference at the Solar oxygen abundance of 8.86 (Delahaye & Pinsonneault 2006).¹

2.2.1. MAIN DWARF SAMPLE SELECTION

Table 2.2 summarizes our selection of the main sample of 24 metal-rich low-mass galaxies. Spiral galaxies are known to have radial metallicity gradients such that the nuclear abundances are higher than averages over whole galaxies. Thus, if only a small fraction of the galaxy is within the SDSS spectroscopic 3'' diameter fibers, the measured metallicity can appear to be artificially high relative to other galaxies. Following Tremonti et al. (2004), we make an initial cut by requiring that the fraction of the galaxy covered by the fiber to be greater than 10%. (In our final cut, we follow Michel-Dansac et al. (2008) and change this lower bound to 20%, which only eliminates two of the galaxies contained in the penultimate sample listed in Table 2.2.) We wanted the sample to be statistically significant, so outliers were then determined via a series of cuts in the $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ versus absolute B -band magnitude (M_B), g -band (M_g), and stellar mass (M_\star) planes, as demonstrated with M_\star in Figure 2.4. For example, we divided the 52477 objects with SDSS magnitude

¹We note that, unlike the other abundances plotted in Figure 2.2, the Solar abundance is neither a nebular abundance nor the abundance within the central ~ 5 kpc of the Galaxy.

errors < 0.1 mag in all bands into bins of M_B of width $\Delta M_B = 0.4$ mag; in each bin we kept the 2.5% with the highest $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$. We likewise took bins of $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ of width 0.1 dex and kept 2.5% of the objects with the faintest M_B . Similar cuts were made with M_g (binsize $\Delta M_g = 0.4$ mag) and $\log M_\star$ (binsize of $\Delta \log M_\star = 0.1$ dex). M_g was calculated from the SDSS g -band magnitude and the spectroscopic redshift, M_B was calculated using the low-resolution spectral templates of Assef et al. 2008, and the stellar masses from the Tremonti et al. sample were measured using a combination of SDSS colors and spectra as described by Kauffmann et al. (2003). Only 58 objects survived this series of cuts.

At this point, we made a redshift cut: galaxies must have $z > 0.024$ in order to have the [O II] $\lambda\lambda 3727, 9\text{\AA}$ emission line pair in their SDSS spectrum, and as this is a highly constraining line for the metallicity, we determined that it should be in the spectrum in order to remove a possible source of systematics and so that we can measure the metallicity with a diagnostic that uses this line. Seven $z < 0.024$ galaxies pass our subsequent $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ error and visual inspection cuts; after studying their spectra, as discussed below, we chose to keep these galaxies in our main sample. We also forced the cited $\pm 1\sigma$ error in $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ to be less than 0.05 dex; metallicities with large uncertainties are obviously more likely to be spurious than ones with small uncertainties. Unsurprisingly, the $z > 0.024$ redshift cut (after all of the other cuts) also removed any galaxies with fiber fractions < 0.1 which would have survived to that stage. We find, however, that this large

number of cuts in various parameter spaces dramatically reduced the number of objects that had to be removed “by eye.” The final visual-inspection cut removed only two objects with nearby potential photometric contaminations. Finally, we re-examined the fiber fraction cut; following Michel-Dansac et al. (2008) we allowed the lower-limit fiber fraction to be 20% (excluding two objects from the sample). The final exclusion was a barred galaxy with a diameter of $\sim 10''$; the SDSS fiber size is $3''$, but this galaxy is labeled as having a fiber fraction of $\sim 60\%$. This galaxy probably has spuriously low SDSS Petrosian magnitudes. The 24 galaxies in this main sample have a range of fiber fractions between 25% and 60% and a redshift range of $0.007 < z < 0.048$.

2.2.2. VERY LOW MASS SAMPLE SELECTION

It is obvious from Figure 2.2 that the selection of our main sample artificially imposes a lower mass cutoff. This does not mean that there is not a statistically significant sample of interesting galaxies with $M_B > -17$; it just means that there are more contaminating objects with measured high metallicities in the low-luminosity regime than at brighter magnitudes. That is, the most extreme outliers with $M_B < -17$ in one parameter space (e.g., the $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ vs. M_B plane) are not also outliers in one of the others (e.g., the $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ vs. $\log M_\star$ plane). The *true* very low luminosity mass–metallicity outliers therefore have lower abundances than these spurious outliers. We therefore did a separate search for high-metallicity

galaxies at extremely low luminosities and masses, as summarized in Table 2.3. We chose to not apply a fiber fraction cut for this sample because lower luminosity galaxies are preferentially closer and therefore subtend a larger angle on the sky, making it more difficult for a substantial fraction of the galaxy to be within the 3'' SDSS fiber diameter. We therefore began the selection with a magnitude error cut, like the one for the main sample. We also removed objects with fiber fractions > 0.2 occupying the parameter space already excluded by the main sample: any objects with M_B brighter than -17 mag, $\log M_\star > 9.15$, and a high $\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ at the 95% level with respect to M_\star were excluded. The cuts in $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ relative to M_B , M_g and M_\star are all less stringent than for the main sample, but because for this sample we are interested in the *very* low mass objects, we took a strong (99% level) cut in M_\star relative to $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$. Six galaxies were excluded due to metallicity re-estimation considerations (as discussed below). Three of the remaining galaxies are potentially members of the Virgo cluster; of these, only two remain clear outliers from the M_B -metallicity locus when their distance moduli are shifted to the Virgo value of 30.74 magnitudes (Ebeling et al. 1998). (We do not attempt to correct the stellar mass estimates due to the effects of peculiar velocity.) Finally, the 95% high (O/H) with respect to M_g cut excludes the galaxy IC 225 from the sample, which is pointed out by Gu et al. (2006) to have a relatively high metallicity and a compact blue core. As this galaxy passes all of the other cuts and is clearly interesting, we added it back to the sample, raising the total number of galaxies in the very low

mass sample to 17 and the full sample to 41. The very low mass sample has fiber fractions ranging from 0.04 to 0.45; more than half of the 17 galaxies in this sample have fiber fractions below 0.1 and only 5 are above 0.2. Also, none of these galaxies would have survived the main sample redshift cut, as the very low mass galaxies occupy the redshift range $0.00249 < z < 0.0227$, with the most nearby objects being only ~ 12 Mpc away.

2.2.3. MEASURING HIGH OXYGEN ABUNDANCES

Are these 41 galaxies true outliers from the mass–metallicity relation, or are they just the tail of the scatter of the Tremonti et al. (2004) measurements? As a first check, the galaxies fall where expected on the standard Baldwin, Phillips, & Terlevich (BPT) line-diagnostic diagrams for $\log([\text{O III}] \lambda 5007/\text{H}\beta)$ vs. $\log([\text{N II}] \lambda 6548/\text{H}\alpha)$ and $\log([\text{S II}] \lambda \lambda 6717 + 31/\text{H}\alpha)$ (Baldwin et al. 1981; Kewley et al. 2006b). We note that there are several complications with measuring high metallicities using visible wavelength spectra (see Bresolin 2006 for a thorough review). The main problem is that cooling is more efficient at high metallicities, which translates into lower nebular temperatures and hence weaker $[\text{O II}]$ and $[\text{O III}]$ visible-wavelength lines, with the primary cooling load shifting to the far-infrared fine structure emission lines that cannot be readily observed. The result is that at high abundances the visible wavelength spectra become increasingly insensitive to changes in $\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$. In fact, some diagnostics, like the traditional R_{23} line index, effectively saturate at high

metallicity (Kewley & Ellison 2008), making it rather difficult to accurately measure even relative abundances. Because we would like to verify the high estimated oxygen abundances and we cannot reproduce the Tremonti et al. abundance calculations, which are based on a Bayesian statistical method, we measured $\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ in our galaxies using two recommended methods from Kewley & Ellison (2008).

Another possible source of systematic inaccuracy in the abundance estimates is the treatment of extinction corrections. The corrections traditionally applied use the H I Balmer decrement and assume a simple uniform foreground obscuring screen model like that used for stars to estimate A_V and correct the other emission lines. It is expected, however, that extinction towards extended sources like H II regions is better described as a clumpy screen, such as in the turbulent screen models of Fischera & Dopita (2005). In these, use of a simple screen tends to systematically *overestimate* the extinction correction for the [O II] $\lambda\lambda 3727, 29\text{\AA}$ emission line, leading to a systematic *underestimate* of the gas-phase oxygen abundance. In all of our galaxies the H I Balmer decrement measurements are consistent with low A_V ($\lesssim 0.5$) for a simple screen extinction model, so this is not a big effect compared to other sources of measurement error given the attenuation curves in Fischera & Dopita (2005).

Kewley & Ellison have measured the gas-phase metallicities in star forming galaxies from SDSS using ten different methods, including that of Tremonti et al. (2004); they also provide average relations relating each pair of methods. While no

one metallicity estimate is strictly believable—i.e., the *true* Oxygen-to-Hydrogen ratio—the *relative* measurements are generally robust (Kewley & Ellison 2008). Using the Data Release 6 SDSS spectra (Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2008), we subtracted the underlying stellar continuum using the STARLIGHT program (Cid Fernandes et al. 2005). We then calculated $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ using the revised Kewley & Dopita (2002) method given in Equation (A3) of Kewley & Ellison (2008),

$$\begin{aligned} \log([\text{N II}]/[\text{O II}]) = & 1106.8660 - 532.1451Z \\ & + 96.37326Z^2 - 7.8106123Z^3 + 0.32928247Z^4, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

where $Z \equiv 12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$. Like Kewley & Ellison, we found the roots of this equation using the `fz_roots` program in IDL. We also measured the metallicity using the “O3N2” method of Pettini & Pagel (2004), as recommended by Kewley & Ellison, where

$$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.73 - 0.32 \times \log \left(\frac{[\text{O III}]\lambda 5007/\text{H}\beta}{[\text{N II}]\lambda 6584/\text{H}\alpha} \right). \quad (2.2)$$

We choose to not use the R_{23} diagnostic for measuring $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ because it is known to be difficult to calibrate at these abundances (Kewley & Dopita 2002). In particular, while the seventeen $z > 0.024$ galaxies in our main sample span ~ 0.2 dex on the Tremonti et al. scale, they span ~ 0.6 dex when their metallicities are calculated using the R_{23} methods of either McGaugh (1991) or Zaritsky et al.

(1994), reflecting the fact that the R_{23} parameter essentially saturates at high oxygen abundances (Bresolin 2007).

The oxygen abundances for our 41 galaxies are plotted against these adopted metallicities in Figure 2.5. The dotted line indicates equal measurements; the other two lines are the empirically determined relations from Kewley & Ellison. The galaxies in our sample fall preferentially above the relation for the Pettini & Pagel method, but surprisingly those galaxies for which it is measurable fall *below* the relation for the Kewley & Dopita method. One possible explanation for this discrepancy is that because [O II] and [N II] are widely separated in wavelength, a misestimation of the extinction or a poorly fitted continuum (especially for the weak [O II] emission line) can lead to underestimated abundances. Specifically, there is often a degeneracy when fitting the stellar continuum between the extinction and the stellar population. While the continuum fitting for our spectra are fairly good (i.e., they exhibit low residuals after the stellar template is subtracted), we tested the sensitivity to the continuum level at [O II] $\lambda 3727\text{\AA}$ by calculating the Kewley & Dopita metallicity when the continuum is over- and underestimated; the mean of these two extreme metallicities is still systematically larger than expected by the mean relation, implying that the shift is not due to continuum fitting error. We quantify the differences between the Pettini & Pagel and Kewley & Dopita methods by examining the product of the vertical displacement of each galaxy (for an optimally fit continuum) from the two Kewley & Ellison relations; only one galaxy in

the main sample has a significantly high Tremonti et al. metallicity relative to both of the other indicators. However, this $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ was still high enough that even when the Tremonti et al. metallicity was replaced with the one expected from either relation, the galaxy still passes the cuts in both the M_g - and M_\star -metallicity planes. While the $z < 0.024$ galaxies do not have measurable [O II] (and hence we cannot use the Kewley & Dopita diagnostic for them), the low redshift sample occupies a similar part of the Tremonti et al. versus Pettini & Pagel parameter space as the galaxies in the main sample. For the very low-mass sample of galaxies, out of the 22 galaxies which passed our visual inspection test, we excluded 6 because they were more than 0.1 dex above the Pettini & Pagel relation from Kewley & Ellison; this is actually a more stringent cut than used for the main sample because several of the galaxies in the main sample with > 0.1 dex deviations from the Pettini & Pagel relation have compensating negative deviations relative to the Kewley & Dopita scale. We interpret these results to mean that the 41 galaxies we have identified are true high-metallicity low-mass outliers from the mass–metallicity relation.

2.3. SELECTING HIGH-MASS LOW-METALLICITY GALAXIES

We began with a sample of ~ 110000 star-forming galaxies from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) Data Release 4 (Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2006) with gas-phase abundances measured by Tremonti et al. (2004) and stellar masses derived

using the techniques of Kauffmann et al. (2003). High-luminosity outliers from the mass-metallicity relation can be found in the low-metallicity region of parameter space for one of two reasons: either they have spuriously low derived metallicities or they are genuine outliers. (The third possibility of an object having a spuriously high measured luminosity is much less likely.) In general, the strengths of the visible-wavelength oxygen forbidden [O II] and [O III] emission lines increase as the oxygen abundance decreases; hence, it is possible for a bright galaxy with a weak active galactic nucleus (AGN) component to appear to have a low oxygen abundance due to contribution from the AGN itself. Likewise, an otherwise “red and dead” galaxy with strong [O II] emission might be labeled as star-forming and, in the Bayesian analysis of Tremonti et al., be assigned an artificially low metallicity. We therefore selected our sample of massive low-metallicity galaxies by first ensuring that they are outliers in the luminosity– and mass–metallicity parameter spaces and then following up with several line-ratio diagnostic tests in an attempt to guarantee that their oxygen abundances relative to the rest of the sample are indeed believable. Images of the galaxies in our final sample are shown in Figure 2.6 and summary information is provided in Table 2.4. As only two of the galaxies in Figure 2.6 are clearly undisturbed spirals, we note these two galaxies in Table 2.4, Figure 2.1, and subsequent figures with “§” symbols.

One possible contamination source of these seemingly bright metal-poor galaxies is a low-level AGN, such as a low-ionization nuclear emission-line region

(LINER). While it is possible for galaxies with weak AGN activity to *also* have low oxygen abundances, we choose to not try to disentangle these two effects on the emission line fluxes. Using the line fluxes measured by Tremonti et al. (2004)², we put these galaxies on the standard Baldwin, Phillips, & Terlevich (BPT) 1981 diagrams. In particular, as shown in Figure 2.8, we find that about half of these outliers have strong enough [O I] λ 6300 to place them in the “AGN” region of the BPT diagram. (We note that while the Tremonti et al. (2004) galaxies were chosen to be star-forming based on where they fall in the [O III]/H β v. [N II]/H α plane, 3.4% of the parent sample galaxies fall in the AGN region of the [O III]/H β v. [O I]/H α plane.) As expected, the strong-[O I] galaxies also fall close to the “composite” H II–AGN boundary as defined by Kewley et al. (2006b) in the [O III]/H β v. [N II]/H α plane. Visual inspection of the spectra and images of these bogus outliers reveals that many of them are quite red, with only strong [O II] λ 3727 and perhaps weak H α emission being suggestive of ongoing star formation. Because [O I] λ 6300 is a relatively weak line and many of the outliers are clustered near the the Kewley et al. (2006b) boundary, we kept galaxies whose [O I]/H α ratio is within $2\text{-}\sigma$ of the H II–AGN boundary and whose spectra passed a visual inspection test for, e.g., clear H β emission. Representative spectra are shown in Figure 2.9.

We further tested whether or not the measured metallicities could be due to measurement errors in the relevant line fluxes. Using the Data Release 6 SDSS

²See http://www.mpa-garching.mpg.de/SDSS/DR4/raw_data.html for this very rich dataset.

spectra (Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2008), we subtracted the underlying stellar continuum using the STARLIGHT program (Cid Fernandes et al. 2005), which simultaneously corrects for reddening and extinction using the Cardelli et al. (1989) extinction curves. While the extinction corrections are all small ($A_V < 1$), the Tremonti et al. line fluxes do not account for reddening, and thus a comparison of widely spaced line ratios produces a systematic offset. We therefore reject seven galaxies for which our measurements strongly disagree with Tremonti et al.’s on the $[\text{N II}]/\text{H}\alpha$ ratio; the difference in each of these cases is such that using the Tremonti et al. ratio would result in a lower $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ than if ours were used. The added advantage to using the $[\text{N II}]/\text{H}\alpha$ ratio is that this is the ratio used in the Pettini & Pagel (2004) metallicity determination, which we use as discussed below.

2.3.1. MEASURING LOW OXYGEN ABUNDANCES

We note that we do not impose a metallicity error cut when selecting these low-metallicity outliers. This is because the errors on Tremonti et al.’s $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ are not a simple function of metallicity in this range. It has long been recognized that accurately measuring low oxygen abundances (e.g., using R_{23}) can be tricky due to degeneracies in the ionization parameter, and the line ratios usually used to determine the ionization parameter (e.g., $[\text{O III}]\lambda 5007/[\text{O II}]\lambda 3727$) are also dependent on metallicity (McGaugh 1991; Kewley & Dopita 2002). Unfortunately,

this means that many metallicity indicators are discontinuous or systematically tend to avoid particular abundance solutions.

We therefore adopted a different approach to ensure that our low-metallicity high-mass outliers genuinely have relatively low oxygen abundances. As discussed in §2.3, we first chose only those galaxies that lie in the H II region locus of the BPT diagrams, and secondly, we discarded those galaxies for which we did not measure a comparable $[\text{N II}]/\text{H}\alpha$ ratio to those given by Tremonti et al.. Finally, we argue that if these galaxies are truly high-mass low-metallicity outliers, then they should be outliers regardless of how $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ is measured. (See Kewley & Dopita 2002, Kewley & Ellison 2008, and Chapter 3 for thorough discussions of how and why different metallicity calibrations differ.) We therefore used the Tremonti et al. measurements recalculate $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ for the entire parent sample using the Pettini & Pagel (2004) method (equation 2.2). The main disadvantage of this method is that it uses nitrogen as a proxy for oxygen; however, there are several factors that make it advantageous in these objects. First, it is reddening insensitive because the $[\text{N II}]\lambda 6584$ line and $\text{H}\alpha$ are separated by only $\sim 20 \text{ \AA}$. This means that we can safely use the Tremonti et al. measurements and our own measurements without being overly concerned about the reddening corrections. Second, unlike the various of R_{23} methods, the Pettini & Pagel method is both continuous and single-valued throughout the metallicity range of interest; there are no “upper-” and “lower-”-branches to concern us. We show the mass-metallicity relation with

$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ measured with the Pettini & Pagel (2004) method in Figure 2.10. Only one galaxy in the low-[O I] sample did not pass the $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ – $\log M_\star$ cuts described in Table 2.2, suggesting that the remaining galaxies are true low-metallicity outliers.

We have made several other checks for potential systematics. First, spiral (and thus many star-forming) galaxies are known to have metallicity gradients such that their centers have higher abundances than at larger radii (e.g., Zaritsky et al. 1994; Kennicutt et al. 2003). It is therefore reasonable to expect that, on average, spiral galaxies with larger fractions of their light falling in the 3'' SDSS fiber will have lower integrated metallicities. However, most of our galaxies (see Fig. 2.6) are not spiral galaxies, so we do not expect for this to be a huge effect. Regardless, as shown in Figure 2.11, while the galaxies in our sample do have somewhat high fiber fractions, this is only a small effect, and the offsets we see in metallicity are much greater than can be explained by large fiber fractions, which would cause contamination of central high-metallicity H II regions by low-metallicity H II gas at larger galactocentric radii.

Similarly, the final redshift distribution for the galaxies in our sample peaks at higher z than for the main sample; since we have convinced ourselves that this is not purely a fiber fraction effect, it is worrisome that it might partially be a redshift-evolution effect. When the universe was younger, galaxies are expected to have had lower oxygen abundances; the observed mass–metallicity relations for redshifts $z > 0.1$ are systematically shifted to lower metallicity from what is

observed for nearby galaxies (Erb et al. 2006a; Maiolino et al. 2008). We plot our low-metallicity outliers against the observed mass–metallicity evolution from Maiolino et al. (2008) in Figure 2.12. While the median redshift for galaxies in our sample is $z \sim 0.17$, the observed oxygen abundances are more typical of redshifts $2.2 \lesssim z \lesssim 3.5$. Though a large amount of scatter in the mass-metallicity relation is both expected and observed (Savaglio et al. 2005; Erb et al. 2006a; Kobayashi et al. 2007; Finlator & Davé 2008; Maiolino et al. 2008) at all redshifts, the abundance offsets of our low-metallicity outliers are much more pronounced than the relatively subtle expectations from metallicity evolution with cosmic time.

2.4. DISCUSSION

To seek to explain these galaxies’ extreme oxygen abundances, we need to consider the populations’ other physical properties. The 41 dwarf galaxies selected as described in § 2.2 are surprisingly non-pathological. They have undisturbed stellar morphologies (see Figure 2.3). Furthermore, given that by selection these galaxies have both low luminosities and high metallicities and that there is a trend for redder, brighter galaxies to have higher oxygen abundances (see, e.g., Cooper et al. 2008) these metal-rich dwarfs do not occupy an unexpected region of the color–magnitude diagram (see Figure 2.15 and also § 2.4.4). How, then, did they come to have such high oxygen abundances? One obvious possibility is that these metallicities are due

to an environmental effect, but as we describe in §2.4.1, the galaxies in our sample are non-interacting and rather isolated. Though several models predict that these galaxies should have high specific star formation rates, we show in §2.4.2, that these galaxies have normal star formation rates for their masses. We explain in §2.4.3 why we predict that these metal-rich dwarf galaxies should have relatively low gas fractions, and we discuss the implications of this prediction in the broader context of transition-type dwarf galaxies in §2.4.4.

As shown in Figure 2.15, our low-metallicity outliers are all *very* blue; most—but not all—are also outliers in the galaxy color–magnitude diagram. In §2.4.2, we discuss how this blueness can be attributed to the galaxies’ high specific star formation rates. Figure 2.6 shows that 40 out of 42 of the galaxies in our sample have disturbed morphologies suggestive of merging systems. Though some of the less-resolved galaxies in our sample may appear only slightly morphologically disturbed in the SDSS images, evidence suggests that, with higher resolution, these galaxies do in fact have unusual morphologies. In a *Hubble Space Telescope* study of local Lyman break galaxy (LBG) analogs, Overzier et al. (2008) found SDSSJ102613.97+4884458.9 ($[\alpha, \delta] = [156.5580, 48.7497]$, leftmost image on the bottom row of Figure 2.6) to have a strongly asymmetric profile with several distinct knots of star formation. In a preliminary study of the most UV luminous galaxies, Hoopes et al. (2007) found that these high specific star formation rate LBG analogs are metal-poor by ~ 0.5 dex relative to other galaxies of similar stellar mass. Hoopes

et al. and Overzier et al. suggest that the observed high specific star formation rates and low metallicities for these LBG analogs are related to the galaxy collisions that formed these objects. (See also Struck et al. 2008 for a discussion of so-called “delayed” galaxies, i.e., high star formation rate interacting galaxies which have apparently managed to retain most of their gas until $z = 0$.) In § 2.4.5, we show how a simple merger-induced gas inflow picture can account for an offset in metallicity, and we discuss possible shortcomings in this interpretation. The other two galaxies in the sample are undisturbed spiral galaxies, and while these are clearly very interesting objects, we have no explanation to offer for their extreme offsets from the mass-metallicity relation.

2.4.1. METAL-RICH DWARF GALAXIES ARE ISOLATED

While the origin of scatter in the mass-metallicity relation is unknown, one popular proposal is that environment affects metallicity. Recently, Michel-Dansac et al. (2008) studied close pairs of star-forming galaxies in SDSS with projected separations of < 100 kpc and radial velocity separations of < 350 km s⁻¹. Their results indicate that for minor mergers, the less massive galaxy is likely to be preferentially more metal rich than predicted by the mass-metallicity relation. Likewise, Cooper et al. (2008), after accounting for correlations within the color–magnitude diagram, find a strong positive correlation between metallicity and overdensity for $0.05 < z < 0.15$ SDSS-selected star-forming galaxies that can

account for up to $\sim 15\%$ of the scatter in the mass–metallicity relation. In light of these results, we searched for nearby neighbors of the seventeen $z > 0.024$ main sample metal-rich dwarf galaxies in a cylindrical volume of depth $\pm 1000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and projected radius of 1 Mpc. We find that our galaxies are relatively isolated; none of them would have made it into the Michel-Dansac et al. (2008) sample. Seven out of these seventeen galaxies in our sample have no neighbors within this volume. Of the 10 remaining galaxies, four have no neighbors within 500 km s^{-1} and 500 kpc, and only two have any neighbors within 500 km s^{-1} and 100 kpc. One of these two seems to be on the outskirts of a nearby cluster, but it is unclear whether or not it is physically associated with the cluster (and there is only one small, faint, non-star-forming galaxy within the Michel-Dansac et al. volume). The other galaxy with a nearby neighbor is $\sim 400 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and 85 kpc from a less-massive relatively metal-poor ($12 + \log[\text{O}/\text{H}] \approx 8.6$) star-forming galaxy. We therefore conclude that interactions with neighbors do not explain the observed high abundances of our main sample of $\log M_{\star} \sim 9.5$ galaxies.

The galaxies in the very low mass sample (as well the $z < 0.024$ galaxies in the main sample), however, are generally at low enough redshift that an automated search for neighbors in velocity and projected distance space is difficult. Like the galaxies in the main sample, none of the lower-mass galaxies are in obviously interacting systems. Interestingly, two of the outliers seem to be in the same system, separated by 56 kpc and 180 km s^{-1} . Only one other has a clear companion; it is a

$\log M_{\star} = 9.13$ galaxy which appears to be a satellite of a non-starforming companion 33 kpc and $\sim 120 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ away. Also, while two of the seventeen galaxies in the very low mass sample may be in the Virgo cluster, clearly a rich environment cannot explain the high oxygen abundances observed in all of these galaxies.

2.4.2. STAR FORMATION RATES

Dalcanton (2007) finds that for a galaxy to have a low metallicity, it must have both a low star formation rate and a high gas fraction; she argues that the observed low star formation efficiency in galaxies with circular velocities $\lesssim 120 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ can explain the mass-metallicity relation. Köppen et al. (2007) similarly suggest that the mass-metallicity relation could be due to a mass–star formation rate relation: a galaxy with a lower rate of star formation will have relatively fewer massive stars, and therefore a lower oxygen abundance. In either of these scenarios, we might expect the low mass-metallicity outliers to have high star formation rates for their masses. On the other hand, Ellison et al. (2008a) find that at low stellar masses, galaxies with higher specific star formation rates tend to have *lower* oxygen abundances. As Figure 2.13 shows, the galaxies in the main sample do not have preferentially high or low instantaneous specific star formation rates, while typical star formation rates for the the very low mass sample galaxies are $\sim 0.3 \text{ dex}$ *lower* than expected given their masses.

On the other hand, most (but not all) of our low-metallicity outliers clearly have higher specific star formation rates than typical of the larger sample. We plot the specific star formation rates against the mass–metallicity residual from Tremonti et al. (2004) in Figure 2.16; generally speaking, aperture corrections for the specific star formation rate only matter at the low SSFR end. While our low-metallicity outliers do have higher-than-normal SSFRs, this relative difference alone is not enough to explain their low oxygen abundances.

2.4.3. EFFECTIVE YIELDS AND GAS FRACTIONS

So why do the metal-rich outliers have such high oxygen abundances? Consider a closed box star forming system (i.e., a system with no gas inflow or outflow). The metallicity $Z \equiv (\text{mass of metals in gas phase})/(\text{total gas mass})$ is

$$Z = y \ln \left(\frac{1}{f_{\text{gas}}} \right), \quad (2.3)$$

where $f_{\text{gas}} \equiv M_{\text{gas}}/(M_{\star} + M_{\text{gas}})$ is the gas fraction and $y \equiv (\text{mass of metals in gas})/(\text{mass of metals in stellar remnants and main sequence stars})$ is the metal yield. An immediately striking aspect of Equation 2.3 is that there is no implicit dependence on the total galaxy mass; the deviations from a universal metallicity³

observed via the mass-metallicity relation are presumably then due to the fact that

³While the Z in Equation 2.3 is *not* the same as $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ —it is a mass ratio of *all* metals rather than the abundance ratio of one element relative to Hydrogen—the same arguments still qualitatively hold for observed abundances.

galaxies are not scaled closed box versions of one another: variations of the yield with mass, a dependence on the gas fraction with mass, or a combination of these effects plays a role. For a galaxy to have a higher metallicity than other galaxies of the same mass, Equation 2.3 tells us that it must have either a relatively high yield or a relatively low gas fraction. Observationally, the yield—which depends on both star formation physics as well as gas inflow and outflow—is a difficult quantity to measure; one popular way to address this problem is to define an effective yield,

$$y_{\text{eff}} \equiv \left[\frac{Z_{\text{gas}}}{\ln(1/f_{\text{gas}})} \right], \quad (2.4)$$

as the yield the galaxy *would* have were it actually a closed system. Given the galaxy’s metallicity and gas fraction, one can then easily calculate y_{eff} . A common explanation for the mass-metallicity relation is that the effective yield is positively correlated with galaxy mass, so that lower mass galaxies are able to preferentially lose metals to the intergalactic medium via winds because of their relatively shallow potential wells (see e.g., Larson 1974; Finlator & Davé 2008, and references therein). In particular, Tremonti et al. (2004) tested this idea by comparing effective yields and baryonic masses. However, because when estimating the effective yield from Equation 2.4, Tremonti et al. use the measured $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ values, outliers in the mass-metallicity relation are practically guaranteed to be outliers in the effective yield–baryonic mass relation.

Regardless, it is obvious from Equation 2.3 that our metal-rich dwarfs must either have unusually high yields or unusually low gas fractions for their masses. Galaxy yields can be affected by three processes: star formation, metal-deficient gas inflows, and metal-rich gas outflows. As shown in Figure 2.13 and discussed in §2.4.2, we find that the star formation rates for this population of galaxies are consistent with those of other galaxies of similar masses. Dalcanton (2007) has shown that metal-poor gas inflow is insufficient to explain the typically low metal abundances of low-mass galaxies; we therefore conclude that a lower inflow rate is insufficient to explain the higher abundances of our galaxies. It is possible that these galaxies are less effective at driving outflows than other dwarfs. For example, Ellison et al. (2008a) find that, at fixed mass, galaxies with smaller half-light radii tend to have higher abundances; this picture is consistent with the idea that it is more difficult to drive winds from deeper potential wells. (Tremonti et al. 2004, on the other hand, find no correlation with how concentrated a galaxy’s light is and its oxygen abundance.) While the galaxies in our main sample do tend to have small radii for their masses (half-light radii of less than 2 kpc), the typical $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ for galaxies of similar masses and radii is still ~ 0.3 dex lower (about 2σ) than that of our galaxies. Furthermore, the very low mass sample galaxies do not have preferentially small radii for their masses, leading us to conclude that while small radii may be a contributing factor to why some of these galaxies have been able to retain their metals, size alone does not tell the whole story.

Dalcanton (2007) calculated that enriched gas outflows can only severely decrease a galaxy’s effective yield if the gas fraction is sufficiently high; that is, for low gas fractions, even a very strong outflow cannot drastically decrease the effective yield—and thus measured abundance. Likewise, if a galaxy has a relatively low gas fraction, then only a small amount of pollution is needed to enrich the gas and cause the measured abundance to be high. We therefore predict that these mass–metallicity outliers have anomalously low gas masses relative to other isolated galaxies of similar luminosities and star-formation rates. There are unfortunately no H I data in the literature for our galaxies that we can call upon to lend observational support to this prediction. However, Lee et al. (2006) have found that, in a sample of 27 nearby dwarf irregular galaxies, the gas-phase oxygen abundance is negatively correlated with the H I-measured gas-to-stellar mass ratio, which lends observational credence to our expectation.

2.4.4. TRANSITIONAL DWARF GALAXIES

If these high-metallicity dwarf galaxies really do have relatively little gas, then they should be rapidly approaching the end of their star formation. Specifically, these galaxies are likely to be transitioning from gas-rich dwarf irregulars (dIrr) to gas-deficient dwarf spheroidals (dSph) or the more massive dwarf ellipticals (dE). In general, so-called dIrr/dSph transitional dwarfs have similar star-formation histories as their currently non-starforming dSph cousins: both galaxy types typically have a

mix of old and intermediate-age stellar populations (Grebel et al. 2003). In a study of five nearby star-forming transitional dwarfs, Dellenbusch et al. (2007) found that these relatively isolated galaxies seem to have unusually high oxygen abundances for their luminosities, much like our sample of mass–metallicity outliers.⁴ Grebel et al. (2003) stress that the only difference between dSph galaxies and the transitional dIrr/dSph galaxies is the absence of star formation and of gas in dSph galaxies. While much of this conclusion is based on galaxies in higher-density environments than ours are (i.e., the Grebel et al. (2003) dwarf galaxies are mostly in the Local Group), we find it likely that our galaxies are part of a similar transition population: morphologically, they have smooth, undisturbed profiles (see Figure 2.3), indicating a stronger relationship to dwarf spheroidals than to the dwarf irregulars. In particular, for all of our galaxies we note a lack of the irregular flocculent structures or spiral features often associated with dIrr galaxies.

In fact, the only remarkable morphology any of the galaxies in our sample displays are the bright—and often very blue—cores noticed in ten of the galaxies. These galaxies are shown in Figure 2.14 and noted in Table 2.1. Some of these cores appear to have merely much higher surface brightnesses than their

⁴All five of the Dellenbusch et al. galaxies are in the Tremonti et al. sample; four were either too high mass or too low metallicity (as measured by Tremonti et al.) to be significant outliers by our definitions. The final galaxy (IC 745) was excluded from our sample because its measured Pettini & Pagel (2004) abundance when converted to the Tremonti et al. scale is 0.22 dex above the Kewley & Ellison (2008) relation (as discussed in § 2.2.3), highlighting the point that while our sample is rather pure, it is almost certainly incomplete.

surroundings, but some are decidedly blue: Gu et al. (2006) measure a difference of $\Delta(g - r) \gtrsim 0.3 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$ from the center of IC 225⁵ relative to isophotes at $> 5''$. These bright cores are almost certainly not a signature of active galactic nuclei; as mentioned in § 2.2.3, these galaxies fall squarely within the star-forming locus of the normal BPT line-ratio diagnostic diagrams (Baldwin et al. 1981; Kewley et al. 2006b). Boselli et al. (2008) find that for similar transitional dwarf galaxies with blue centers in the Virgo cluster (including VCC 1855, the least massive galaxy in our sample with $\log[M_*/M_\odot] \sim 7.4$), star formation is limited to these central blue nuclei. (Boselli et al. attribute this centralized star formation to the effects of ram pressure stripping preferentially removing gas from the outer regions of the galaxies. However, not all of the galaxies in our sample with bright nuclei are in the kinds of rich environments like the Virgo cluster where ram pressure stripping expected to play an important role.) Intriguingly (yet unsurprisingly), most of our galaxies which appear to be approaching or on the red sequence (see Figure 2.15) also have bright and/or blue cores, implying that their colors are already dominated by their non-starforming regions. Furthermore, having star formation limited to a relatively small region of the galaxy supports the idea that there is relatively little fuel available for forming stars, and thus that these galaxies are on their way to becoming standard dwarf spheroidal or dwarf elliptical galaxies.

⁵As mentioned in § 2.2.2, IC 255 did not pass all of the cuts for our very low mass sample, and so we reinserted it into the sample by hand.

2.4.5. OBSERVED METALLICITY OF MERGING GALAXIES

As can be seen in Figure 2.6, most of galaxies in the low-metallicity sample are tidally interacting. Simulations have shown that galaxy major mergers are accompanied by starbursts and gas inflow from large galactocentric radii (e.g., Barnes & Hernquist 1992; Mihos & Hernquist 1996; Cox et al. 2006). Because typical spiral galaxies have metallicity gradients (Kennicutt et al. 2003), the inflowing gas will have a lower oxygen abundance than the native central gas. This suggests that perhaps our galaxies' observed low metallicities are a consequence of large quantities of low-metallicity gas from large galactocentric radii are being transported into the central few kiloparsecs and diluting the metal-rich central gas.

We can test this idea at the order of magnitude level to verify that it can give the observed oxygen abundance offsets of -0.3 to -0.8 dex (see, e.g., Fig. 2.11). The SDSS data measure the galaxies' *central* oxygen abundances; we wish to know what the change in oxygen abundance would be if low-metallicity gas from larger radii were dumped into the central regions. If we assume that *all* of the gas out to some large radius R was to participate in this inflow, then the lower abundance would be the same as if we simply measured the total oxygen abundance for the entire galaxy gas disk out to the radius R . For reference, typical observed H I disks (e.g., NGC 6946; Boomsma et al. 2008) have radii of $R \sim 20$ kpc. We consider a model spiral galaxy with a gradient of $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ of slope $\Gamma_{\text{O}/\text{H}}$ in units of dex per

kiloparsec; $\Gamma_{\text{O/H}}$ is and is typically of order $-0.05 \text{ dex kpc}^{-1}$ (Zaritsky et al. 1994; van Zee et al. 1998; Kennicutt et al. 2003). We will also assume that our model galaxy has a gas surface density Σ that obeys a power-law relation with the radius such that $\Sigma(R) = \Sigma_0(R/R_0)^\alpha$. While a constant surface density ($\alpha = 0$) is a reasonable assumption at large radii (Wong & Blitz 2002; Leroy et al. 2008), we will show that the calculated oxygen abundance dilution is not strongly dependent on the choice of this power-law slope. For notational simplicity, in this section only we will use O/H as shorthand for the more cumbersome $12 + \log(\text{O/H})$.

Let $\langle \text{O/H} \rangle_{\text{SDSS}}$ be the mean O/H within an SDSS spectroscopic fiber of a spiral galaxy (i.e., within the central $3''$ diameter). Formally,

$$\langle \text{O/H} \rangle_{\text{SDSS}} \equiv \frac{\int_0^{R_3} \Sigma(R) (\text{O/H}) R dR d\theta}{\int_0^{R_3} \Sigma(R) R dR d\theta}, \quad (2.5)$$

where R_3 is the radius in kiloparsecs of the galaxy at a radius of $1.5''$ (i.e., spanned by the $3''$ SDSS fiber; this corresponds to $\approx 4.9 \text{ kpc}$ at $z = 0.2$) and we are implicitly assuming the scale-height of the galaxy is roughly constant with radius. For radii $R > R_3$, the oxygen abundance is $\text{O/H} = (\text{O/H})_0 + \Gamma_{\text{O/H}} R$, where $(\text{O/H})_0$ is the oxygen abundance extrapolated to $R = 0$ using the adopted the abundance gradient.

We can now expand Equation (2.5) to find

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \text{O/H} \rangle_{\text{SDSS}} &= \left[\frac{2 + \alpha}{2\pi R_3^{2+\alpha}} \right] 2\pi \int_0^{R_3} R^\alpha [(\text{O/H})_0 + \Gamma_{\text{O/H}} R] R dR \\ &= (\text{O/H})_0 + \left[\frac{2 + \alpha}{3 + \alpha} \right] \Gamma_{\text{O/H}} R_3. \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Solving for the $R = 0$ abundance, we find $(\text{O}/\text{H})_0 = \langle \text{O}/\text{H} \rangle_{\text{SDSS}} - [(2 + \alpha)/(3 + \alpha)]\Gamma_{\text{O}/\text{H}}R_3$. The mean metallicity $\langle \text{O}/\text{H} \rangle_{\leq R}$ out to a radius R is therefore

$$\langle \text{O}/\text{H} \rangle_{\leq R} = \frac{\int_0^R \Sigma(R)(\text{O}/\text{H})RdRd\theta}{\int_0^R \Sigma(R)RdRd\theta} = (\text{O}/\text{H})_0 + \left[\frac{2 + \alpha}{3 + \alpha} \right] \Gamma_{\text{O}/\text{H}}R. \quad (2.7)$$

Hence the change in metallicity $\Delta(\text{O}/\text{H})$ we would expect within an SDSS fiber diameter is $\Delta(\text{O}/\text{H}) = [(2 + \alpha)/(3 + \alpha)]\Gamma_{\text{O}/\text{H}}\Delta R = [(2 + \alpha)/(3 + \alpha)]\Gamma_{\text{O}/\text{H}}(R - R_3)$. For an outer radius of $R = 20$ kpc, an inner radius of $R_3 = 5$ kpc, an abundance gradient of $\Gamma_{\text{O}/\text{H}} = -0.05$ dex kpc $^{-1}$, and a flat radial gas-surface density distribution of $\alpha = 0$, this leads to an oxygen abundance dilution of $\Delta(\text{O}/\text{H}) = -0.5$ dex, which is in the range we observe for these low-metallicity outliers (see, e.g., Fig. 2.16).

We note that there are several caveats with this picture. First, we have assumed that the observed oxygen abundance corresponds to a mass-weighted abundance, whereas because we measure the metallicity via emission line spectra, it is actually weighted by the luminosities of the H II regions. Secondly, it is unclear if the timescales involved pose any problem. Simulations show mergers *do* induce gas inflow to the centers of galaxies (Cox et al. 2006), but most of this inflow occurs during the first close encounter between the two galaxies. While a few of the galaxies in our sample do have nearby neighbors, most do not: SDSS detects only a single, if disturbed, galaxy. It is possible that these are not yet dynamically relaxed; the two galaxies can pass close enough to one another that they are seen by SDSS as

one object. If a merger-induced starburst lasts ~ 1 Gyr (Cox et al. 2006), then $\sim 1\%$ of all (properly defined) starburst mergers should display lower-than-expected metallicities. The relevant dynamical timescale for gas inflow depends on the typical radius from which the gas originates. Because the dynamical time $t_{\text{dynam}} \approx R/v_{\text{esc}}$, gas at larger radii takes longer to reach R_3 and help dilute the central metallicity.

Several studies have shown that galaxies in close pairs tend to have lower metallicities than expected. Kewley et al. (2006a) found that galaxies separated by $\lesssim 20h^{-1}$ kpc have systematically lower oxygen abundances by ~ 0.2 dex. On the other hand, Ellison et al. (2008b) found an offset of ~ 0.05 dex in $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ at fixed mass galaxies in pairs with similar separations; the investigations of Michel-Dansac et al. (2008) of galaxies in close pairs suggest that the relative $\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ offset is greater for the lower-mass galaxy in the pair than for the higher-mass galaxy. Kewley et al. also found relatively high specific star formation rates for the lower-metallicity member in their galaxy pairs; they attribute both the strong starburst activity and the lower oxygen abundance to fresh gas inflowing to the galaxies' central regions due to interaction with the closely neighboring galaxy.

In a similar vein, Lee et al. (2004) found that morphologically disturbed galaxies have systematically lower oxygen abundances (or higher luminosities) than galaxies of similar brightness (or metallicity). Likewise, luminous infrared galaxies (LIRGs), whose high specific star formation rates and highly disturbed morphologies are believed to be due to a recent major merger, are observed to have oxygen

abundances that are ~ 0.4 dex lower than other galaxies of comparable masses (Rupke et al. 2008). Hydrodynamic simulations of galaxy mergers indicate that the offset in metallicity from the mass-metallicity relation could possibly be used to “date” the stage of the merger (Montuori et al. 2010). The pronounced blue colors of our outliers (see Fig. 2.15) implies that while the star formation rates for many of these galaxies are consistent with those of LIRGs, these outliers are clearly not as dusty as their infrared-luminous cousins; it is unclear the extent to which these classes of galaxies are related, and why, if LIRGs do typically have such relatively low metallicities, no galaxies in our sample are extremely red.

2.5. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

We have identified outliers from the mass-metallicity relation. Of these, a sample of 41 are low-luminosity high-oxygen abundance galaxies.

1. These galaxies are fairly isolated and none show any signs of morphological disturbance. It is likely, however, that the handful of galaxies in this sample which are possible group or cluster members have disturbed *gas* morphologies, due to e.g., ram-pressure stripping. However, environmental effects cannot account for the large gas-phase oxygen abundances observed in all of these galaxies.

2. Based on the effective yield considerations of Dalcanton (2007) and various related observational results (Grebel et al. 2003; Dellenbusch et al. 2007; Lee et al. 2006; Boselli et al. 2008), we predict that these galaxies should have low gas fractions relative to other dwarf galaxies of similar stellar masses and star formation rates in similar environments but with more typical (i.e., lower) oxygen abundances. Furthermore, in this scenario, the *stellar* metallicities should be consistent with that of other dwarfs of similar luminosity, i.e., the stellar metallicities should be lower than the measured gas-phase abundances.

3. These mass–metallicity outliers appear to be “transitional” dwarf galaxies: because they are running out of star-forming fuel, they are nearing the end of their star formation and becoming typical isolated dwarf spheroidals. This conclusion is most sound for the $M_{\star} < 9.1M_{\odot}$ galaxies which are observed to have low specific star formation rates. More data—specifically, gas fractions and stellar metallicities—are needed to help elucidate the situation for the higher mass galaxies.

We have further identified a sample of 42 low-metallicity high-mass outliers from the mass–metallicity relation. As a population, these galaxies have disturbed morphologies and high specific star formation rates, implying that they are undergoing a merger-induced starburst. We propose that their observed low oxygen abundances are due the tidal interaction inducing large-scale gas inflow which

subsequently dilutes the central interstellar medium in these galaxies. While there have been several observational and theoretical suggestions that interacting galaxies will result in a decreased observed gas-phase metallicity, this is the first work that has shown that the vast majority of severe low-metallicity outliers from the mass-metallicity relation are morphologically disturbed. Finally, we note that the cuts outlined in § 2.3 provide an effective means of using *only* colors and spectra to identify a rather pure (though not necessarily complete) sample of tidally disturbed galaxies.

One striking implication of these results is that, while it is safe to assume that the metallicities for *populations* of galaxies will fall within a particular range of values given their luminosities at redshifts for which the luminosity–metallicity relation has been measured, one should not assign metallicities to *individual* galaxies based solely on their luminosities. For example, while studies of the host galaxies of long gamma-ray bursts (GRBs) suggest that GRBs are only found in low-metallicity environments (Stanek et al. 2006; Kewley et al. 2007), several recent GRBs have been associated with very luminous hosts, such as GRB 070306 and its $M_B \sim -22.3$ host galaxy (Jaunsen et al. 2008). We have shown here that assuming an oxygen abundance for a galaxy from its luminosity alone can result in mis-estimating $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ in luminous galaxies by a whole dex, and thus one should not assume that, e.g., the host of GRB 070306 necessarily has a high metallicity. For cases in which $\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ has been measured via emission line spectra for GRB hosts, it

is generally low, even if the galaxy is luminous. For example, the host galaxy of GRB 031203 has an absolute B -band magnitude similar to that of the Milky Way, yet Margutti et al. (2007) find it to have a low metallicity ($12 + \log[\text{O}/\text{H}] = 8.12$) as well as a high star formation rate ($\sim 13 M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$). Prochaska et al. (2004) interpret this offset in metallicity as a sign that GRB 031203 went off in a “very young star-forming region,” which is in line with our interpretation in §2.4.5. Furthermore, the brighter GRB hosts studied by Fruchter et al. (2006) are morphologically very similar to our massive low-metallicity galaxies, and our results strongly suggest that the oxygen abundances inferred from luminosity alone are uncertain by as much as 1 dex. Specifically, if a luminous galaxy is morphologically disturbed, has a high specific star formation rate, and is extremely blue, then it should not be assumed to lie within the luminosity–metallicity locus of star-forming galaxies.

Fig. 2.1.— The mass-metallicity relation, with $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ from Tremonti et al. (2004), with low-mass outliers marked in pink and high-mass outliers marked in blue. The shaded regions in this and subsequent figures denote the 1- and 2- σ dispersion in moving bins of $\log M_*$.

Fig. 2.2.— $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ vs. M_B , with $\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ taken from Tremonti et al. (2004) and M_B measured using the methods of Assef et al. (2008). The small grey points are star-forming galaxies with SDSS magnitude errors < 0.1 mag; the red circles are the 24 galaxies in our main sample, and the green triangles are the very low mass sample. The errorbars on $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ show the central 68% spread from Tremonti et al. (2004). The pale blue histogram denotes the median $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ in bins of M_B with width $\Delta M_B = 0.4$ mag; these medians are probably artificially high at low luminosities due to substantial contamination at high $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ as discussed in § 2.2.2. The Milky Way, SMC, and LMC are shown using M_B from Karachentsev (2005), and the $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ measurements are as discussed in the § 2.2.

Fig. 2.3.— SDSS images of high-metallicity dwarf galaxies scaled to 10×10 kpc, with M_B decreasing to the right and down from -14.4 to -19.1 , so that the faintest galaxy is in the upper-left corner. The stellar masses for this sample range from $\log M_\star \approx 7.4$ to 9.9 .

Fig. 2.4.— Zoomed in portion of the $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ vs. $\log M_*$ plane with 97.5% (solid line and short dashed line) and 99% (long dashed line) cuts shown; see §2.2.1 and Table 2.2. The small points have SDSS magnitude errors < 0.1 mag and the larger grey points are the 24 galaxies in our main sample, which are similar in luminosity to the Large Magellanic Cloud (which has a $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ of 8.39). The errorbars on $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ show the central 68% spread from Tremonti et al. (2004).

Fig. 2.5.— Comparisons of oxygen abundances of low-luminosity mass–metallicity outliers measured with different methods as compared to mean relations. The triangles denote abundances measured with the method of Pettini & Pagel (2004); the squares are metallicities from revised Kewley & Dopita (2002) method from Kewley & Ellison (2008). The solid line and dashed lines are the conversion from the Pettini & Pagel (2004) method and the Kewley & Dopita (2002) method to the Tremonti et al. (2004) metallicity respectively; the dotted line indicates equal measurements. Conversions are from Kewley & Ellison (2008); see § 2.2.3 for a more in depth discussion.

Fig. 2.6.— Normalized SDSS g -band images of massive low-metallicity galaxies scaled to 40×40 kpc, with mass decreasing to the right and down from $\log M_{\star} \approx 11.1$ to 9.4. The only two clearly spiral galaxies are the middle two on the top row.

Fig. 2.7.— An example of one of the cuts made to find low-metallicity high-luminosity outliers from the mass–metallicity relation. Plotted is $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ vs. M_g for the main sample (*small light grey points*), the 1% objects the lowest $\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ in bins of M_g of width 0.4 mag (*small black points*), and the final sample of high-mass low-metallicity outliers (*large grey points*). The only two clearly spiral galaxies in the sample are denoted with “§” symbols. The histogram shows the 1% threshold in $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ in bins of M_g .

Fig. 2.8.— Baldwin, Phillips, & Terlevich diagrams of $\log([\text{O III}]/\text{H}\beta)$ v. $\log([\text{N II}]/\text{H}\alpha)$ [*left*] and $\log([\text{O III}]/\text{H}\beta)$ v. $\log([\text{O I}]/\text{H}\alpha)$ [*right*]. Plotted are the spectroscopic galaxies from SDSS DR4 (*small grey points*), the galaxies passing our luminosity, mass, and $\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ cuts but not in the final sample (*open points*), the galaxies passing the BPT diagram cuts (*light grey points*), and the galaxies in our final low-metallicity sample (*dark grey points*). Lines are taken from Kewley et al. (2006b).

Fig. 2.9.— Sample spectra. Two low-metallicity high-mass outliers (*top and middle panels*) and one galaxy rejected as a potential AGN (*bottom*).

Fig. 2.10.— Plot of Pettini & Pagel (2004) $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ v. $\log(M_*/M_\odot)$. The massive outliers in our sample are plotted as the large blue circles in the lower-right region of the mass–metallicity diagram; the only two clearly spiral galaxies in the sample are denoted with “§” symbols. The histogram denotes the median $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ in bins of stellar mass, while the curves are fits to standard deviation offsets as labeled.

Fig. 2.11.— Plot of residual in $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ from the Tremonti et al. fit to the mass–metallicity relation v. fiber fraction. The high-mass low-metallicity outliers are shown as the large blue points at the bottom of the diagram, with the only two distinctly spiral galaxies in the sample as “§” symbols. For reference we plot the high-metallicity outliers as large pink points.

Fig. 2.12.— Evolution of the mass-metallicity relation from Maiolino et al. (2008) with comparison to low-metallicity high-mass outliers (grey points). Fits to the mass-metallicity relation from Maiolino et al. (2008) are shown with lines: $z \sim 0.7$, dotted; $z \sim 0.7$, short dashed; $z \sim 2.2$, long dashed; and $z \sim 3.5$ solid. The grey points denote our high-mass low-metallicity outliers ($0.035 < z < 0.27$), with re-calculated metallicities using the Kewley & Dopita (2002) diagnostic using our measurements of the line ratios so that they are on the same scale as the Maiolino et al. results. (The stellar masses have also been shifted to match the Maiolino et al. fits.)

Fig. 2.13.— *Left*: Star formation rate vs. stellar mass. The grey points are galaxies from the Tremonti et al. (2004) sample with SDSS magnitude errors < 0.1 mag, the galaxies in our main dwarf sample are denoted with pink squares, the galaxies in our very low mass sample are marked with green triangles, with the massive metal-poor galaxies marked with blue circles. The yellow histogram denotes the median star formation rate in bins of $\log M_*$ of width 0.1 dex. The star formation rates estimates are from (Brinchmann et al. 2004) and the stellar mass estimates are from Tremonti et al. (2004) and Kauffmann et al. (2003). *Right*: Specific star formation rate vs. stellar mass. The grey points are galaxies from the main Tremonti et al. (2004) SDSS sample described in §2.3, the low-metallicity massive galaxies in our sample are denoted with blue circles (with the only two clearly spiral galaxies marked by “§” symbols), and the metal-rich dwarf galaxies are shown with pink points for reference. The histogram denotes the median specific star formation rate as a function of stellar mass and the dotted lines show lines of constant star formation rate. The star formation rates estimates are from (Brinchmann et al. 2004) and the stellar mass estimates are from Tremonti et al. (2004) and Kauffmann et al. (2003); both have been aperture corrected.

Fig. 2.14.— SDSS images of high-metallicity low-mass galaxies with bright and/or blue cores, scaled to 5×5 kpc, with M_B decreasing to the right and down so that the faintest galaxy is in the upper-left corner.

Fig. 2.15.— Mass-metallicity outliers on the color–magnitude diagram. *Right:* High-metallicity low-mass galaxies on the color–magnitude diagram ($u - r$ vs. M_r) from the flux-limited $z < 0.06$ sample of Unterborn & Ryden (2008). The color scale on the right shows the $\log f$ of each bin, where f is the fraction of galaxies in that bin; bin sizes are 0.05 mag in $u - r$ and 0.25 in M_r . The red circles denote the 24 galaxies from the main sample and the green triangles denote the 17 galaxies in the very low mass sample. *Left:* $(g - r)$ vs. M_r , both k -corrected to $z = 0.1$ using the templates from Assef et al. (2008)] from the SDSS DR6 spectroscopic galaxy sample (Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2008). The blue circles denote the 42 low-metallicity high-mass galaxies in our sample; for reference, metal-rich dwarf galaxies are denoted by the pink circles.

Fig. 2.16.— Residual in $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ from Tremonti et al. (2004) fit to the mass-metallicity relation v. specific star formation rate (SSFR), both within the SDSS $3''$ fiber (*left*) and aperture-corrected (*right*). In each panel, the blue points are the high-mass low-metallicity outliers while the pink points are the metal-rich dwarf galaxies. (The “S” symbols denote the only two clearly spiral galaxies in the low-metallicity high-mass sample.) The grey cloud of points are the galaxies from the main Tremonti et al. (2004) SDSS sample described in § 2.3, and the central thick yellow histogram is the median residual $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ in bins of SSFR. The thin black histograms at the top and bottom of each panel are the distribution of SSFR of the parent sample, while the blue histograms at the bottom of each panel is the SSFR distribution of the low-metallicity outliers and the pink histogram at the top of each panel is the SSFR distribution of the high-metallicity outliers.

RA	dec	$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$	M_B	$\log M_\star$	redshift	Notes
193.9056	-1.32986	8.68	-14.46	7.65	0.0029	blue core, IC 225
180.4589	55.14507	8.73	-14.56	7.73	0.0035	
190.2097	4.52583	9.06	-14.64	7.39	0.0025	blue core, VCC 1855
179.0295	64.35073	8.83	-14.89	8.06	0.0047	
228.0340	1.58571	8.76	-15.14	8.21	0.0065	
126.6407	25.49979	8.69	-15.23	8.07	0.0072	
227.2679	0.82197	8.85	-15.35	8.17	0.0055	
193.6735	2.10447	9.12	-15.50	8.40	0.0029	bright core
126.6633	25.59821	8.86	-15.87	8.59	0.0078	
208.3607	5.20778	8.94	-16.19	8.64	0.0027	blue core
128.5841	50.45248	8.95	-16.36	8.69	0.0114	
40.3408	0.05813	8.90	-16.56	8.70	0.0227	
212.9768	53.93956	8.85	-16.57	8.81	0.0064	blue core
190.5886	2.06662	9.00	-16.73	8.40	0.0044	bright core
36.6179	1.16053	8.82	-16.86	7.92	0.0051	blue core
117.1775	26.53979	8.94	-16.88	9.08	0.0155	

(cont'd)

Table 2.1. Full sample of low-luminosity mass-metallicity outliers

Table 2.1—Continued

RA	dec	$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$	M_B	$\log M_\star$	redshift	Notes
182.7831	0.95682	8.95	-16.98	9.13	0.0206	
133.8883	31.21168	9.10	-16.99	9.29	0.0068	
25.7673	14.52434	9.12	-17.16	9.25	0.0284	
225.5670	38.80631	9.12	-17.32	9.45	0.0147	bright core
142.9797	39.27156	9.07	-17.36	9.35	0.0275	
139.3797	33.47552	9.15	-17.52	9.46	0.0221	
202.2088	-0.90846	9.14	-17.58	9.26	0.0217	
39.0487	-7.73400	9.12	-17.66	9.16	0.0314	
143.4695	41.07965	9.14	-17.92	9.54	0.0145	bright core
187.1760	44.09813	9.13	-17.93	9.35	0.0239	
182.8574	44.43604	9.14	-17.97	9.52	0.0231	
211.3199	54.20347	9.13	-18.15	9.54	0.0417	
258.4301	57.18840	9.16	-18.18	9.61	0.0290	
208.9341	4.24367	9.14	-18.19	9.68	0.0295	
227.6711	41.16220	9.13	-18.20	9.61	0.0316	
352.8635	13.90885	9.14	-18.34	9.74	0.0324	

(cont'd)

Table 2.1—Continued

RA	dec	$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$	M_B	$\log M_\star$	redshift	Notes
206.4402	63.85402	9.14	-18.36	9.58	0.0313	
153.2177	12.34451	9.20	-18.39	9.57	0.0315	
177.7870	49.69415	9.14	-18.41	9.41	0.0482	
144.1848	33.91996	9.14	-18.45	9.71	0.0426	
162.6325	0.36061	9.16	-18.60	9.68	0.0384	
195.6390	-3.33894	9.26	-18.66	9.55	0.0471	
235.5660	51.73211	9.16	-18.87	9.83	0.0425	
163.2191	43.42840	9.27	-18.92	9.90	0.0242	
245.3673	40.20360	9.25	-19.05	9.91	0.0285	blue core

Note. — Sample of metal-rich dwarf galaxies, sorted by M_B . First sixteen lines (above the thick horizontal line; first page) are the very low mass ($\log[M_\star/M_\odot] < 9.1$) sample. RA and dec are in degrees, $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ and stellar mass from Tremonti et al. (2004), and M_B is measured using the low-resolution templates of Assef et al. (2008) and corrected where necessary for peculiar velocities, as discussed in § 2.2; redshifts are spectroscopic redshifts and have not been corrected for peculiar velocities.

Cut	Number Surviving
Fiber fraction > 0.1	107992
k -corrected SDSS magnitude errors < 0.1 mag	48327
97.5% large (O/H) and small M_B	227
97.5% large (O/H) and small M_g	202
99% large (O/H) w.r.t. M_B	87
99% large (O/H) w.r.t. M_\star	66
97.5% small M_\star w.r.t. (O/H)	51
redshift > 0.024 for [O II]	34
$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ error < 0.05 dex	22
Visual inspection	20
Fiber fraction > 0.2 and photometry	17
redshift $z < 0.024$ but surviving subsequent cuts	7

Note. — See § 2.2.1 and Figure 2.4 for a more detailed explanation.

Table 2.2. Cuts for Selection of Main Sample of Metal-Rich Dwarf Galaxies

Cut	Number Surviving
k -corrected SDSS magnitude errors < 0.1 mag	52744
84% high (O/H) w.r.t. M_B	8405
$M_B > -17$ mag	217
$\log M_\star < 9.15$	201
84% high (O/H) w.r.t. M_\star	192
$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ error < 0.05 dex	139
99% low $\log M_\star$ w.r.t. (O/H)	105
<i>exclude</i> 95% high (O/H) w.r.t. M_\star , fiber fraction > 0.1	78
95% high (O/H) w.r.t. M_g	32
Visual inspection	23
Metallicity comparison	17
Absolute magnitude correction	16

Note. — See § 2.2.2 and Figure 2.4 for a more detailed explanation. The 95% high (O/H) w.r.t. M_g cut excludes IC 225, which passes subsequent cuts and is nonetheless included in plots and discussions. Note lack of fiber-fraction cut.

Table 2.3. Cuts for Very Low Mass Sample Selection

RA	dec	$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$	$\log M_{\star}/M_{\odot}$	redshift
149.9796	10.24727	8.63	11.07	0.2423
255.5060	60.79618	8.62	10.97	0.1257
191.3246	4.87648	8.33	10.94	0.1800 [§]
168.6324	48.91903	8.72	10.88	0.1116 [§]
197.4139	62.76859	8.70	10.84	0.2587
329.9707	1.03852	8.59	10.83	0.2200
150.2157	8.30726	8.72	10.75	0.2290
148.0473	54.31252	8.71	10.65	0.2544
146.8469	53.06987	8.67	10.63	0.2471
214.2315	40.44983	8.69	10.61	0.2060
196.1901	62.40580	8.70	10.56	0.1118
206.4954	11.47993	8.60	10.54	0.2373
128.9575	44.87386	8.69	10.53	0.2264
158.5174	6.20286	8.59	10.53	0.1043
140.1770	0.84295	8.69	10.49	0.2521
118.9094	33.44449	8.57	10.49	0.1413
170.4012	0.54706	8.69	10.48	0.2292
17.1399	-0.46871	8.66	10.47	0.2270
158.5274	5.51848	8.69	10.41	0.1708
181.9754	12.39080	8.67	10.41	0.2613
200.4299	43.40588	8.45	10.34	0.1950
126.2741	7.21643	8.69	10.33	0.1974
349.5542	-0.69060	8.68	10.29	0.2517
218.7960	44.18318	8.66	10.29	0.1276
250.6480	42.39715	8.59	10.29	0.1511
244.4054	35.82085	8.66	10.24	0.2259
196.2852	53.19373	8.67	10.23	0.2719

(cont'd)

Table 2.4. Low-metallicity mass-metallicity outliers

Table 2.4—Continued

RA	dec	$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$	$\log M_{\star}/M_{\odot}$	redshift
146.2970	42.64472	8.33	10.16	0.2576
240.8967	31.83226	8.17	10.12	0.1544
127.9271	51.42651	8.21	10.07	0.0813
153.3421	2.58265	8.19	10.07	0.0780
48.8150	-7.76643	8.25	9.95	0.0612
129.3898	47.96454	8.31	9.92	0.2152
234.2552	31.44251	8.30	9.92	0.1538
233.5084	-1.96201	8.30	9.83	0.0787
1.2987	1.06057	8.24	9.82	0.1028
156.5582	48.74970	8.33	9.79	0.1604
226.0778	2.76445	8.17	9.65	0.0350
345.7720	1.24968	8.22	9.59	0.0690
168.1920	1.33819	8.17	9.49	0.1088
219.6623	53.14538	8.16	9.44	0.0900
197.1532	59.88513	8.16	9.41	0.1410

Note. — Sample of massive low-metallicity galaxies, reverse sorted by stellar mass. RA and Dec are in degrees (J2000.0), $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ and stellar masses are from Tremonti et al. (2004).

[§]Spiral galaxy.

Cut	Number Surviving
Low magnitude errors	86754
1% low O/H w.r.t. M_g	855
1% low O/H w.r.t. M_z	598
2.5% low O/H w.r.t. $\log M_\star$	381
2.5% high $\log M_\star$ w.r.t. O/H	113
within 2σ of H II region of [O I] BPT diagram	56
OK spectrum reduction	52
reproducible [N II]/H α ratio	44
2.5% low PP04 (O/H) w.r.t. $\log M_\star$	42

Note. — See § 2.3 and Figure 2.7 for a more detailed explanation.

Table 2.5. Cuts for Selection of Massive Low-Metallicity Galaxies

CHAPTER 3

BALANCING OUTFLOWS AND GAS DILUTION

3.1. INTRODUCTION

Star-forming galaxies follow a tight (~ 0.1 dex scatter) correlation between their gas phase oxygen abundance (hereafter referred to as “metallicity”) and stellar mass (Tremonti et al. 2004). This mass-metallicity relation is primarily understood to be a sequence of oxygen *suppression*, rather than enrichment (Tremonti et al. 2004; Dalcanton 2007; Erb 2008; Finlator & Davé 2008). The production of oxygen traces the production of stars, implying that the observed trend in the oxygen-to-gas ratio reflects either a trend in the galaxy gas-to-stellar mass ratio or in processes that affect gas-phase metals but not stars. If the mass-metallicity relation is governed by an underlying trend in gas fractions, then the metals in low-mass galaxies are more diluted than in more massive galaxies because of the relatively larger gas fractions in the smaller galaxies (Garnett 2002; Leroy et al. 2008). Such preferential dilution can be attributed to variations in gas accretion and/or star formation efficiency with galaxy mass. On the other hand, large-scale galaxy winds affect galaxies’ gas (and thus gas-phase metals) while not affecting the stars; if outflows are more efficient

at removing metals from low-mass galaxies than more massive ones due to the less massive galaxies' relatively shallow potential wells, then the lower-mass galaxies will have lower metallicities (Wyse & Silk 1985; Heckman et al. 2000). In this Chapter, we present a comprehensive approach to modelling the mass-metallicity relation, incorporating both mass-dependent outflows and gas fractions.

Previous analytic studies have reached conflicting conclusions on the relative importance to the mass-metallicity relation of galaxy outflows and gas dilution. Focusing on the $z \sim 2.2$ mass-metallicity relation observed by Erb et al. (2006a), Erb (2008) used a simple analytic chemical evolution model to argue that the star formation rate, \dot{M}_{SFR} , and the outflow rate, \dot{M}_{w} , should be roughly equal. While \dot{M}_{w} and the gas accretion rate \dot{M}_{acc} vary with the star formation rate (and thus gas fraction), $\eta_{\text{w}} \equiv \dot{M}_{\text{w}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$ and $\eta_{\text{a}} \equiv \dot{M}_{\text{acc}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$ are constant universal parameters, a common practice in analytic models of galaxy chemical evolution (see also Samui et al. 2008, and references therein). Though models specifically aimed at duplicating observations of the mass-metallicity relation commonly assume $Z_{\text{w}} = Z_{\text{g}}$, Dalcanton (2007) argues that metal-enriched outflows (those comprised predominantly of Type II supernova ejecta, and thus with $Z_{\text{w}} > Z_{\text{g}}$) are required if the rate of gas accretion is to be reasonable. Several analytic models focus on the efficiency of star formation as a function of stellar mass. In the context of the mass-metallicity relation, variations in the star formation efficiency affect galaxy gas fractions (as well as the M_{\star} - M_{halo} relation). In such models, an increase in the star

formation efficiency with galaxy mass—without the need for outflows—is sufficient to reproduce the observed mass-metallicity relation (Calura et al. 2009).

The mass-metallicity relation has also been studied in detail in several cosmological hydrodynamic simulations. Brooks et al. (2007) used a set of smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) simulations evolved with Gasoline (Wadsley et al. 2004) to argue that preferentially expelling gas from the low-mass galaxies is insufficient for reproducing the observed mass-metallicity relation. These authors claim that it is instead the reduced star-formation efficiency (and thus differences in galaxy gas fractions) induced by such feedback that is primarily responsible for driving the relation’s morphology. Conversely, Finlator & Davé (2008) used a suite of SPH simulations evolved with GADGET-2 (Springel 2005)—and therefore a different recipe for star-formation feedback¹ than Brooks et al. (2007)—in conjunction with detailed analytic models to show that, in general, $Z_g \propto \eta_w^{-1}$ for $\eta_w \gg 1$. Their favored model that reproduces the Erb et al. $z \sim 2.2$ mass-metallicity relation is one in which $\eta_w \propto \sigma^{-1}$, where σ is the galaxy velocity dispersion.² In this simulation,

¹Because of the resolution of cosmological SPH simulations, star-formation feedback must be included using “recipes” instead of directly modelling the underlying physics. The winds in Finlator & Davé’s simulations are implemented by physically moving gas particles away from star-forming regions. In Brooks et al.’s simulations, star formation thermally heats neighboring particles. In both prescriptions, the relevant particles are not allowed to interact hydrodynamically (Finlator & Davé) or radiatively cool (Brooks et al.) for some physically-motivated amount of time.

²This parametrization is motivated by the observations of Martin (2005) and the theory of momentum-driven winds (Murray et al. 2005); see §3.2.3 for more details.

$\sigma^{-1} \propto M_{\text{halo}}^{-1/3} \propto M_{\star}^{-1/3}$, which naturally explains why this η_w scaling is able to reproduce a mass-metallicity relation with $Z_g \propto M_{\star}^{0.3}$. These simple scaling relations highlight a link between a galaxy’s stellar mass, its halo mass, and its potential well: wind models aimed at successfully reproducing the mass-metallicity relation also need to correctly reproduce (or incorporate) the M_{\star} - M_{halo} relation.

A final class of models invokes a change in the galactic stellar initial mass function (GSIMF). The initial mass function (IMF) affects the mass-metallicity relation via the nucleosynthetic yield, i.e., the amount of oxygen (produced in Type II supernovae; Wallerstein 1962) made per mass of stars (see appendix A for a more thorough discussion). If, for example, the IMF is top-light in low-mass globular clusters, and massive clusters are not found in low mass galaxies, then low mass galaxies will simply produce less oxygen per unit stars than more massive galaxies, leading to a mass-metallicity relation like the observed one (Köppen et al. 2007). Similarly, while Calura & Menci (2009) use a hierarchical galaxy formation model to show that the mass-metallicity relation can be reproduced by assuming that a substantial fraction of the heavy elements is lost through metal-enhanced outflows in low mass galaxies, these authors also point out that a varying GSIMF helps in reproducing other observables, such as the $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ - σ relation in ellipticals (see also Recchi et al. 2009, and references therein).

These apparently conflicting results highlight several issues surrounding the origin of the mass-metallicity relation. First, a model that successfully reproduces the

observed mass-metallicity relation does *not* uniquely constrain the relation’s origin: gas dilution and galaxy outflows can be combined in a variety of ways—ranging from no preferential dilution to no preferential mass loss—to yield the same mass-metallicity relation. The question is what combinations of outflows and dilution can match the observed relation. Second, models must be constrained by observed gas fractions, not by the mass-metallicity relation alone. Finally, a fully consistent model of the mass-metallicity relation must allow for the fact that both galaxy gas fractions and galaxy outflow properties vary (as theory predicts and observations demonstrate) with galaxy mass. Furthermore, the way in which these properties depend on the galaxy mass may be more directly related to the galaxy’s host halo’s mass or velocity structure (such as the virial velocity or escape velocity). The origin of the mass-metallicity relation can then be constrained by appealing to external constraints set by observations of galaxy gas fractions and the empirically derived M_\star - M_{halo} relation. Here we present a new formalism for understanding the mass-metallicity relation that straightforwardly addresses these issues and apply it to the observed $z \sim 0$ mass-metallicity relation, where these external constraints are well measured.

Our approach is straightforward: we assume that galaxies populate a hypersurface describing their stellar and gas masses, halo properties, and metallicities. Observationally, Mannucci et al. (2010) and Lara-López et al. (2010) have recently shown that Z_g has less scatter at fixed M_\star and \dot{M}_{SFR} than at just

fixed M_* (i.e., the mass-metallicity relation); there is no evidence for evolution of this surface up to $z \sim 2.5$. This finding implies that the $M_*-\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}-Z_g$ hypersurface provides a more physical description of the underlying physics than just the M_*-Z_g plane. In our formalism, the star formation rate is closely linked with outflow efficiencies, and observationally, gas fractions and star formation rates are tightly correlated. We calculate the relevant hypersurface by expressing the time evolution of a galaxy’s stellar mass, gas mass, and gas-phase metallicity (\dot{M}_* , \dot{M}_g , and \dot{Z}_g , respectively) in terms of each piece’s possible sources and sinks (e.g., star formation, outflows, accretion). As detailed in § 3.3.1, the time dependence in these equations can be eliminated by dividing by the star formation rate to give the dZ_g/dM_* differential, which, once integrated, is the mass-metallicity relation. By assuming that as galaxies grow in stellar mass they stay along mean relations, we require that the mass-metallicity relation depends only on instantaneous galaxy properties, such as gas masses and outflow efficiencies. In this Chapter, we apply this formalism to the observed $z \sim 0$ mass-metallicity relation, where these other externally constrained mean relations are best understood.

This Chapter is organized as follows. In §3.2, we discuss the relevant observations: those of the $z = 0$ mass-metallicity relation (§3.2.1), galaxy gas fractions (§3.2.2), and galaxy outflows (and theoretical models thereof, §3.2.3). We lay out our formalism in §3.3.1, along with how we connect galaxy stellar masses to host halo properties (§3.3.2). In §3.4, we show how gas dilution and

outflows must combine in order to yield the observed mass-metallicity relation, and what this implies about galaxy outflows in order for predicted gas fractions to be consistent with the data. We then present in §3.5 what constraints wind metallicity and entrainment fraction considerations place on viable outflow models, with a summary and further discussion in §3.6 . Appendix A gives a detailed discussion of the definition of the nucleosynthetic yield, which sets the amplitude of the mass-metallicity relation. Appendix B describes the connection between gas masses, accretion, and star formation rates in our formalism, with implications for star formation efficiency.

Throughout we adopt a cosmology of $(\Omega_m, \Omega_b, \sigma_8, h) = (0.26, 0.047, 0.77, 0.72)$ and a Chabrier (2003a) initial mass function (IMF), unless otherwise noted. We note here that varying the cosmological parameters, within the ranges allowed from observations (e.g., Hinshaw et al. 2009), does not alter our conclusions. The impact of varying Ω_m or Ω_b , has, for example, little effect on the shape of the M_\star - M_{halo} relation or on the determination of the stellar masses in SDSS. Though varying σ_8 does change the number density of massive halos, it has little impact on the range of halo masses of interest here. Finally, we note that the virial relations only have a mild change in normalization when varying cosmological parameters, without having much impact on our overall results.

3.2. RELEVANT OBSERVATIONS

3.2.1. THE OBSERVED $z \sim 0$ MASS-METALLICITY RELATION

It is difficult—if not impossible—to measure the gas phase abundances of all of the elements not made in the Big Bang, i.e., true gas phase metallicities. Oxygen-to-hydrogen abundance ratios in H II regions, however, are relatively straightforward to estimate. Since oxygen is effectively produced only in Type II SNe—the deaths of massive, short-lived stars—and H II regions are associated with ongoing star formation, the gas-phase “mass-metallicity relation” typically refers to only the galaxy’s oxygen abundance in gas that is currently forming stars; we therefore will use “metals” and “oxygen” interchangeably unless otherwise noted. However, though $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ is measured at the sites of star formation, the measured abundances are the *birth* abundances of the H II regions; supernovae (the sites of oxygen production) destroy their nascent clouds, rendering so-called “self enrichment” of H II regions extremely rare. We therefore also assume that the galaxy gas is well-mixed, i.e., that the mixing time is short relative to the timescale for star formation.

Observationally, oxygen abundance increases with galaxy stellar mass. This relation has very little scatter (~ 0.1 dex in $12 + \log[\text{O}/\text{H}]$ at fixed stellar mass), though severe outliers do exist (Chapter 2). The amplitude and slope of the

mass-metallicity relation, however, are not well constrained, despite exquisite and extensive data (e.g., from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey [SDSS]; Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2006). This ambiguity is due to the theoretical uncertainties in how to convert emission-line fluxes to $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$, as one must make assumptions about both the gas temperature and ionization structure in order to derive $\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$. While the electron temperature can be estimated directly using the [O III] $\lambda 4363$ auroral line, this line is extremely weak and usually only detectable in very metal-poor environments. Thus, it is common to calibrate measurement methods using much stronger forbidden emission lines such as [O II] $\lambda\lambda 3726, 3729$, $\text{H}\beta$, [O III] $\lambda\lambda 4959, 5007$, $\text{H}\alpha$, and [N II] $\lambda 6584$ based on the so-called direct [O III] $\lambda 4363$ T_e method. However, since [O III] $\lambda 4363$ preferentially emits in high-temperature regions, this calibration can lead to an over-estimate of the electron temperature based on this line and thus an under-estimate of the oxygen abundance (Kewley & Ellison 2008). It is therefore common to instead calibrate strong-line measurement methods based on theoretical photoionization models. On the other hand, there are arguments that such strong-line methods *over*-estimate the true abundance (Kennicutt et al. 2003). In addition to these problems, most indicators are either double-valued at low metallicities (such as the popular R_{23} indicator) or saturate at high metallicities as emission-line cooling shifts to the near-infrared (e.g., Bresolin 2006).

Kewley & Ellison (2008) highlight many of these issues, and derive $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ for a large set of galaxies from SDSS using ten indicators (eight of which we consider here: T04, Tremonti et al. 2004; D02, Denicoló et al. 2002; KK04, Kobulnicky & Kewley 2004; Z94, Zaritsky et al. 1994; KD02, Kewley & Dopita 2002; M91, McGaugh 1991; PP04O3N2 and PP04N2, using the Pettini & Pagel 2004 $([\text{O III}]/\text{H}\beta)/([\text{N II}]/\text{H}\alpha)$ and $[\text{N II}]/\text{H}\alpha$ flux ratios, respectively). The Kewley & Ellison fits to the mass-metallicity relation are given in Table 3.1, where we have converted from a Kroupa (2001) to a Chabrier (2003a) IMF and from $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ to $\log Z_{\text{g}}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \log Z_{\text{g}} &= [12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})] - 12 - \log \left[\frac{M_{\text{O}}/M_{\text{H}}}{X M_{\text{H}} + Y M_{\text{He}}} \right] \\ &= \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) - \log \left[\frac{15.999/1.0079}{0.75 \times 1.0079 + 0.25 \times 4.0026} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

These mass-metallicity relations are plotted in Figure 3.1; the scatter in Z_{g} at fixed M_{\star} for each mass-metallicity relation is smaller by a factor of 2–3 than the spread in normalizations, implying that the differences are caused by the systematics discussed above.

The two relations in black in Figure 3.1 and in bold in Table 3.1 (T04, Tremonti et al. 2004 and D02, Denicoló et al. 2002) are the two mass-metallicity relations we focus on in § 3.4. While we do not favor any one $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ indicator, we take these two mass-metallicity relations as representative of the normalizations and slopes observations as a whole. The D02 indicator is a linear relation between

the [N II] $\lambda 6584$ /H α ratio and $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ calibrated against T_e metallicities. The relatively low normalization of this method is common for T_e -calibrated indicators. The T04 method is based on theoretical stellar population synthesis and photoionization models combined with a Bayesian analysis of many more strong emission lines than used in most methods.

3.2.2. OBSERVED GAS FRACTIONS OF $z \sim 0$ GALAXIES

Figure 3.2 shows how the gas-to-stellar mass ratio F_g (left panel) and gas mass M_g (right panel) vary with galaxy stellar mass. The open diamonds are total H I gas masses measured from 21 cm line fluxes (McGaugh 2005). The crosses are also H I gas masses, with stellar masses measured from SDSS (Garcia-Appadoo et al. 2009; West et al. 2009, 2010). The filled circles represent the total H I + H₂ gas masses (including a correction for helium) from The H I Nearby Galaxy Survey (THINGS), with the H₂ masses derived from HERA CO-Line Extragalactic Survey (HERACLES) and the Berkeley-Illinois-Maryland Association Survey of Nearby Galaxies (BIMA SONG) CO measurements (Leroy et al. 2008). Though there is large scatter in the gas fraction at a fixed stellar mass, gas fractions clearly decrease as M_\star increases; this behavior is also found in cosmological hydrodynamic simulations (e.g., Hopkins et al. 2008). The mean $\log F_g$ in bins of $\Delta \log M_\star = 0.4$ dex for $8.1 \leq \log M_\star \leq 11.3$ is overplotted with the large solid orange squares; we list these means and uncertainties in Table 3.2. We note that each of these data sets

focus on star-forming galaxies similar to those in which $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ is measurable; surveys not restricted to actively star-forming galaxies (e.g., Catinella et al. 2010) lead to much lower average gas fractions.

We parameterize F_g as power-law of the form

$$F_g \equiv \frac{M_g}{M_\star} = \left(\frac{M_\star}{M_{\star,0}} \right)^{-\gamma} = K_f M_\star^{-\gamma}, \quad (3.2)$$

with $\gamma > 0$. Table 3.3 lists $\log M_{\star,0}$, K_f and γ for our adopted gas relations. As we show in §3.3.1, F_g is a more convenient parameterization than the commonly used and more arguably intuitive μ_g , the gas mass as a fraction of the total baryonic galaxy mass $M_\star + M_g$,

$$\mu_g \equiv \frac{M_g}{M_g + M_\star} = \frac{F_g}{1 + F_g}. \quad (3.3)$$

The “total” gas fraction relation is a power-law fit to the combined McGaugh, Leroy et al., and Garcia-Appadoo et al. data sets, offset by +0.2 dex. In order to understand the contribution of a sloped gas fraction relation to the mass-metallicity relation, we also consider a flat gas relation of $M_g = 0.5M_\star$, shown in green in Figure 3.2.

For reference, Figure 3.2 shows how the total baryonic halo mass, $(\Omega_b/\Omega_m)M_h$, varies with stellar mass (halo mass as a function of M_\star is calculated as discussed in §3.3.2). The offset between the baryonic halo mass and $M_\star + M_g$ is evidence of

the so-called missing baryon problem; the missing baryons are either hot or have been expelled from the halos by $z = 0$ (e.g., Crain et al. 2007). Figure 3.2 further highlights the fact that for $M_\star \lesssim 10^{10} M_\odot$, the fraction of baryons in the form of cold gas is roughly constant (i.e., the blue and red lines are roughly parallel). Moreover, while massive galaxies are gas poor, galaxies with stellar masses below $\sim 10^{9.5} M_\odot$ have most of their mass in the form of gas: the processes responsible for the “missing baryons” in $z = 0$ halos must also account for this inefficiency of star formation in low mass halos. We discuss this issue further in Appendix B.

The Kennicutt-Schmidt (K-S, Kennicutt 1998; Schmidt 1959) law is commonly used to indirectly estimate gas masses in star-forming galaxies when direct gas masses are expensive (or currently impossible) to achieve, such as at high redshifts (e.g., Erb et al. 2006b) or for large samples of galaxies (e.g., Tremonti et al. 2004). Furthermore, since $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ is measured only in star-forming gas, it is reasonable to consider gas fractions that trace this same gas. The purple lines in Figure 3.2 are the gas masses we derive from applying the K-S law to star-forming Data Release 4 SDSS galaxies with z -band magnitude errors of < 0.01 mag (Brinchmann et al. 2004; Adelman-McCarthy et al. 2006). Specifically, we relate the star formation rate surface density Σ_{SFR} to the gas surface density Σ_g by

$$\Sigma_{\text{SFR}} \equiv \frac{\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}}{A_g} = K_g \Sigma_g^\alpha = 1.67 \times 10^{-4} \left(\frac{\Sigma_g}{1 M_\odot \text{ pc}^{-2}} \right)^{1.4} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2} \quad (3.4)$$

from Kennicutt (1998), where we have corrected for the fact that the Brinchmann et al. (2004) star formation rates are based on a Kroupa (2001) IMF while the Kennicutt relation is based on a Salpeter (1955) IMF. SDSS spectra are taken within a $3''$ aperture; therefore, to measure *total* galaxy properties (e.g., star formation rates and stellar masses), the fact that the aperture does not subtend the entire galaxy must be corrected for. We therefore consider Σ_{SFR} and M_{\star} both for the full galaxy-light radius (which we take to be 1.1 times the 90th percentile z -band isophotal radius $R_{90,z}$) and only within the fiber, i.e., we take

$$A_g = \pi R_g^2 = \pi R_{\text{light}}^2 = \pi \times \begin{cases} 1.1^2 \times R_{90,z}^2; & \text{solid lines.} \\ R_{\text{fiber}}^2; & \text{dashed line.} \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

The galaxy gas mass is then simply

$$M_g = \left(\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}} \times \frac{A_g^{\alpha-1}}{K_g} \right)^{1/\alpha}. \quad (3.6)$$

The shaded contours in the right panel of Figure 3.2 denote the $1\text{-}\sigma$ and $2\text{-}\sigma$ gas masses derived for the entire galaxy ($R_g = 1.1R_{90,z}$) in running bins of $\log M_{\star}$ from $\log M_{\star} = 8.3$ to 11.1; for clarity, galaxies falling outside this region are not shown. The solid line is an eyeball power-law fit to the median $R_g = 1.1R_{90,z}$ gas masses while the dashed line is the same for the gas (and stellar) masses within the SDSS fiber. The fact that these relations are quite similar to one another indicates that aperture corrections are relatively small and/or that gas fractions are relatively scale-invariant within $1.1R_{90,z}$.

The gas masses estimated from the K-S law and the measurements of total cold gas masses roughly agree with one another on the low gas fraction of $F_g \sim 0.1$ at $\log M_\star \sim 11$, and that F_g increases with decreasing stellar mass. The amount of this increase in gas fraction, however, is in stark disagreement, with a range of over an order of magnitude in F_g . The K-S law only traces star-forming gas and therefore traces molecular gas more closely than atomic, and dwarf galaxies are deficient in molecular gas (Leroy et al. 2008). At large radii in more massive galaxies, the gas is predominately atomic, i.e., the H I radii of galaxies is often much larger than the optical (star-forming) radii (Boomsma et al. 2008; Walter et al. 2008). For the purposes of the mass-metallicity relation, what matters is the total amount of gas that is able to effectively mix and dilute metals. A lower limit to this gas mass is the gas that is able to collapse and form stars—the gas traced by the K-S law. If on the other hand the atomic and molecular gas are well mixed (as opposed to, e.g., molecular gas only populating the galaxy center and atomic gas being at large radii), then the total gas fractions are more applicable. Finally, neither of these gas fraction estimates include ionized gas; if such gas is not only prevalent in typical galaxies but also has efficient mass transfer with both supernova ejecta and gas that will cool to form molecular clouds (and subsequently H II regions), then even the “total” gas fraction relation will be an underestimate of the gas diluting the galaxies’ metals.

3.2.3. GALAXY OUTFLOWS

Though observations of galaxy-scale outflows are notoriously difficult, galaxy winds observed in a range of star-forming galaxies display a complex, multiphase structure. Since detectability increases with the star formation rate density (Veilleux et al. 2005), however, the most detailed studies of galaxy winds have been of the outflows associated with extreme starbursts, namely, (ultra)luminous infrared galaxies ([U]LIRGs). Studies of blue-shifted absorption-lines reveal both neutral (Heckman et al. 2000; Rupke et al. 2002; Martin 2005) and photoionized gas (Grimes et al. 2009), often with several kinematically distinct components. In contrast, X-ray emission around local starbursts such as M82 indicates a hot ($T \sim 10^{6.5-10^8}$ K), tenuous ($n \sim 10^{-4}-10^{-3}$ cm $^{-3}$) wind fluid (Strickland & Stevens 2000; Strickland & Heckman 2007, 2009). Wind velocities derived from both emission and absorption line studies are typically hundreds of km s $^{-1}$ (Martin 2005; Grimes et al. 2009). The systemic outflow velocity of emitting regions in this coronal gas phase is found to be positively correlated with the ionization energy of the absorbing ion (Grimes et al. 2006), indicating the presence of a shock, though in some cases this has been interpreted as a possible AGN contribution to the outflow (Spoon & Holt 2009). While outflows are highly multiphase, current indications are that most of the mass is in a colder neutral phase, even if the bulk of the energy is in a hot phase. The outflow velocity v_w of this cold gas is typically comparable to one to a few times

the galaxy’s circular velocity v_{circ} (Martin 2005), which is comparable to the galaxy’s virial velocity v_{vir} (e.g., Diemand et al. 2007).

The scaling $v_w \sim v_{\text{vir}}$ follows naturally if momentum transfer from radiation pressure is driving the wind (Murray et al. 2005). For radiation pressure to be effective, the starburst must be Eddington limited and the outflowing gas has an asymptotic velocity of

$$v_w(\infty) = 2v_{\text{esc}} \left(\frac{L}{L_{\text{edd}}} - 1 \right)^{1/2}, \quad (3.7)$$

where the escape velocity v_{esc} is comparable to the virial velocity. The wind velocity is therefore typically taken to be $v_w = 3v_{\text{vir}}$. In the single-scattering limit (Murray et al. 2005),

$$\dot{M}_w v_w = \frac{L_{\text{starburst}}}{c} = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{nuc}} \dot{M}_{\text{SFR}} c^2}{c}, \quad (3.8)$$

where $L_{\text{starburst}}$ is the starburst luminosity and $\epsilon_{\text{nuc}} = 8 \times 10^{-4}$ is the nuclear burning efficiency. Thus the mass-loading factor³ η_w is proportional to the inverse of the virial velocity such that

$$\eta_w \Big|_{\text{momentum}} \equiv \frac{\dot{M}_w}{\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}} = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{nuc}} c}{v_w} \sim \frac{80 \text{ km s}^{-1}}{v_{\text{vir}}}. \quad (3.9)$$

³Definitions in the literature of the “mass-loading factor” vary; we take it to mean the *total* outflow mass rate divided by the *total* star formation rate (including short-lived stars).

This same scaling is achieved if the wind is driven by cosmic rays (Socrates et al. 2008).

On the other hand, the outflow may be driven by energy transfer, perhaps from supernovae thermally heating the ISM (Chevalier & Clegg 1985; Dekel & Silk 1986; Silk & Rees 1998; Murray et al. 2005). In this popular scenario,

$$\frac{1}{2}\dot{M}_w v_w^2 \approx \xi E_{\text{SN}} \times [\# \text{ of SNe per solar mass of stars formed}] \dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}, \quad (3.10)$$

where $E_{\text{SN}} \sim 10^{51}$ erg is the typical energy per supernova and ξ is the efficiency with which supernovae transfer energy to the ISM. Letting $\xi = 0.1$, i.e., a 10% efficiency, and taking the number of supernovae per unit mass to be 10^{-2} , this yields a mass-loading factor of

$$\eta_w|_{\text{energy}} \equiv \frac{\dot{M}_w}{\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}} \sim \left(\frac{73 \text{ km s}^{-1}}{v_{\text{vir}}} \right)^2, \quad (3.11)$$

where we have implicitly assumed $v_w \approx 3v_{\text{vir}}$. While we in general consider models in which $\eta_w \propto v_{\text{vir}}^{-\beta}$ for $\beta > 0$ (or, equivalently, $\eta_w \propto M_{\text{halo}}^{-\beta/3}$, see §3.3.2); it is helpful to keep the normalizations suggested by equations (3.9) and (3.11) in mind.

Except via the impact of outflows on galaxy gas fractions, the mass-metallicity relation is insensitive to the *total* mass outflow rate \dot{M}_w . Instead, as we show in §3.3.1, oxygen depletion due to winds is governed by the rate of metal loss, $Z_w \dot{M}_w$, where Z_w is the metallicity of the outflow; in our case (see §3.2.1), the mass ratio

of oxygen in the outflowing material. While many metals (oxygen, as well as, e.g., iron, sodium, carbon, magnesium, and neon; Heckman et al. 2000; Martin 2005; Strickland & Heckman 2007; Martin & Bouché 2009; Grimes et al. 2009; Spoon & Holt 2009) are observed in galaxy outflows, there are relatively few observations of outflowing oxygen, and elemental abundances in the wind fluid are rarely reported. Strickland & Heckman (2009), however, find that the X-ray emitting outflow from M82 has a high enough metal content that it is consistent with containing nearly all of the freshly produced metals in the starburst with an inferred velocity of $\sim 1000\text{--}2000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Combined with their interpretation that the outflow has very little entrained gas (i.e., that it is essentially comprised solely of supernova ejecta), this implies that the metallicity of the outflow is quite high. (We note that in this interpretation of the data, supernova explosions surprisingly have no radiative energy losses when interacting with the ambient ISM [$\xi = 1$ in equation 3.10]; see also Heckman 2003.) This picture is further complicated by the fact that outflows are likely multi-phase, and the metallicities and escape fractions in, e.g., the cold and ionized phases may be different. From the perspective of the mass-metallicity relation, however, what matters is the total amount of expelled oxygen relative to the total amount of expelled gas, where “expelled” oxygen or gas is just the oxygen or gas that has either been physically ejected from the galaxy or simply heated up such that it cannot efficiently transfer mass to the gas that is able to cool and form stars and thus be observed contributing to the mass-metallicity relation.

3.3. THE FORMALISM

3.3.1. THE MASS-METALLICITY RELATION

The three galaxy masses relevant to the mass-metallicity relation are the total galaxy mass in stars, M_\star , the galaxy gas mass, M_g , and the mass of gas-phase metals, M_Z . We base our model on relating the instantaneous change in these masses via their sources and sinks to the instantaneous galaxy star formation rate, \dot{M}_{SFR} , ignoring environmental effects such as mergers and tidal stripping. The instantaneous change in the stellar mass,

$$\dot{M}_\star = \dot{M}_{\text{SFR}} - \dot{M}_{\text{recy}} \quad (3.12)$$

$$= \dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}(1 - f_{\text{recy}}), \quad (3.13)$$

is given by the creation of stars (\dot{M}_{SFR}) and the rate at which stars return mass to the ISM when they die, \dot{M}_{recy} . (We include the mass of stellar remnants in M_\star .) The relative rate of these two effects, $f_{\text{recy}} \equiv \dot{M}_{\text{recy}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$, depends on the star formation history and therefore varies somewhat with time; its effect on our results, however, is small, and we are safe to adopt $f_{\text{recy}} = 0.2$. (See Appendix A for a more thorough discussion of f_{recy} .)

The gas mass is also regulated by the star formation rate and f_{recy} , with gas accretion adding gas and outflows removing gas from the system. The instantaneous

change in M_g is therefore

$$\dot{M}_g = \dot{M}_{\text{acc}} - \dot{M}_{\text{SFR}} + \dot{M}_{\text{recy}} - \dot{M}_w \quad (3.14)$$

$$= \dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}(\eta_a - 1 + f_{\text{recy}} - \eta_w), \quad (3.15)$$

where \dot{M}_{acc} is the gas accretion rate and \dot{M}_w is the mass rate of outflowing gas. As introduced in §3.2.3, we define the mass-loading factor η_w as $\dot{M}_w/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$; analogously, $\eta_a \equiv \dot{M}_{\text{acc}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$. The sources and sinks of metals are essentially the same as for gas, except that each component can have a different metallicity. Hence,

$$\dot{M}_Z = Z_{\text{IGM}}\dot{M}_{\text{acc}} - Z_g\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}} + Z_{\text{ej}}\dot{M}_{\text{recy}} - Z_w\dot{M}_w \quad (3.16)$$

$$= \dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}(y + Z_g(\zeta_a - \zeta_w - 1)), \quad (3.17)$$

where Z_{IGM} is the metallicity of accreting gas, Z_g is the ISM metallicity, Z_{ej} is the metallicity of gas being returned to the ISM by dying stars, and Z_w is the metallicity of outflowing gas. The yield y is the nucleosynthetic yield, which is defined as the rate at which metals are being returned to the ISM relative to the current star formation rate, i.e.,

$$y = \frac{\dot{M}_{\text{new metals}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{recy}}} \times \frac{\dot{M}_{\text{recy}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}} = Z_{\text{ej}}f_{\text{recy}}. \quad (3.18)$$

After the first generation of Type II supernovae explode ($\sim 10^7$ yr), y is constant for continuous star formation. The IMF and Type II supernova yields, however, are

highly uncertain, so the true value of y is only constrained to be $0.08 \lesssim y \lesssim 0.023$ (e.g., Finlator & Davé 2008); we adopt a mid-range value of $y = 0.015$. (Note that this is not the same definition as in §2.4.3; see Appendix A for more details.)

The metallicity-weighted mass-loading factors ζ_a and ζ_w in equation (3.17) describe the relative rates at which metals are being accreted and expelled from the system, and are defined as

$$\zeta_a \equiv \frac{Z_{\text{IGM}}}{Z_g} \times \frac{\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}} = \left(\frac{Z_{\text{IGM}}}{Z_g} \right) \eta_a, \text{ and} \quad (3.19)$$

$$\zeta_w \equiv \frac{Z_w}{Z_g} \times \frac{\dot{M}_w}{\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}} = \left(\frac{Z_w}{Z_g} \right) \eta_w. \quad (3.20)$$

The metallicity of accreting gas, Z_{IGM} , is typically taken to be zero, though SPH simulations indicate that due to previous episodes of enrichment of the intergalactic medium (IGM) from metal-containing galaxy outflows, the effective Z_{IGM} may be non-negligible (Finlator & Davé 2008; Oppenheimer et al. 2009). Because a self-consistent model of an enriched IGM will be based on the evolution of the mass-metallicity relation, we will for now take Z_{IGM} and thus $\zeta_a = 0$, though we will return to the ramifications of this assumption in §3.6. The wind metallicity, Z_w , is often assumed to be the ISM metallicity (Finlator & Davé 2008; Erb 2008), giving $\zeta_w = \eta_w$. However, Z_g is simply a lower-limit to the possible outflow metallicity (if the wind is driven by supernovae, then it can be metal-enriched relative to the ambient ISM, but not metal-depleted). The actual wind metallicity will depend on the fraction f_e of the outflow that is entrained interstellar gas, which has a generic

metallicity Z_g , and the fraction $1 - f_e$ that is from newly exploded supernovae and therefore has a metallicity $Z_{\text{ej,max}} \sim 0.1$ (see Appendix A). The wind metallicity is thus

$$Z_w = (1 - f_e)Z_{\text{ej,max}} + f_e Z_g, \quad (3.21)$$

where we note that f_e may vary with galaxy mass and must satisfy $0 \leq f_e < 1$.

Since we are interested in the mass-metallicity relation at $z = 0$, and not its rate of change, it is useful to eliminate the time-dependence in equations (3.12–3.17). We assume galaxies live on a hypersurface of M_g , M_\star , Z_g , halo, accretion and wind properties. Dividing out the time-dependence in these equations allows us to solve for the shape of this surface, with observations setting the amplitude. Combining equations (3.13) and (3.15),

$$\frac{dM_g}{dM_\star} = \frac{\eta_a - \eta_w - 1 + f_{\text{recy}}}{1 - f_{\text{recy}}} = F_g(1 - \gamma), \quad (3.22)$$

where we include $dM_g/dM_\star = F_g(1 - \gamma)$ based on our parameterization of $F_g = M_g/M_\star$ (equation 3.2) introduced in §3.2.2. Note that if we assume we know how gas fractions vary with stellar mass (§3.2.2), then for any given wind model η_w , the accretion rate as a function of the star formation rate η_a is uniquely determined. We explore this point and its implications in Appendix B.

The rate of change of the gas phase metallicity Z_g is

$$\dot{Z}_g = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{M_Z}{M_g} = \frac{\dot{M}_Z}{M_g} - \frac{Z_g}{M_g} \dot{M}_g = \frac{1}{M_g} [\dot{M}_Z - Z_g \dot{M}_g]. \quad (3.23)$$

We can now combine equations (3.13), (3.15), (3.17), and (3.23) to find

$$\frac{dZ_g}{dM_\star} = \frac{y + Z_g \left(\zeta_a - \zeta_w - 1 - \frac{\dot{M}_g}{M_{\text{SFR}}} \right)}{M_g (1 - f_{\text{recy}})} \quad (3.24)$$

$$= \frac{y + Z_g [\zeta_a - \zeta_w - 1 - F_g (1 - \gamma)]}{M_g (1 - f_{\text{recy}})}. \quad (3.25)$$

Equation (3.24) can be integrated with respect to M_\star to find $Z_g(M_\star)$. Furthermore, using the Kewley & Ellison (2008) fits (§ 3.2.1, Table 3.1), we can turn the problem around: by assuming we know the mass-metallicity relation (and dZ_g/dM_\star), we can infer the required relation between, e.g., F_g and ζ_w . Specifically, by rearranging equation (3.24), we find

$$Z_g = y \left[\zeta_w - \zeta_a + F_g (1 - f_{\text{recy}}) \left(\frac{d \log M_g}{d \log M_\star} + \frac{d \log Z_g}{d \log M_\star} \right) + 1 \right]^{-1} \quad (3.26)$$

$$= y [\zeta_w - \zeta_a + \alpha F_g + 1]^{-1}, \quad (3.27)$$

where

$$\alpha \equiv (1 - f_{\text{recy}}) ([d \log M_g / d \log M_\star] + [d \log Z_g / d \log M_\star]) \quad (3.28)$$

is a factor of order unity. Equation (3.27) is the mass-metallicity relation; by finding combinations of the yield, outflow strength, and gas fractions that combine as stated on the right-hand side to give $Z_g(M_*)$ on the left-hand side, we can explicitly reproduce the observed mass-metallicity relation. This is the tack we take in §3.4.

3.3.2. CONNECTING GALAXIES AND HALOS

A number of methods have been developed to empirically connect galaxies to halos. One straightforward approach is the cumulative matching of galaxy (n_{gal}) and halo (n_{halo}) number counts (e.g., Vale & Ostriker 2004; Shankar et al. 2006; Conroy & Wechsler 2009), i.e.,

$$n_{\text{gal}}(> M_*) = n_{\text{halo}}(> M_{\text{halo}}). \quad (3.29)$$

Assuming that each halo (and subhalo) contains a galaxy, equation (3.29) determines the average mapping between halo mass and galaxy mass.

We adopt one of the latest determinations of the M_* - M_{halo} relation by Moster et al. (2009, top panel of Figure 3.3),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{M_*}{M_{\text{halo}}} &= 0.0633(1+z)^{-0.72} \\ &\times \left[\left(\frac{M_{\text{halo}}}{M_{\text{h},0}} \right)^{-1.06-0.17z} + \left(\frac{M_{\text{halo}}}{M_{\text{h},0}} \right)^{0.556(1+z)^{-0.26}} \right]^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.30)$$

with the zero point increased by 0.05 dex to correct from a Kroupa (2001) to a Chabrier (2003b) IMF (Bernardi et al. 2010), and where

$$\log M_{h,0}/M_{\odot} = [\log 11.88] (1+z)^{0.019}. \quad (3.31)$$

The Moster et al. (2009) M_{\star} - M_{halo} mapping is in good agreement with constraints from galaxy-galaxy lensing, galaxy clustering, and predictions of semi-analytic models. Following the scaling relations in Tonini et al. (2006, and references therein), we have verified that equation (3.31) yields a Tully-Fisher relation (Tully & Fisher 1977) consistent with the more recent calibrations by Pizagno et al. (2007), as long as the dynamical contribution of the dark matter within a few optical radii is less than the one predicted by a pure Navarro, Frenk, & White (1996) mass profile, in line with many other studies (e.g., Salucci et al. 2007). Also note that the subhalo masses quoted by Moster et al. refer to *unstripped* quantities, which represent more reliable indicators of the intrinsic potential well in which satellites formed.

The Moster et al. relation is in broad agreement with previous studies, such as the ones by Shankar et al. (2006), although the latter relied on a stellar mass function based on dynamical mass-to-light ratios that cannot be directly used in the present study based on SDSS stellar masses. Despite the different techniques adopted, most of the studies find consistent results on the M_{\star} - M_{halo} relation, especially in the mass range of interest here, i.e., star-forming galaxies with stellar mass $\lesssim 2 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ and hence halos with mass $\lesssim 5 \times 10^{12} h^{-1} M_{\odot}$ (Firmani et al. 2009; More et al. 2010).

If winds depend on the potential well depth of the halo rather than the mass itself, then the halo virial velocity v_{vir} is more relevant than M_{halo} . Roughly speaking,

$$v_{\text{vir}}^2 \sim \Phi \sim \frac{GM_{\text{halo}}}{R_{\text{halo}}}, \quad (3.32)$$

where the dependence of the halo radius R_{halo} on the halo mass is a function of both cosmology and the structure of the halo (Łokas & Mamon 2001; Ferrarese 2002; Loeb & Peebles 2003; Baes et al. 2003). We connect v_{vir} to M_{halo} via

$$\begin{aligned} v_{\text{vir}} &= \left(\frac{GM_{\text{halo}}}{R_{\text{vir}}} \right)^{1/2} \\ &= 112.6 \left(\frac{M_{\text{halo}}}{10^{12} M_{\odot}} \right)^{1/3} \times \left[\frac{\Omega_m}{0.25} \frac{1}{\Omega_m^z} \frac{\Delta}{18\pi^2} \right]^{1/6} (1+z)^{1/2} \text{ km s}^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.33)$$

where the mean density contrast (relative to the critical density) within the virial radius R_{vir} is $\Delta = 18\pi^2 + 82d - 39d^2$, with $d \equiv \Omega_m^z - 1$, and $\Omega_m^z = \Omega_m(1+z)^3 / [\Omega_m(1+z)^3 + \Omega_{\Lambda}]$ (Bryan & Norman 1998; Barkana & Loeb 2001). The bottom panel of Figure 3.3 shows how v_{vir} varies with stellar mass in this model. We have verified that our M_{\star} - v_{vir} relation is in good agreement with the M_{\star} - v_{200} relation recently derived by Dutton et al. (2010a).

3.4. MODELS OF THE MASS-METALLICITY RELATION

We now turn to what is required to reproduce the observed mass-metallicity relation. Rearranging equation (3.27), we find

$$\frac{y}{Z_g} - 1 = \zeta_w - \zeta_a + \alpha F_g, \quad (3.34)$$

where we hereafter take $\zeta_a = 0$ (see §3.6.3 for a discussion of this choice).

Expressed this way, the metallicity Z_g is related explicitly to a sum of ζ_w (a term describing outflows) and $F_g = M_g/M_\star$ (a term describing the galaxy gas content). Equation (3.34), or equivalently equation (3.27), is the principal theoretical result of this Chapter, connecting gas-phase metallicities to gas fractions, outflows, and accretion. Functionally, one can use equation (3.34) to find working models for a given $Z_g(M_\star)$ in several ways:

1. Assume y and $Z_g(M_\star)$ are known; use trial and error to find combinations of $\zeta_w(v_{\text{vir}})$ and $[\alpha F_g](M_\star)$ that satisfy equation (3.34).
2. Assume y , $Z_g(M_\star)$, and $\zeta_w(v_{\text{vir}})$ are known; solve for $d \log M_g / d \log M_\star$ in equation (3.24) and integrate to find $M_g(M_\star)$.
3. Assume y , $Z_g(M_\star)$, and $M_g(M_\star)$ are known; equation (3.34) then says

$$\zeta_w = y/Z_g - 1 - \alpha F_g.$$

Method 1 works well for developing intuition regarding tensions in the data and theoretical wind models, while methods 2 and 3 yield models that exactly produce the observed mass-metallicity relation, as demonstrated for the Tremonti et al. mass-metallicity relation in Figures 3.4 and 3.6. Best-fitting models of ζ_w for the T04 mass-metallicity relation and relations based on other indicators (§ 3.2.1) are plotted in Figure 3.5–3.7 and tabulated in Table 3.4. In the top two panels of Figure 3.4, the observations are shown as the solid black curves; the colored lines denote models with different scalings of ζ_w with v_{vir} . Panel (a) shows the mass-metallicity relation ($\log Z_g$ as a function of $\log M_\star$). The models are chosen so that they give $\zeta_w + \alpha F_g$ to equal the observed $y/Z_g - 1$ (panel b). Gas fractions and $\zeta_w(v_{\text{vir}})$ are plotted in panels (c) and (d), respectively.

There are two striking features of the form of $\zeta_w + \alpha F_g$ in panel (b). First, $\zeta_w + \alpha F_g$ is not a power law (because the mass-metallicity relation and therefore $y/Z_g - 1$ as a function of M_\star is not a power law). Specifically, $\zeta_w + \alpha F_g$ increases rapidly at low masses but flattens at high mass; this translates into either ζ_w or F_g needing to scale steeply with mass in order to reproduce the steepness of the mass-metallicity relation, but either ζ_w or F_g needs to likewise flatten at high masses in order to reproduce the observed turnover of the mass-metallicity relation. Because of uncertainties in the nucleosynthetic yield, the normalization of the mass-metallicity relation, and possible saturation of metallicity indicators at high $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ (see Appendix A and § 3.2.1), we will consider both the

mass-metallicity relation across the mass range $8.1 \leq \log M_\star \leq 11.3$ and restricted to below $M_\star \sim 10.5 M_\odot$.

The gas fractions needed to dilute the metals in the absence of winds ($\zeta_w = 0$) are shown as the solid orange line in Figure 3.4; these gas fractions are higher by a factor of $\gtrsim 3$ than observed cold gas fractions in typical $z \sim 0$ galaxies. For a non-varying yield, outflows are therefore required in order to keep the observed mass-metallicity relation consistent with galaxy gas fraction observations. This conclusion holds even more strongly for the other mass-metallicity relations plotted in Figure 3.1: in the absence of winds, lower metallicities imply higher gas fractions.

The other colored lines in Figure 3.4 show the required gas fractions if we assume $\zeta_w = [50 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}}$ (pink, long-dashed), $([85 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}})^2$ (blue, short-dashed), or $([85 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}})^3$ (green, dotted). Both the momentum-driven and energy-driven ζ_w scalings require F_g to scale more steeply with mass than is observed: for the shown normalizations, at $\log M_\star \lesssim 9.5$, higher than observed F_g are needed, while for higher normalizations, lower than observed F_g are needed at $\log M_\star \gtrsim 10$. Lower normalizations of ζ_w force F_g to asymptote to the no winds case. A steeper scaling of ζ_w with v_{vir} , however, leads to more reasonable gas fractions.

We quantify what $\zeta_w(v_{\text{vir}})$ scalings are required in order to reproduce the mass-metallicity relation while remaining consistent with the observed gas fractions by using method 2: by taking a given ζ_w we can compare the corresponding F_g

to binned gas fractions (§3.2.2, Table 3.2) to calculate a χ^2 . Parameterizing ζ_w as $(v_0/v_{\text{vir}})^{-b} + \zeta_{w,0}$, the best-fit model for the T04 mass-metallicity relation is $\zeta_w = (78 \text{ km s}^{-1}/v_{\text{vir}})^{-3.81} + 0.19$, as shown in Figure 3.5. We show the $\Delta\chi^2$ contours for 1-, 2-, and 3- σ using the $\Delta\chi^2$ -to- σ conversion from Press et al. (1992) for 5 degrees-of-freedom (8 data points and 3 parameters). The best-fit values do not change significantly if the dispersion about the mean is used instead of the uncertainties when calculating χ^2 , and we safely consider the points and errors for the binned data to be uncorrelated because the measurements for individual galaxies do not depend on one another. Also, we choose to bin F_g instead of Z_g because the mass-metallicity relation has been more rigorously measured than the F_g - M_* relation. The white regions in Figure 3.5 correspond to models that are unphysical because they require negative gas fractions. The best-fit models are always close to the border between physical and unphysical regions in parameter space, reflecting the fact that gas fractions at $z = 0$ are relatively small; it takes only a small change in ζ_w to go from a small F_g to a negative one.

The best-fit ζ_w can be strongly driven by the turnover of the mass-metallicity relation and change in slope of the M_* - v_{vir} relation above $\log M_* = 10.5$. For example, for the T04 mass-metallicity relation, if we instead only consider the data at $\log M_* < 10.5$, the best-fit ζ_w is instead $(72 \text{ km s}^{-1}/v_{\text{vir}})^{-4.69} + 0.41$; that is, the velocity normalization v_0 does not change much, but the slope steepens and the constant offset $\zeta_{w,0}$ increases. Whether the best-fit ζ_w shifts to higher b and $\zeta_{w,0}$ (T04

and D02), lower b and $\zeta_{w,0}$ (M91, Z94, PP04O3N2, and PP04N2), or doesn't change (KD02 and KK04) when only modeling $\log M_\star < 10.5$ depends on the subtle details of the particular fit to the mass-metallicity relation under consideration. In all cases, however, $\Delta\chi^2$ for the parameters for the best fitting ζ_w for a given mass-metallicity relation when the entire mass range is modeled fall within $1\text{-}\sigma$ of the $\log M_\star < 10.5$ best fitting model for that indicator (but not necessarily vice-versa, since the best fitting low-mass model often requires negative gas fractions if extrapolated above $10^{10.5}M_\odot$). The $1\text{-}\sigma$ range of ζ_w for the T04 mass-metallicity relation is shown by the shaded yellow and beige regions in the right-hand panel of Figure 3.6 for the $\log M_\star < 10.5$ and entire mass range, respectively.

We turn this problem around in Figure 3.6 by considering $\zeta_w(v_{\text{vir}})$ while assuming $F_g(M_\star)$ is known [method 3]. As discussed in § 3.2.2, we consider the total gas fractions (blue, solid lines), $M_g = 0.05(\Omega_b/\Omega_m)M_{\text{halo}}$ (red, dotted), gas fractions as inferred by inverting the Schmidt law for SDSS galaxies (purple), and $M_g = 0.5M_\star$ (green). The $M_g \propto M_{\text{halo}}$ model is included because it might provide a natural explanation for the observed turnover in the mass-metallicity relation near M^* . We find that for the observed normalization of $F_g(M_\star)$, the *slope* of the gas fraction relation is largely irrelevant in setting the mass-metallicity relation morphology. That is, $z = 0$ galaxies have little enough gas that the mass-metallicity relation is shaped by how ζ_w rather than F_g scales with galaxy mass. This can be seen visually in the right-hand panel of Figure 3.6: at low masses, even the flat gas

fraction relation has approximately the same ζ_w slope as those models with steep F_g - M_\star relations.

Other metallicity indicators lead to mass-metallicity relations that are generally shallower and have a lower normalization than the Tremonti et al. mass-metallicity relation. This translates into $\zeta_w + \alpha F_g$ needing to be larger and to scale slightly less steeply with mass than seen in Figure 3.6; the best-fit ζ_w for all of the mass-metallicity relations shown in Figure 3.1 are plotted in Figure 3.7. Detailed example models for the shallow, low-normalization Denicoló et al. (2002) mass-metallicity relation are shown in Figure 3.8. Numerically, observed gas fractions require $2.3 \lesssim b \lesssim 4$; this scaling with v_{vir} is much steeper than the canonical models for the unweighted mass-loading parameter discussed in §3.2.3. Furthermore, ζ_w must be large ($\gtrsim 1$) at all relevant masses. The only way around a large ζ_w is if a significant fraction of the gas that is diluting the metals is ionized.

In the limit of small F_g and large ζ_w , one can see from equation (3.27) that $Z_g \propto \zeta_w^{-1}$ (Finlator & Davé 2008). We are using cubic fits to the mass-metallicity relation (Table 3.1, Kewley & Ellison 2008), but for the relevant mass range, the mass-metallicity relation has $0.2 \lesssim \text{slope} \lesssim 0.45$ for most of the relations plotted in Figure 3.7. Our M_\star - M_{halo} - v_{vir} relation (Figure 3.3) has $M_\star \propto v_{\text{vir}}^6$ for $\log M_\star \lesssim 10$ (and $M_\star \propto v_{\text{vir}}^{1.5}$ for $\log M_\star \gtrsim 10.6$). Thus, the metallicity Z_g is roughly proportional to $v_{\text{vir}}^{1.2}$ to $v_{\text{vir}}^{2.7}$, implying that for $\zeta_w \propto v_{\text{vir}}^{-b}$, b should be in the range 1.2 to 2.7. The large constant offset $\zeta_{w,0}$, however, means that the parameterization presented

here (see, e.g., Figure 3.5) cannot be directly interpreted in terms of the simple power-law scalings presented in §3.2.3; we also caution that $\zeta_w \neq \eta_w$, and explore the consequences of metallicity-weighting the mass-loading parameter below (§3.5). Moreover, the metal outflow efficiency ζ_w is independent of v_{vir} .

We note that a crucial step in this analysis is the assignment of virial velocities to stellar masses. For example, Finlator & Davé (2008) found that $\zeta_w \propto v_{\text{vir}}^{-1}$ was sufficient to reproduce the $z \sim 2.2$ mass-metallicity relation (which does not differ significantly in slope from the shallow relations at $z = 0$). In their simulations, however, $M_\star \propto M_{\text{halo}}$, which is a shallower relation than our $M_\star \propto M_{\text{halo}}^2$, a slope which Moster et al. (2009) finds to approximately hold to $z \sim 2$ (see their Figure 14). Because $M_{\text{halo}} \propto v_{\text{vir}}^3$, these differences have extreme consequences for the interpretation of how ζ_w scales with v_{vir} .

3.5. OUTFLOW METALLICITY AND ENTRAINMENT

Supernova-driven galaxy outflows are comprised of some combination of supernova ejecta and ambient interstellar medium entrained in the outflow. The fraction f_e of entrained gas determines wind metallicity Z_w . As mentioned in §3.3.1, the wind metallicity Z_w is usually assumed to be equal to the ISM metallicity Z_g when modeling the mass-metallicity relation, but if the outflowing supernova ejecta

entrains very little gas (which would dilute the wind metallicity) then Z_w could be much higher than Z_g .

We showed in §3.4 that models of the observed $z = 0$ mass-metallicity relation are more consistent with observations of $z = 0$ galaxy gas fractions when the metallicity-weighted mass-loading factor $\zeta_w \equiv (Z_w/Z_g)\eta_w$ scales steeply with the halo virial velocity, i.e., $\zeta_w = (v_0/v_{\text{vir}})^b + \zeta_{w,0}$ with $b \gtrsim 3$. Theoretical models for how supernovae drive galaxy-scale outflows, however, generally predict that the *unweighted* mass-loading factor $\eta_w \equiv \dot{M}_w/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}} = (\sigma_0/v_{\text{vir}})^\beta$ will scale much more shallowly, with $\beta = 1$ or 2 (§3.2.3). Reconciling these disparate scalings therefore requires that Z_w/Z_g and hence the wind fluid composition varies with galaxy mass.

For any given ζ_w that reproduces the mass-metallicity relation, additionally assuming the form of $\eta_w(v_{\text{vir}})$ uniquely constrains the wind metallicity $Z_w(M_\star)$. Figure 3.9 shows Z_w for the best-fit $\zeta_w = (78 \text{ km s}^{-1}/v_{\text{vir}})^{3.81} + 0.19$ for the T04 mass-metallicity relation (left) and $\zeta_w = (79 \text{ km s}^{-1}/v_{\text{vir}})^{3.42} + 1.25$ for the D02 mass-metallicity relation (right). The dotted, short-dashed, and long-dashed lines are for $\eta_w \propto v_{\text{vir}}^{-1}$, v_{vir}^{-2} , and v_{vir}^{-3} , models, respectively. If η_w has a similar scaling with mass as ζ_w , then $Z_w \sim Z_g$ for all masses. However, a less steep dependence of η_w on v_{vir} implies that outflow metallicities should depend less on galaxy mass than Z_g . Moreover, determining Z_w from galaxy wind observations has different systematics than determining η_w , and Z_w clearly depends sensitively on the scaling

of η_w . Figure 3.9 shows how measurements of $Z_w(M_*)$ can therefore be used to place unique constraints on η_w .

Physically, different scalings of η_w and ζ_w (and thus Z_g and Z_w) indicate that the entrainment fraction f_e (equation 3.21) varies with galaxy mass, offering a clue to the physics of galaxy outflows. If, for example, f_e increases with increasing gas mass (and thus galaxy mass), it would indicate that the wind fluid does not “punch” through a blanketing column density of gas but instead sweeps up this material and expels it from the galaxy. On the other hand, f_e decreasing with increasing galaxy mass, would indicate that the ability of supernova ejecta to collect the surrounding ISM into the wind fluid depends on the depth of the galaxy potential well. We find the former to be the case: to reconcile a steep ζ_w scaling with a shallower η_w scaling, then winds driven from deeper potential wells must be *more* efficient at entraining the ambient ISM than those driven from shallow potential wells. We also find that in order to have the normalization of η_w be consistent with the normalizations suggested in § 3.2.3 (i.e., $v_0 \sim 70 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) then the entrainment fraction must be ~ 1 , though the exact value is dependent on the value of $Z_{\text{ej,max}}$. This is particularly interesting in light of interpretations of X-ray emitting outflows in which the wind fluid is almost entirely comprised of supernova ejecta, i.e., $f_e \sim 0$ (e.g., Strickland & Heckman 2009).

3.6. SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

3.6.1. THE APPROACH: MODELING A SYSTEM OF GALAXIES

We present a new formalism in which to understand the mass-metallicity relation. We have shown (§3.3.1 and equation 3.26) that the gas phase (oxygen) metallicity Z_g of star forming galaxies is

$$Z_g = y [\zeta_w - \zeta_a + \alpha F_g + 1]^{-1}, \quad (3.35)$$

where y is the nucleosynthetic yield, ζ_a describes accreting metals, ζ_w describes the efficiency of metal expulsion, F_g describes dilution by gas, and α is a factor of order unity (see equation 3.28). In the absence of metal accretion ($\zeta_a = 0$), equation (3.35) shows that the metallicity Z_g is set by a balance of outflows (ζ_w) and gas dilution (αF_g), with the normalization set by the nucleosynthetic yield y . This equation represents a general result: each piece can vary with galaxy mass, halo mass, and redshift. To the extent that the star formation history is not bursty, i.e., \dot{M}_{SFR} varies slowly on timescales of 10 Myr (see Appendix A) then the yield y can be taken as constant with time, letting equation (3.35) describe the instantaneous state of a sequence of galaxies. Galaxies at $z = 0$ are assumed to live on a hypersurface described by their stellar masses, gas fractions, metallicities, outflow and host halo properties. By taking gas fractions and metallicities from observations, we are therefore able to uniquely solve for outflow properties in terms of galaxy masses or

metallicities (that are therefore easily comparable to observations) or in terms of the galaxy potential (and therefore easily comparable to models of the underlying wind physics). The only fitting of models to data in this approach is that of functional forms to observations of the mass-metallicity relation (e.g., Kewley & Ellison 2008) and either models or parameterizations to gas fractions as a function of stellar mass (§3.2.2). Because there is theoretical uncertainty in which metallicity indicator(s) to use when calculating the mass-metallicity relation from data, we do not favor a particular indicator when drawing our conclusions, and specifically state which constraints come from which pieces of the mass-metallicity relation.

3.6.2. RESULTING CONSTRAINTS

We consider implications for both the efficiency of star-formation driven galaxy outflows and for the content of the outflowing material. The two relevant outflow efficiencies are the efficiency with which a galaxy expels its metals, $\zeta_w \equiv (Z_w/Z_g)(\dot{M}_w/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}})$, which we parameterize as $\zeta_w = (v_0/v_{\text{vir}})^b + \zeta_{w,0}$. The second relevant efficiency is that with which a galaxy expels its gas, the unweighted mass-loading parameter $\eta_w \equiv \dot{M}_w/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$, which we similarly parameterize as $\eta_w = (\sigma_0/v_{\text{vir}})^\beta$, where β is predicted to be ~ 1 or ~ 2 with $\sigma_0 = 70\text{--}80 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (§3.2.3). The content of the wind is observed by its metallicity Z_w , which can be expressed in terms of the fraction of entrained ISM in the outflow, f_e , where $Z_w = (1 - f_e)Z_{\text{ej,max}} + f_e Z_g$ (equation 3.21 in §3.3.1). Under the assumptions

that $Z_{\text{IGM}} = 0$ and y is constant, we draw the following conclusions by requiring that viable models reproduce both the $z = 0$ mass-metallicity relation and are consistent with observed cold gas fractions.

THE NECESSITY OF OUTFLOWS

Models with no outflows ($\dot{M}_w = 0 \Rightarrow \zeta_w = 0$) are inconsistent with observed galaxy gas fractions. Specifically, in the absence of winds, the gas masses needed to dilute the produced metals are higher at all galaxy masses than the total observed cold gas masses; the magnitude of this offset is as great as ~ 0.3 dex in $F_g \equiv M_g/M_\star$, depending on the particular mass-metallicity relation being modeled.

CONSTRAINTS FROM THE NORMALIZATION OF THE MASS-METALLICITY RELATION

Equation (3.35) makes it clear that the nucleosynthetic yield sets the normalization of the mass-metallicity relation. From a modeling perspective, it is useful to consider the mass-metallicity relation normalization relative to the yield (rather than their absolute values) because the true nucleosynthetic yield is unknown to a factor of two due to uncertainties in both the IMF and in Type II supernova physics (Appendix A). Likewise, the overall normalization of the mass-metallicity relation (§3.2.1) is unknown at the ~ 0.3 dex level.⁴ The normalization of y/Z_g

⁴Though neither the nucleosynthetic yield nor the normalization of the mass-metallicity relation are well determined, the scatter in $\log Z_g$ at fixed M_\star is known to be ± 0.1 dex (Kewley & Ellison

sets the value of the constant offset $\zeta_{w,0} > 0$ (which is set by the turnover of the mass-metallicity relation, see below). The typical required velocity normalization $v_0 \sim 70\text{--}80 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is consistent with expectations.

Low normalization mass-metallicity relations require $\zeta_w > 1$ for all relevant masses; if the true nucleosynthetic yield is larger than our fiducial value ($y > 0.015$), then the efficiency with which galaxies expel metals will have to be even stronger. Thus if normal quiescently star forming galaxies are not expelling winds with $\zeta_w \gg 1$, then the data prefer a low nucleosynthetic yield and a high normalization of the mass-metallicity relation. Furthermore, because the mass-metallicity relation shifts to lower normalizations at higher redshifts, galaxies at these epochs must have either stronger winds or higher gas fractions than their $z = 0$ counterparts.

CONSTRAINTS FROM THE MORPHOLOGY OF THE MASS-METALLICITY RELATION

The morphology of the mass-metallicity relation has two main features: the slope below $\sim M^*$ and the turnover at higher masses. The slope of the mass-metallicity relation largely determines how ζ_w scales with galaxy mass, though with some degeneracies with the normalization and constant offset. For small F_g , as is the case at $z = 0$, ζ_w should scale roughly as Z_g^{-1} . The power-law scaling of ζ_w with respect to v_{vir} is typically $b \sim 3$. This need for a high and mass-dependent

2008). In light of the formalism presented here, this small scatter implies that either the scatter in both αF_g and ζ_w are small, or they are highly correlated.

wind efficiency agrees with several other works (e.g., Dekel & Woo 2003; Dutton et al. 2010b; Sawala et al. 2010; Spitoni et al. 2010).

The turnover⁵ in the mass-metallicity relation at $\log M_\star \sim 10.5$ may be an observational artifact of the metallicity indicators saturating at high Z_g (§ 3.2.1); however, if oxygen abundances do asymptote to a particular value at high masses, then this behavior can be used to place strong constraints on galaxy outflow properties. Specifically, both the normalization of the mass-metallicity relation relative to the yield and the effects of v_{vir} increasing sharply above $M^* \sim 10^{11} M_\odot$ (Figure 3.3) must be then taken into consideration; moreover, the interplay between these effects can place stronger constraints on viable models than just considerations of the mass-metallicity relation below $10^{10.5} M_\odot$. Morphologically, a turnover in the mass-metallicity relation means that either αF_g or ζ_w cannot be approximated as a power-law. Because cold gas fractions are observed to roughly follow a power-law with respect to M_\star , then ζ_w needs a constant offset $\zeta_{w,0} \sim 0.2\text{--}1.5$, depending on which indicator is used to calculate the mass-metallicity relation. We note that, in several cases, if $M_g \propto (\Omega_b/\Omega_m)M_{\text{halo}}$, then ζ_w can be described as a power-law; physically, this would imply that galaxies above M^* have large reservoirs of ionized gas that are able to efficiently transfer mass with colder, star-forming gas.

⁵The turn-“up” at low masses for the Z94 mass-metallicity relation is unphysical and due to the cubic fit to the data.

If ζ_w and η_w scale differently with galaxy mass, then the fraction of entrained ISM in the wind fluid will vary with galaxy mass. Observationally this will be seen as Z_w/Z_g varying with mass. As the morphology of the mass-metallicity relation constrains the scaling of ζ_w with mass, the scaling of Z_w and thus η_w with mass therefore depends on the slope of the mass-metallicity relation. For example (see Figure 3.9), for a fixed η_w , a steep mass-metallicity relation will lead to a shallower Z_w - M_* relation than a shallower mass-metallicity relation will. However, since current uncertainties in the slope of the mass-metallicity relation are smaller than uncertainties in how (or if) η_w scales with mass, measurements of Z_w across a large range in galaxy mass, especially above M^* , will be particularly useful for constraining how η_w (and ζ_w) scale.

3.6.3. THE ROLE OF METAL-(RE)ACCRETION

At $z = 0$, the assumption that accreting material has a negligible metal content (i.e., that $Z_{\text{IGM}} = 0$ and therefore $\zeta_a = 0$) may not be entirely safe. The IGM is enriched as early as $z > 3$ (Songaila & Cowie 1996; Ellison et al. 2000; Schaye et al. 2003), and if this material is re-accreted onto galaxies at later epochs it could have a significant effect on the shape and normalization of the $z = 0$ mass-metallicity relation. The re-accretion of winds (i.e., gas with $Z_{\text{IGM}} > 0$) is a significant component of accreted gas in cosmological SPH simulations (Oppenheimer et al. 2009). Though the total accretion rate scales with halo mass ($\dot{M}_{\text{acc}} \propto M_{\text{halo}} \propto v_{\text{vir}}^3$,

see Appendix B), the contribution of accreted metals to the mass-metallicity relation may not scale so steeply (Finlator & Davé 2008). Moreover, an extra source of metals ζ_a will imply that the *amplitude* of outflows ζ_w will need to be even higher than the ones presented here. However, the reaccretion of wind material seen in SPH simulations may be sensitive to numerical issues in the wind implementation; more detailed investigations are needed to verify the importance of wind-recycling. The metal budget available for re-accretion depends on both the amount of metals expelled at higher redshifts and the recycling timescale. We will address the metal content of winds at $z > 0$ as implied by the evolution of the mass-metallicity relation in a later paper.

Fig. 3.1.— Mass-metallicity relations listed in Table 3.1 (Kewley & Ellison 2008, and equation 3.1). The scatter about any given one of these curves is 0.1–0.15 dex, which is much less than the differences in normalization; that is, the normalization differences are systematic. The mass-metallicity relations in black (T04, solid; D02, dashed) are modeled in detail §§3.4 and 3.5.

Fig. 3.2.— Left: Gas fractions F_g as a function of M_\star . Right: Gas masses M_g as a function of M_\star . The open black diamonds are H I gas fractions and masses from McGaugh (2005); the crosses are the same from West et al. (2009, 2010). The filled circles are H I + H₂ gas fractions and masses (Leroy et al. 2008), who find that there is very little H₂ below $\log M_\star \sim 9.5$, which is consistent with the comparison to the H I samples. The red dotted line shows the maximum baryonic mass $(\Omega_b/\Omega_m)M_{\text{halo}}$, while the green “flat” line shows $M_g = 0.5M_\star$. The blue “total” line is a fit to these data with the normalization increased by 0.2 dex; the orange squares are the mean $\log F_g$ of these same data in bins of $\Delta \log M_\star = 0.4$ dex with the inner and outer errorbars denoting the uncertainty in and dispersion about the mean, respectively. Gas fractions and masses derived from SDSS data and inverting the K-S law, assuming a radius of $1.1R_{90,z}$ (solid line) and the fiber radius (dashed line); in the right panel, the shaded region corresponds to the 1- and 2- σ dispersions in moving bins of $\log M_\star$.

Fig. 3.3.— Halo mass, M_{halo} , and virial velocity, v_{vir} , as a function of stellar mass, M_* , at $z = 0$ (Moster et al. 2009). See §3.3.2 for more details.

Fig. 3.4.— Required gas fractions to reproduce the T04 mass-metallicity relation with varying power-law slopes of $\zeta_w(v_{\text{vir}})$: $\zeta_w = 0$ (orange, solid), $[50 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}}$ (pink, long dashed), $([85 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}})^2$ (blue, short dashed), $([85 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}})^3$ (green, dotted); these normalizations are chosen to give gas fractions that are as compatible with the observations as possible. Note that all models fit data in (a) and (b) by construction: panel (a) shows the T04 mass-metallicity relation (black, solid) and models (colored lines) while panel (b) shows $\log[\zeta_w + \alpha F_g]$ as a function of stellar mass for the four models (colored lines) and $\log[y/Z_g - 1]$ for the T04 mass-metallicity relation in black. Panel (c) shows the model $\log F_g$ as a function of stellar mass (colored lines) and the observed gas fractions as grey triangles; these are the same observations plotted in Figure 3.2 (McGaugh 2005; Leroy et al. 2008; West et al. 2009, 2010). The model $\log \zeta_w$ as a function of virial velocity are plotted in panel (d) (the $\zeta_w = 0$ case is unplotsed because of the logarithmic ζ_w axis).

Fig. 3.5.— $\Delta\chi^2$ contours for the T04 mass-metallicity relation with $\zeta_w = (v_0/v_{\text{vir}})^{-b} + \zeta_{w,0}$. The black “X” marks the parameters with the lowest χ^2 ; the yellow, green, cyan, and grey regions denote solutions with $\Delta\chi^2 \leq 1\text{-}\sigma$, $1\text{-}\sigma < \Delta\chi^2 \leq 2\text{-}\sigma$, $2\text{-}\sigma < \Delta\chi^2 \leq 3$, and $\Delta\chi^2 > 3\text{-}\sigma$, respectively, using the $\Delta\chi^2$ -to- σ conversion from Press et al. (1992). The white regions correspond to unphysical ($M_g \leq 0$) models.

ID	a	b	c	d
T04	-0.759210	1.30177	0.003261	-0.00364112
Z94	73.0539	-20.9053	2.23299	-0.0783089
KK04	28.1404	-7.02595	0.812620	-0.0301508
KD02	28.4613	-7.32158	0.855119	-0.0318315
M91	46.1480	-12.3801	1.33589	-0.0471074
D02	-8.91951	4.18231	-0.323383	0.00818179
PP04O3N2	32.5769	-8.61049	0.981780	-0.0359763
PP04N2	24.1879	-5.69253	0.648668	-0.0235065

Note. — $\log Z_g = a + b \log M_\star + c(\log M_\star)^2 + d(\log M_\star)^3$, sorted by decreasing $\max(Z_g)$. The two fits we consider in the main text (T04 and D02) are in bold. See text for abbreviations.

Table 3.1. Kewley & Ellison (2008) fits to the mass-metallicity relation

Fig. 3.6.— Required ζ_w to reproduce the T04 mass-metallicity relation with varying gas fraction relations: total (blue, solid), $M_g = 0.5M_*$ (green, dashed), inverting the K-S law from SDSS data (purple, solid), and $M_g = 0.05(\Omega_b/\Omega_m)M_{\text{halo}}$ (red, dotted); see § 3.2.2 for the motivations behind these relations. *Left*: Gas fractions as a function of stellar mass. The grey triangles in are the gas fractions plotted in Figure 3.2 (McGaugh 2005; Leroy et al. 2008; West et al. 2009, 2010) and the orange squares are the binned data (§ 3.2.2). *Right*: $\log \zeta_w$ as a function of virial velocity corresponding to the gas fractions in the left panel. The orange lines are the best-fitting models based on the binned data (see Figure 3.5); the beige and yellow shaded regions in the right-hand panel show the 1- σ range in ζ_w for the entire mass range and $\log M_* \leq 10.5$, respectively.

Fig. 3.7.— *Left:* The mass-metallicity relation as derived from different metallicity indicators (§3.2.1, Kewley & Ellison 2008), relative to the nucleosynthetic yield $y = 0.015$. *Right:* The corresponding best fitting $\zeta_w = (v_0/v_{\text{vir}})^b + \zeta_{w,0}$ under the requirement that the models' gas fractions are consistent with observations. The ζ_w parameters are listed in Table 3.4.

Fig. 3.8.— Same as Figures 3.4 and 3.6, but for the Denicoló et al. (2002) mass-metallicity relation. The normalizations for $\zeta_w \propto v_{\text{vir}}^{-b}$ in the middle two panels are chosen to give gas fractions that are as compatible with the observations as possible and are: $[185 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}}$ (pink, long dashed), $([100 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}})^2$ (blue, short dashed), $([90 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}})^3$ (green, dotted).

Fig. 3.9.— Wind metallicities Z_w for the best-fit ζ_w T04 (left) and D02 (right) mass-metallicity relations (see Figures 3.6 and 3.8). The solid line corresponds to $\zeta_w = \eta_w$ and therefore $Z_w = Z_g$ and $f_e = 1$; different scalings for $\eta_w = (\sigma_0/v_{\text{vir}})^\beta$ are shown as the dotted ($\beta = 1$), short-dashed ($\beta = 2$), and long-dashed ($\beta = 3$) lines.

$\langle \log M_\star \rangle$	$\langle \log F_g \rangle$	$\sigma_{\log F_g}$
8.3298	0.5153	0.07867
8.7265	0.3084	0.06500
9.0892	0.2062	0.06359
9.5141	-0.07142	0.06220
9.8941	-0.3230	0.04817
10.298	-0.5548	0.06666
10.664	-0.8389	0.06212
11.053	-0.8303	0.06566

Note. — Cold gas fractions $\log F_g = \log(M_g/M_\star)$ in bins of $\Delta \log M_\star = 0.4$ dex and the uncertainty in the mean $\sigma_{\log F_g}$ for the McGaugh (2005), Leroy et al. (2008), and Garcia-Appadoo et al. (2009) data sets.

Table 3.2. Cold gas fractions $\log F_g = \log(M_g/M_\star)$

Name	$\log M_{\star,0}$	K_f	γ
Total	9.6	316228	0.57
SDSS	6.0	15.85	0.20
Fiber	2.7	2.24	0.13
Flat	—	0.50	0.00

Note. — Gas fraction relation parameters, $F_g = M_g/M_{\star} = K_f M_{\star}^{-\gamma}$.

Table 3.3. Gas fraction relation parameters

ID	v_0	b	$\zeta_{w,0}$
T04	78.0	3.81	0.19
Z94	63.5	3.20	0.23
KK04	55.5	3.04	0.32
KD02	71.0	3.18	0.39
M91	73.0	2.47	0.77
D02	79.0	3.42	1.25
PP04O3N2	90.0	3.15	1.50
PP04N2	111.8	2.31	1.35

Note. — Best-fit parameters for $\zeta_w = (v_0/v_{\text{vir}})^b + \zeta_{w,0}$ the fits to the mass-metallicity relation calculated by Kewley & Ellison (2008) and listed in Table 3.1 and the binned gas fractions plotted in Figure 3.2. These ζ_w are plotted next to the corresponding $Z_g(M_*)$ in Figure 3.7.

Table 3.4. Best-fit ζ_w parameters

CHAPTER 4

PRESSURE SUPPORT VS. THERMAL BROADENING IN THE LYMAN- α FOREST

4.1. INTRODUCTION

The Lyman- α forest, caused by Ly α absorption of neutral hydrogen atoms along the line of sight to some distant source (usually a quasar), was originally described in terms of discrete intervening gas “clouds” (Lynds 1971; Sargent et al. 1980), analogous to clouds in the Galactic interstellar medium. In this picture, the velocity widths of the observed absorption structures were primarily a consequence of thermal motions of the absorbing atoms. Most of the information we have on the nature of the intergalactic medium (IGM) is from sightlines piercing physically distinct regions of the IGM. Absorption features have finite widths, but from individual sightlines it is difficult to separate the contribution of bulk velocities (Hubble flow and peculiar velocities) from those of thermal broadening. Close quasar pairs can break this degeneracy by probing the transverse structure of the IGM. In the mid-1990s, several studies of quasar groups and lensed quasars definitively showed that the absorbing structures are coherent over hundreds of kpc (Bechtold et al. 1994; Dinshaw et al.

1994; Fang et al. 1996; Charlton et al. 1997; Crofts & Fang 1998). These observations provided critical support for the physical picture of the Ly α forest then emerging from theoretical considerations. Three-dimensional hydrodynamic simulations of cold dark matter (CDM) cosmological models achieved remarkable success in reproducing the observed properties of the Ly α forest (Cen et al. 1994; Zhang et al. 1995; Hernquist et al. 1996; Miralda-Escudé et al. 1996; Theuns et al. 1998). In these simulations, most of the absorbing gas is at low density ($\rho/\bar{\rho} \sim 0.1\text{--}10$) and naturally described as a continuously fluctuating medium rather than a series of discrete structures (Hernquist et al. 1996; Bi & Davidsen 1997; Rauch et al. 1997; Croft et al. 1997, 1998). The velocity width of individual features is set largely by the Hubble flow across them, reflecting the physical extent of the absorbing gas along the line of sight (Hernquist et al. 1996; Weinberg et al. 1997a). The temperature of the IGM, therefore, affects the structure of the Ly α forest in two ways: by smoothing absorption along the line of sight through the thermal motions of atoms, and by smoothing the physical distribution of the gas in three dimensions through pressure support. In this study, we use two smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) simulations with different photoionization heating rates—and thus different IGM temperatures and amounts of gas pressure support—to disentangle the relative effects of pressure support and thermal broadening in the Ly α forest.

Both hydrodynamical simulations (Katz et al. 1996; Miralda-Escudé et al. 1996; Theuns et al. 1998) and analytic arguments (Hui & Gnedin 1997) suggest

that low-density intergalactic gas should have a power-law temperature-density relation, i.e., $T = T_0(1 + \delta)^\alpha$, where $1 + \delta \equiv \rho/\bar{\rho}$ is the local gas overdensity. Reasonable assumptions for heating and cooling rates yield $T_0 \sim 10^4$ K and $\alpha \sim 0.6$ (Hui & Gnedin 1997; Theuns et al. 1998). Observations, however, imply that the normalization T_0 could be nearly twice as high, and the slope could be much shallower or even inverted (Schaye et al. 1999; Ricotti et al. 2000; McDonald et al. 2001; Bolton et al. 2008). Regardless of the parameter values, because the optical depth to Ly α absorption is related to both the temperature and the density by a power law, the existence of the temperature-density relation (also called the “equation of state”) implies a tight relation between the observed Ly α absorption and the IGM gas density. Since the universe has ~ 5 times as much mass in dark matter as in baryons, we can expect in general for intergalactic gas to trace the underlying dark matter on scales above the gas Jeans length (Schaye 2001). The Ly α forest therefore provides a powerful tool for tracing the dark matter power spectrum in the quasi-linear regime—modulo the effects of peculiar velocities, thermal broadening, and gas pressure (Croft et al. 1998, 1999, 2002; McDonald et al. 2000, 2006; Viel et al. 2004; Viel & Haehnelt 2006).

Pressure should be important on scales at or below the Jeans length,

$$\lambda_J = c_s \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{G\rho}} = \sigma_{\text{th}} \sqrt{\frac{5\pi}{3G\rho}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where $c_s = \sqrt{[5kT]/[3m]} = \sigma_{\text{th}}\sqrt{5/3}$ is the speed of sound in an ideal gas expressed as a multiple of the 1-D thermal velocity σ_{th} (Miralda-Escudé et al. 1996; Schaye 2001; Desjacques & Nusser 2005). Here m is the average mass of the gas particle; in an ionized primordial mixture of hydrogen and helium, $m = 0.59m_p$, where m_p is the proton mass. The density ρ is the density of the gravitating medium, which is dominated by dark matter, so we take $\rho = \Omega_{m,0}\rho_{c,0}(1+z)^3(1+\delta)$. In comoving coordinates,

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_{J,\text{comv}} &= (1+z)\sigma_{\text{th}}H_0^{-1}\sqrt{\frac{5\pi}{3}}\left[\frac{3}{8\pi}\Omega_{m,0}(1+z)^3(1+\delta)\right]^{-1/2} \\ &= 782 h^{-1} \text{kpc} \times \left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{th}}}{11.8 \text{ km s}^{-1}}\right) \left[\left(\frac{\Omega_{m,0}(1+\delta)}{0.25 \times (1+0)}\right) \left(\frac{1+z}{1+3}\right)\right]^{-1/2},\end{aligned}\quad (4.2)$$

where we have normalized the thermal broadening velocity σ_{th} to correspond to a fiducial temperature of 10^4 K. By defining a “Jeans velocity” as $v_J \equiv H\lambda_J$ we can find the relative importance of the Jeans scale and σ_{th} ,

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{v_J}{\sigma_{\text{th}}} &= \frac{2\pi\sqrt{10}}{3}(1+\delta)^{-1/2}\left[\frac{\Omega_{m,0}(1+z)^3 + \Omega_\Lambda}{\Omega_{m,0}(1+z)^3}\right]^{1/2} \\ &\approx 6.62(1+\delta)^{-1/2},\end{aligned}\quad (4.3)$$

which is essentially redshift-independent for the redshifts relevant to the Ly α forest. The Jeans length of equation (4.1) divides stable from unstable modes in a static, homogeneous, self-gravitating medium. The IGM is expanding, inhomogeneous, non-self-gravitating (because dark matter dominates), and evolving in density and temperature on the same timescale that fluctuations grow. Even for linear

perturbations in a baryonic universe, the “filtering scale” below which fluctuations growth is suppressed depends on the thermal history of the gas rather than the instantaneous temperature-density relation (Gnedin & Hui 1998). We therefore expect equation (4.1) to describe the scale of gas pressure support only at an order-of-magnitude level. Equation (4.3) shows that Jeans velocities and thermal velocities should be comparable at the overdensities of typical Ly α forest features, but the calculation is not definitive enough to show whether one will dominate in practice. Our simulations indicate that the “effective” Jeans length in the Ly α forest is smaller than that given in Equation (4.2) by a factor of a few, probably owing to a combination of geometric factors, the universe expanding on the same timescale as the gas evolves, and the contribution of dark matter to the gravitational forces.

Hence, to predict the statistical properties of the Ly α forest in a given cosmological model, one must calculate the predicted gas distribution. The most reliable way to do this uses full N -body plus hydrodynamic simulations, which include the gravity of dark matter and gas and the additional effects of pressure, adiabatic heating and cooling, heating by photoionization and shocks, and radiative cooling. However, large volume hydrodynamic simulations with the necessary resolution are computationally intensive. Weinberg et al. (1997a) and Croft et al. (1998) show that one can achieve reasonable accuracy in the Ly α forest regime from pure dark matter simulations, applying the temperature-density relation to the evolved dark matter distribution to compute spectra. Indeed, the log-normal model

(Bi & Davidsen 1997), in which the dark matter distribution is computed from the linear density field by an exponential transformation (Coles & Jones 1991), provides a qualitatively accurate physical model of the Ly α forest, sufficient for creating artificial spectra with reasonable statistical properties.

A fast way to include the effects of gas pressure in an approximate way is the hydrodynamic particle-mesh (HPM) method (Gnedin & Hui 1998; Ricotti et al. 2000; Meiksin & White 2001). HPM assumes that all the gas follows the power-law IGM equation of state, and it uses a modification of the standard (fast) particle-mesh N -body method to compute the sum of gravitational forces and pressure gradient forces given this equation of state. In a detailed comparison of fully hydrodynamic SPH simulations and the approximated HPM simulations, both evolved using GADGET-2, Viel et al. (2004) found that while the HPM approach does converge to the SPH results, for some Ly α forest properties, such as the flux probability distribution or small-scale power spectrum, it can differ from the SPH calculation by as much as 50% at $z \sim 2$. A simpler alternative to HPM is to use a pure N -body simulation but smooth the evolved dark matter distribution on the Jeans scale before extracting Ly α forest spectra (Zaldarriaga et al. 2001; Desjacques & Nusser 2005). Because the Jeans smoothing is three-dimensional, it is not degenerate with line-of-sight thermal broadening. Zaldarriaga et al. (2001) found that, even though the thermal broadening dominates the pressure correction, the value of the Jeans length becomes a large source of uncertainty in cosmological inferences from the Ly α

forest if one tries to estimate it from the data rather than predict it from theory. Because the Jeans length is expected to vary with the gas temperature and density, a Zel'dovich-like scheme can be used when smoothing the dark matter distribution in order to model these effects (Viel et al. 2002). Though we do not carry out a comprehensive comparison of these methods here, we do investigate the impact of pressure in detail, as well as compare full SPH simulations to results derived from the dark matter distribution alone.

The primary purpose of this Chapter is to disentangle the roles of pressure support and thermal broadening in the Ly α forest by studying two SPH simulations with different thermal histories and temperature-density relations. In addition to examining the physics of the Ly α forest, this study is motivated by observational evidence (discussed in §4.3.1) that the temperature of the IGM at $z \sim 2-4$ is higher than expected from simple photoionization models by a factor of 1.5–2. This evidence comes from analyses of data along single lines of sight. Because the higher pressure associated with hotter gas would smooth the IGM in three dimensions, using closely paired lines of sight to probe this coherence scale has been proposed as an alternative route for inferring the temperature-density relation (J. Hennawi, private communication, 2007). However, before we can understand the relative roles of temperature and pressure on the transverse structure of the Lyman- α forest, we must first understand their longitudinal effects along independent sightlines. While we find that thermal broadening dominates pressure support in setting the

level of longitudinal structure in the Ly α forest, we show that the gas Jeans length dominates the level of coherence transverse to the line of sight. Intuitively, this is because thermal broadening affects the observed IGM by smoothing the Ly α forest in one-dimension (namely, along the line of sight), while pressure support smooths the physical gas distribution in all three dimensions.

For $\Omega_m = 0.25$ and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.75$, the relation between angular separation $\Delta\theta$ and comoving transverse separation R at $z = 2\text{--}4$ is approximately

$$\Delta\theta \approx 4.4'' \left(\frac{1+z}{4} \right)^{0.6} \times \left(\frac{R}{100h^{-1} \text{ kpc}} \right). \quad (4.4)$$

Lines of sight with angular separations of 3–10'' are needed to probe the Jeans scale of the IGM. While this scale is just larger than the cutoff for the typical Einstein radius of galaxy lenses (Schneider, Kochanek, & Wambsganss 2006), new searches for binary quasars are revealing samples of a few to dozens with $\Delta\theta \lesssim 10''$ (Hennawi et al. 2006, 2009).

This Chapter is organized as follows. In §4.2, we describe the SPH simulations we have evolved to investigate these effects. In §4.3, we describe the physics of the Ly α forest in these simulations and examine the impact of the thermal history on observable spectra; this section also serves to review the physical understanding of the high-redshift Ly α forest that has emerged from simulations and associated analytic work since the mid-1990s. We then study these effects on several typical

statistical measures for learning about the IGM from the Ly α forest in §4.4, with our conclusions in §4.5. All distances are given in comoving coordinates unless otherwise stated.

4.2. SIMULATIONS

We analyze two SPH simulations with identical initial conditions, one with a fiducial photoionization heating rate and one with a heating rate from photoionization that is four times higher than the fiducial; hereafter, we refer to these simulations as the “fiducial” and “H4” simulations, respectively. In the terminology of Katz et al. (1996), we compute the photoionization rates Γ and photoionization heating rates ϵ for the fiducial simulation assuming the Haardt & Madau (2001) quasar + galaxy photoionizing background, and for the H4 simulation we increase ϵ_{HI} , ϵ_{HeI} , and ϵ_{HeII} by a factor of four. In principle, these heating rates could arise from a much harder UV background spectrum that yields more residual energy per photo-electron. However, we do not propose any specific model for these heating rates—they are a computationally simple way to obtain IGM temperatures that are higher than those in the fiducial model and closer to those estimated from observations (see §4.3.1 for further discussion).

We evolve these SPH simulations using the parallel GADGET-2 code (Springel 2005) to trace the evolution of 288^3 dark matter and 288^3 gas

particles in a $12.5 h^{-1}$ Mpc comoving cubic volume from $z = 15$ to $z = 2$. We also evolved another simulation using the fiducial heating rates and the same initial conditions but only 2×144^3 particles to serve as a test for resolution convergence. We adopt a standard Λ CDM cosmological model with the parameters $(\Omega_M, \Omega_\Lambda, \Omega_b, h, \sigma_8, n_s) = (0.25, 0.75, 0.044, 0.7, 0.8, 0.95)$, all of which are in good agreement with the *Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe* (WMAP) five-year results (Hinshaw et al. 2009); our choice of $\sigma_8 = 0.8$, however, is somewhat lower than what is typically considered for Ly α studies. These parameters give a mass per SPH particle of $1.426 \times 10^6 M_\odot$, which is much less than the typical Jeans mass of $M_J \equiv \rho \lambda_J^3 \sim 7 \times 10^9 M_\odot$. The spline gravitational force softening has an equivalent Plummer length of $0.875 h^{-1}$ kpc comoving ($\sim 1/50$ of the initial particle grid spacing). The SPH smoothing lengths are chosen to enclose 33 ± 2 neighbors within the smoothing kernel. The simulation incorporates standard heating and atomic cooling processes and the standard GADGET-2 treatment of star formation and metal enrichment. These simulations do not incorporate galactic winds, but these should have very little effect on the Ly α forest (Kollmeier et al. 2006; Bertone & White 2006; Marble et al. 2008b).

We extract spectra from the SPH gas distribution using TIPSYS¹, as described by Hernquist et al. (1996). Following common practice, we rescale the intensity of the UV background so that the mean flux decrement of the extracted spectra

¹University of Washington version

matches observations (Table 4.1), as the mean decrement itself is much better known than the background intensity (see discussions by, e.g., Croft et al. 2002; Marble et al. 2008b). Our extracted spectra have 1250 pixels across the $12.5h^{-1}$ Mpc volume, making the pixel size $\approx 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, which is well below the smoothing scale imposed by thermal broadening.

4.3. PHYSICS OF THE LYMAN- α FOREST

4.3.1. THE TEMPERATURE-DENSITY RELATION

In the absence of shock heating, the evolution of the temperature of the IGM is described by

$$\frac{dT}{dz} = \frac{2T}{1+z} + \left[\frac{2T}{3(1+\delta)} \right] \frac{d\delta}{dz} - \left[\frac{T}{m} \right] \frac{dm}{dz} + \frac{2}{3k_B n_b} \frac{dQ}{dz}, \quad (4.5)$$

as shown in detail by Hui & Gnedin (1997). Here, $d\delta/dz$ and $H(z)$ depend on the cosmology, the overdensity $1 + \delta \equiv (\rho_{\text{gas}}/\bar{\rho}_b)$, m is the mean particle mass, and dQ/dz is the net power per unit volume owing to the ambient radiation field. The first two terms in equation (4.5) describe heating and cooling owing to adiabatic processes. After reionization, the change in temperature owing to the change in the ionization fraction (the third term in equation [4.5]) is effectively zero at all redshifts and relevant densities.

Hydrogen reionization produces one energetic photoelectron per hydrogen atom, and it is expected to heat the IGM to a temperature $T \sim 2\text{--}5 \times 10^4$ K, depending on the spectral shape of the ionizing sources and radiative transfer effects (Miralda-Escudé & Rees 1994). Thereafter, adiabatic cooling reduces the overall temperature, but denser regions remain hotter because they have higher neutral fractions and thus higher photoionization heating rates. At a given redshift, the simulated temperature-density (T - ρ) relation of the photoionized medium can be well approximated by a powerlaw,

$$T(z) = T_0(z)(1 + \delta)^{\alpha(z)}. \quad (4.6)$$

The slope $\alpha(z)$ approaches 0.6 well after reionization. Evolution with the Haardt & Madau (2001) UV background spectrum and $\Omega_b h^2 \approx 0.022$ yields $T_0 \approx 10^4$ K at $z = 2\text{--}4$, for reionization at $z \gtrsim 7$ (e.g., Hui & Gnedin 1997; Theuns et al. 1998; Davé et al. 1999; Table 4.1). Figure 4.1 shows the distribution of SPH particles for our fiducial simulation in the temperature-overdensity plane at $z = 3$; Figure 4.2 shows the same at $z = 2.4$. At low overdensities ($1 + \delta \lesssim 10$), most of the gas falls along a tight locus, as expected from the above discussion. At higher densities ($1 + \delta \gtrsim 100$), the gas has begun to cool to form galaxies. The higher temperature gas has been shock heated. (The apparent increase in temperature at $1 + \delta \sim 10^4$ owes to the way GADGET-2 treats the multiphase interstellar medium.) For many of our subsequent analyses, we will isolate physical effects by imposing one of the three T - ρ relations,

denoted by dashed lines in Figures 4.1 and 4.2. Specifically, we assign each gas (or dark matter) particle the temperature implied by its overdensity and a given T - ρ relation before extracting spectra. The yellow line in Figure 4.1 is an eyeball fit to the T - ρ relation in the fiducial simulation, while the pink line is the corresponding fit to the H4 relation; the H4 T - ρ normalization is ~ 2.3 times higher than the fiducial normalization. In both of these cases we set gas with $1 + \delta > 10$ to a “shocked” temperature of $T = 5 \times 10^5$ K, so that this high density gas will be entirely ionized and thus not contribute to the Ly α forest. The mass- and volume-fraction of gas in these high density regions is relatively tiny; for all of the statistics presented here, the fiducial and H4 gas distributions using the imposed fiducial and H4 T - ρ relations, respectively, yield nearly identical results to those obtained using the actual temperatures calculated by GADGET-2. Parameters for these fits are listed in Table 4.1. For some comparisons, we impose a flat T - ρ relation, with all particles set to $T = 2 \times 10^4$ K, as shown by the blue dashed line.

Although most Ly α forest features are broadened by Hubble flow, the narrowest features arise at velocity caustics and have widths set by thermal broadening. Analyses of observed line width distributions imply $T_0 \approx 1.5\text{--}2 \times 10^4$ K at $2 \leq z \leq 4$ (Gnedin & Hui 1998; Ricotti et al. 2000; Schaye et al. 2000; McDonald et al. 2001; we adopt McDonald et al.’s constraints in Table 4.1 and Figure 4.3). This is significantly hotter than the value $T_0 \approx 10^4$ K expected for a Haardt & Madau (2001) ionizing background. Theuns et al. (2000) and Zaldarriaga et al. (2001) find a similar result

by fitting the small-scale cutoff of the one-dimensional flux power spectrum. More recently, Bolton et al. (2008) have fit the flux probability distribution function (PDF) in high-resolution spectra inferring a similar, high T_0 and a shallow, possibly inverted ($\alpha < 0$) slope. Lidz et al. (2009) find $T_0 \approx 2 \times 10^4$ K over the redshift range $z = 2-4$, using a wavelet analysis of 40 high-resolution spectra. In all cases, the observations are interpreted by comparing them to a suite of cosmological simulations, which incorporate many parameters in addition to the T - ρ relation itself.

According to equation (4.5), there are two basic ways to increase the gas temperature: either have hotter “initial conditions,” or a higher heating rate dQ/dz . Even with the highest plausible reionization temperatures, it is difficult to reproduce the inferred T_0 at $z = 3$, given the observational evidence that $z_{\text{reion}} \geq 7$ (Fan et al. 2006; Hinshaw et al. 2009; see also Hui & Haiman 2003). Energy injection from He II reionization over an extended period of time could also keep the IGM hot down to $z \sim 3$ (Bolton et al. 2008; Furlanetto & Oh 2008), though even this mechanism appears unable to produce an inverted T - ρ relation (McQuinn et al. 2009). A harder photoionizing spectrum produces more energy input per photoelectron and thus a higher IGM temperature.² It is this solution that we adopt for our H4 simulation, though the heating rates we adopt correspond to an implausibly hard spectrum. The structure of the Ly α forest should depend on the T - ρ relation but be fairly

²Note that in photoionization equilibrium, higher intensity background radiation—with the same spectrum—affects only the photoionization and recombination rates, *not* the electron temperature.

insensitive to the detailed mechanism that produces it, so we expect our conclusions about the impact of pressure support to apply to a broad range of such mechanisms. However, the tension between the T - ρ relations predicted from theory and those inferred from observations remain puzzling, and it is not clear whether the resolution lies in modest changes (e.g., temperatures at the low end of observational estimates and a spectrum that is harder than conventionally assumed) or a physical process that has not yet been identified. Precisely because of this tension, it is important to understand the physics and observational consequences of pressure support in the Ly α forest.

In Figure 4.3, the dashed lines show the approximate T - ρ relationships found in our two SPH simulations; the $z = 3$ dashed lines are the same as the low-density yellow and pink lines in Figure 4.1. The temperature-density parameters for the observations and our simulations at each redshift are given in Table 4.1. The fiducial simulation clearly disagrees with the observations at $z = 3$ and 2.4, while the H4 simulation is in closer agreement but somewhat too hot, i.e., the two simulations bracket the central observation estimates. The points in Figure 4.3 are numerical integrations of equation (4.5), where we approximate the overdensity evolution using a modified Zel’dovich approximation (Reisenegger & Miralda-Escude 1995). H I reionization is modeled by initializing the temperature at a “reionization temperature” T_r for all overdensities at a reionization redshift $z_{\text{reion}} = 9.45$;

the temperature-density relation is fairly independent of T_r by $z = 4$, assuming reionization occurs at $z \gtrsim 6$.

4.3.2. THE FLUCTUATING GUNN-PETERSON APPROXIMATION

The H I optical depth τ_{HI} is proportional to the neutral hydrogen density, with

$$\tau_{\text{HI}} = \frac{\pi e^2}{m_e c} f \lambda_0 H^{-1}(z) n_{\text{HI}}, \quad (4.7)$$

where f_λ is the oscillator strength of the Ly α transition and λ_0 is the center of the Ly α transition, 1216Å (Gunn & Peterson 1965; Miralda-Escude 1993). In the limit of high ionization fraction, the neutral hydrogen density,

$$n_{\text{HI}} = \left(\frac{\alpha_{\text{HII}}}{\Gamma_{\text{UV}}} \right) n_e n_{\text{H}}, \quad (4.8)$$

is proportional to the gas density squared; Γ_{UV} is the photoionization rate owing to the ambient UV background. At the relevant temperatures ($T \ll 10^6$), the recombination coefficient α_{HII} is proportional to $T^{-0.7}$ (Katz et al. 1996). Following Rauch et al. (1997) and Croft et al. (1998), we can combine equations (4.7) and (4.8) with a power-law T - ρ relation to obtain the optical depth

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{\text{HI}} = & 1.54 \times \left(\frac{T_0}{10^4 \text{K}} \right)^{-0.7} \left(\frac{10^{-12} \text{s}^{-1}}{\Gamma_{\text{UV}}} \right) \left(\frac{1+z}{1+3} \right)^6 \left(\frac{0.7}{h} \right) \\ & \times \left(\frac{\Omega_{b,0} h^2}{0.02156} \right)^2 \left[\frac{4.0927}{H(z)/H_0} \right] (1+\delta)^{2-0.7\alpha} \left[1 + \frac{1}{H(z)} \frac{dV_{\text{los}}}{dx} \right]^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

The last factor represents the impact of line-of-sight peculiar velocity gradients dV_{los}/dx , which change the density of atoms in frequency space relative to real space.

Independently of the Ly α forest, the photoionization rate Γ_{UV} is difficult to constrain; the other quantities entering the normalization pre-factor of equation (4.9) are also uncertain. We therefore follow standard practice (e.g., Miralda-Escudé et al. 1996; Marble et al. 2008b) and choose Γ_{UV} for each model so that it reproduces the observed mean flux decrement $\langle D \rangle \equiv \langle 1 - F \rangle = \langle 1 - \exp(-\tau_{\text{HI}}) \rangle$ at the redshift under investigation. Specifically, we adopt $\langle D \rangle$ values from McDonald et al. (2000), which are listed in Table 4.1; at the overlapping redshifts ($z = 2.4, 3$) these $\langle D \rangle$ are consistent with the more recent measurements of Kim et al. (2007). (For reference, we also list the projected angular separation at $100 h^{-1}$ kpc comoving at each redshift in Table 4.1.) If Γ_{UV} were perfectly known, then $\langle D \rangle$ could itself be used as a diagnostic of the IGM temperature T_0 , but in practice it is not well enough known. Hence, we rely on structure in the Ly α forest for IGM diagnostics and cosmological tests.

Our results below rely on our full hydrodynamical simulations, but equation (4.9) is useful to understand our results, and it can be a useful basis for simpler analytic or numerical treatments. It is often referred to as the “fluctuating Gunn-Peterson approximation” (FGPA; Weinberg et al. 1997a; Croft et al. 1998) because it describes Ly α absorption as a continuous phenomenon analogous to the Gunn-Peterson (1965) effect, but arising in a fluctuating medium. As written, it ignores thermal broadening

(a temperature- and therefore density-dependent convolution) and shock heating (i.e., gas not falling on the temperature-density relation). Also, while $1 + \delta \equiv \rho_{\text{gas}}/\bar{\rho}_{\text{gas}}$, the gas overdensity is often approximated as the dark matter overdensity $\rho_{\text{DM}}/\bar{\rho}_{\text{DM}}$ in N -body simulations, perhaps smoothed by an effective Jeans length.

4.3.3. THE $\text{Ly}\alpha$ FOREST IN THE FIDUCIAL CASE

Figure 4.4 shows, on the left, a slice through our fiducial simulation at $z = 3$, with a depth of $125 h^{-1}$ kpc. The small-scale filamentary structure of the high redshift universe is evident. While the dark matter and baryons have similar large-scale structure, the zoom-in panel on the right shows that the gas distribution is more diffuse. In particular, the densest filaments of dark matter lie within thicker filaments of gas. This difference reflects the impact of gas pressure support.

Figure 4.6 shows how density, temperature, velocity, and thermal broadening combine to produce $\text{Ly}\alpha$ forest spectra, along the sightlines marked 1–4 in Figure 4.4. In each panel, the bottommost plot shows the gas temperature in black and the neutral hydrogen fraction in blue. Because $n_{\text{HI}}/n_{\text{H}} \propto n_{\text{H}} T^{-0.7}$ and $T \propto n_{\text{H}}^{0.6}$ for gas on the T - ρ relation, the neutral fraction and temperature are positively correlated at most temperatures. However, high temperature gas has usually been shock heated off the T - ρ relation, and the recombination coefficient α_{HII} falls more steeply than $T^{-0.7}$ at high temperature (Katz et al. 1996), causing the neutral fraction to decrease

dramatically (see, e.g., the feature near 100 km s^{-1} in sightline #2). In the middle graphs, we plot the neutral hydrogen number density [cm^{-3}] in purple, using the scale on the left-hand axis. The gas and dark matter overdensities are plotted in black and cyan, respectively, using the scale on the right-hand axis. In general, the dark matter and gas overdensities are similar, but the dark matter has sharper, higher overdensity peaks as was seen visually in Figure 4.4. As expected from the T - ρ relation, the gas overdensity and the gas temperature follow one another except at very high gas overdensity. The highest gas overdensities correspond to condensed halos—i.e., galaxies—and thus the gas has cooled to lower temperatures in these regions. The neutral hydrogen density shows more variation than the gas density because it is proportional n_{H}^2 (actually $\rho^{1.6}$ once temperature effects are included). The topmost plot has the transmitted flux $F \equiv \exp(-\tau_{\text{HI}})$ in black and the transmitted flux that would be observed in the absence of thermal broadening in grey. The lines between the middle plot and the top plot show the effects of peculiar velocities when converting from neutral hydrogen density in physical space to an observable flux in velocity space.³ Features contracting along the line of sight cause physically distinct gas regions to converge to the same region of the observed spectrum. However, if the connecting lines do not cross, then the region still has net expansion. Both the thermally broadened and non-thermally broadened spectra have the same characteristic broad features, implying that residual Hubble flow dominates

³The bar-like appearance of the lines showing the effects of peculiar velocity also lends these complicated plots the name of “zoo plots.”

the velocity width of these features. However, thermal broadening smooths the small scale roughness. At velocity caustics (converging lines in Figure 4.6), peculiar velocities cancel the Hubble flow, and the features do become narrower when one removes the thermal broadening.

4.3.4. IMPACTS OF TEMPERATURE AND PRESSURE ON GAS EVOLUTION

The obvious consequence of having a higher photoionization heating rate is that gas temperatures in the H4 simulation are higher than in the fiducial simulation, as shown at $z = 3$ in the top panels of Figure 4.7. A more subtle effect, is that the larger Jeans length of the H4 simulation smooths the gas distribution, as shown in the density-coded bottom panels of Figure 4.7. There is a relative paucity of very dense clumps in the H4 simulation; this is especially noticeable in the lower density filaments.

Figure 4.8 plots the distribution of gas overdensity in the fiducial and H4 simulations. The visual differences in the right panel of Figure 4.7 manifest themselves as a higher frequency of particles with $\rho_{\text{gas}}/\bar{\rho}_{\text{gas}} \sim 10\text{--}100$ in the fiducial simulation and a higher frequency of $\rho_{\text{gas}}/\bar{\rho}_{\text{gas}} \sim 1$ particles in the H4 simulation. This difference leads to a cancellation in many of the statistical comparisons in §4.4; though the H4 gas is hotter (and thus has more thermal broadening), its

higher pressure implies that there there is relatively less high-density and therefore relatively higher-temperature gas. For comparison, we also show in Figure 4.8 the density distribution of the dark matter, with densities computed using the SPH smoothing kernel. Because the dark matter is pressureless, it typically reaches higher overdensities, though it does not achieve the highest overdensities seen in the gas distributions because these arise from dissipation, i.e. cooling. Extrapolating from the density distributions in our low-resolution simulation, the dark matter density distribution would probably be somewhat less skewed if we increased the mass resolution of the simulation, but at low overdensity the gas distributions are essentially converged since we resolve the Jeans mass.

4.4. EFFECTS OF PRESSURE AND THERMAL BROADENING ON THE $\text{Ly}\alpha$ FOREST

To isolate the effects of gas pressure and thermal broadening in our subsequent analyses, we examine both the original gas particle distributions and distributions with one of the three imposed T - ρ relations illustrated in Figure 4.1. For an imposed T - ρ relation, we replace each gas particle’s temperature by the temperature that corresponds to its overdensity. We use the same procedure to create $\text{Ly}\alpha$ forest spectra from the dark matter distribution (“gasifying” the dark matter). The fiducial T - ρ relation (yellow in Figure 4.1) matches that found for the IGM in the

fiducial simulation; above $1 + \delta = 10$, the gas is “shock heated” to a temperature of 5×10^5 K. Likewise, the pink lines in Figure 4.1 show the T - ρ relation used to mimic the H4 simulation. Figure 4.8 shows that gas distributions with different pressure also sample the T - ρ relation differently, and if the T - ρ relation is sloped they will therefore experience different thermal broadening. For example, using the fiducial T - ρ relation, the H4 simulation would have less high density gas with large thermal broadening, and the dark matter distribution would have more. We, therefore, consider an additional, flat T - ρ relation, with $T = 2 \times 10^4$ K at all densities, so that we can examine the effects of pressure in the presence of pressure-independent thermal-broadening. At each redshift— $z = 2, 2.4, 3,$ and 4 —we consider 200 lines of sight with paired sightlines separated by $\Delta r = 50, 100, 125, 150, 175, 200, 250, 300, 400,$ and $500 h^{-1}$ kpc comoving for a total of 2200 sightlines per redshift for each overdensity- T - ρ combination.

We now turn to the effects of pressure support and the T - ρ relation on the observed Ly α forest. We first consider the longitudinal case, examining these effects on Ly α forest spectra (§ 4.4.1) and on flux statistics (the flux power spectrum, § 4.4.2; the autocorrelation function, § 4.4.3; and the probability distribution function, § 4.4.4). We then turn to statistics sensitive to the transverse structure of the forest, looking first at how paired sightlines differ in the fiducial and H4 simulations in § 4.4.5. We then quantify these differences by examining the relative changes in the flux decrement cross-correlation function in § 4.4.6 and the relative transverse

coherence of the conditional flux decrement probability distribution in § 4.4.7. For all these analyses we use the same sightlines in each simulation to ensure the effects of sample are variance the same.

4.4.1. SPECTRA OF INDEPENDENT SIGHTLINES

Figure 4.9 shows how pressure and the T - ρ relation affect the Ly α spectra along the five sightlines labelled in Figure 4.4, with sightline #1 corresponding to the topmost spectrum in each panel; as in Figure 4.6, $v = 0$ corresponds to the top of Figure 4.4. Any differences between the models are usually most noticeable in unsaturated lines. The top-left panel shows spectra computed directly from the simulated gas distributions, with differences in pressure support, differences in thermal broadening because of the different T - ρ normalization, and differences in thermal broadening because of the sampling of the T - ρ relation. Light grey lines show spectra from our lower resolution simulation. The impact of resolution is generally very small, but there are some slight differences.

There are two notable differences between the fiducial and H4 spectra exemplified by the $v \sim 450 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ feature in sightline #5 and the $v \sim 750 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ feature in sightline #4. First, features in the H4 spectra are broader than in the fiducial spectra, which could arise because of greater thermal broadening and/or because of the larger Jeans scale (and thus the larger $H\lambda_J$). Second, features in the

H4 spectra are not as deep as in the fiducial case because the hotter gas does not reach as high overdensity and/or because higher thermal broadening smears out inherently sharp features.

The top right panel isolates the impact of thermal broadening, applying the fiducial and H4 T - ρ relations to the gas distribution of the fiducial simulation. The lower-left panel isolates the impact of pressure, applying the flat T - ρ relation to the fiducial and H4 gas distributions and to the dark matter distribution from the fiducial simulation. In some cases, such as the $v \sim 150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ feature in sightline #1, the $v \sim 1025 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ feature in sightline #3, and the $v \sim 250 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ feature in sightline #4, differences in the full simulation spectra (upper left) are largely erased in the upper right panel but remain similar in the lower left panel, which shows that they mostly arise from different pressure effects in the two simulations rather than from differences in the thermal broadening. There are fewer cases of the reverse, where differences present in the full spectra remain in the upper right panels but disappear in the lower left, though some are visible in sightline #5. The differences in the upper-right (thermal broadening isolated) are always systematic, with lower thermal broadening yielding deeper and slightly narrower features. The differences between the H4 and fiducial gas distributions in the lower-left (pressure isolated) are more random, and we will see below that their statistical signature is weaker.

The pressureless dark matter distribution does lead to spectra with more small scale structure, as shown by the thin dark lines in the lower left. However,

despite the clear differences between the gas and dark matter distributions evident in Figures 4.4, 4.6, and 4.8, the differences in the spectra created from these distributions are small. In the absence of thermal broadening, dark matter spectra are much more jagged than their gas counterparts shown in Figure 4.6, but realistic thermal broadening masks these differences to a large extent. The velocity widths of most features are not sensitive to the level of thermal broadening (as seen in the upper right) but neither are they set by the Jeans scale, or else the dark matter and gas spectra would have greater differences. Instead, thermal broadening erases the finest scale structures in the density field so that typical features correspond to coherent, moderate overdensity structures expanding with the Hubble flow.

Adopting the fiducial T - ρ relation in place of the flat T - ρ relation (bottom right) makes only a small difference to the usual appearance of the spectra (top left). Features that are flat-bottomed in the dark matter spectra with the flat T - ρ relation often become less saturated with the fiducial T - ρ relation, such as the $v \sim 775 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ feature in sightline #3 and the $v \sim 1000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ feature in sightline #5. In these regions, the dark matter overdensity is high, so with $T \propto (1 + \delta)^{0.6}$ they have higher thermal broadening, which spreads the feature in velocity space and reduces its saturation. In some cases, such as the $v \sim 725 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ feature of sightline #1, the wings of the dark matter feature become noticeably broader than those of the gas features because of the higher temperatures at higher overdensities.

4.4.2. THE 1-D FLUX POWER SPECTRUM

The Lyman- α flux power spectrum is a powerful tool for probing the dark matter mass power spectrum on the smallest scales. Because of the high redshift, the continuous sampling of the line-of-sight density field, and the moderate overdensity of absorbing structures, the Ly α forest provides a more direct link to the linear theory power spectrum than other small-scale tracers. (Primary cosmic microwave background anisotropies are damped on these scales.) However, to infer information about the structure of the underlying dark matter, one must understand the thermal structure of the IGM, as the amplitude and the shape of the flux power spectrum are connected to the gas temperature-density relation via equation (4.9). The bias of the flux power spectrum, i.e., $b^2(k) = P_F(k)/P_{\text{lin}}(k)$, is also influenced by non-linear gravitational evolution, thermal broadening, pressure support, peculiar velocities, and shock heating (Croft et al. 1998, 1999, 2002; Viel et al. 2004, 2008; McDonald et al. 2005).

Figures 4.11–4.13 show the one-dimensional line-of-sight flux power spectrum, $P_{1\text{D}}(k)$ of $(F - \langle F \rangle)$, where $F \equiv \exp(-\tau_{\text{Ly}\alpha})$, based on 600 randomly selected sightlines through the fiducial, H4, and low resolution simulations. The flux power spectrum $P_{1\text{D}}(k)$ is a measure of the variance of the flux, σ_F^2 , on different scales; specifically, we adopt the normalization convention of McDonald et al. (2000), where

$$\sigma_F^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{dk}{2\pi} P_{1\text{D}}(k) = \pi^{-1} \int_0^{\infty} dk P_{1\text{D}}(k). \quad (4.10)$$

Also plotted in Figures 4.11–4.13 are the flux power spectra for the same lines of sight in both the fiducial and H4 simulations in the absence of thermal broadening. For reference, we also plot the observed flux power spectrum measured from high-resolution spectra given in Table 4 of McDonald et al. (2000, squares) and Table 7 (the “B” sample at $z = 2.4$ and the “D” sample at $z = 3$) of Croft et al. (2002, triangles). We have renormalized the Croft et al. (2002) measurements by McDonald et al.’s $\langle F \rangle^2$ to match our normalization convention.

The cutoff in the flux power spectrum at large k is a consequence of thermal broadening, as is obvious from comparing the power spectra with and without thermal broadening. With thermal broadening included, the low resolution (144^3 gas particles) and fiducial (288^3) simulations produce very similar power spectra, indicating that even the lower resolution simulation is well converged for this statistic. At high k , the power spectra of the H4 simulation are offset by roughly a factor of 1.6 in k from the fiducial simulation, roughly consistent with the difference of 2–2.5 in T_0 (since thermal velocities scale as $T_0^{1/2}$). The cutoff scale in the fiducial simulation agrees better with the observational data, even though its temperatures are low compared to the McDonald et al. (2001) estimates (see Fig. 4.3).

Our cutoff scale also differs from that of Lidz et al. (2009, Figure 5); the flux power spectrum of our fiducial simulation is more similar (on small and large scales) to that of their hotter, $T_0 = 2 \times 10^4$ K and $\alpha = 0.3$, simulation than to their colder, $T_0 = 1 \times 10^4$ K and $\alpha = 0.6$, simulation, which has a T - ρ relation similar to our

fiducial simulation. We see no obvious reason for this discrepancy: the resolution test in Figures 4.11–4.13 show good convergence, we do not expect the cutoff scale to be sensitive to box size, we have checked that high as density peaks produce the expected thermally broadened line profiles in our extracted spectra, and we find good agreement between the flux power spectrum from our $z = 3$ spectra measured by our code (written by R. Croft) and an independent code written by P. McDonald.⁴ When spectra are extracted from our simulation using Lidz et al.’s code, the calculated $P(k)$ is consistent with the one we measure;⁵ the difference is therefore present in the simulated gas distributions themselves. For now, we draw no strong conclusions from the comparison to data in these figures, and focus instead on the relative roles of pressure support and thermal broadening.

To separate the effects of gas pressure and thermal broadening, Figure 4.14 shows $z = 3$ flux power spectra from 200 randomly selected sightlines through the fiducial gas, H4 gas, and fiducial dark matter density fields (indicated by the line type), each with three imposed temperature-density relations: fiducial, H4, and flat (indicated by the line color). Comparing lines of the same color in Figure 4.14 shows the effects of pressure support, with the same T - ρ relation applied to different density distributions. Comparing lines of the same type but different colors isolates the effect of the T - ρ relation for the same underlying density distribution. The lines clearly separate into three groups based on color, showing that thermal broadening

⁴We thank Patrick McDonald for carrying out this test for us.

⁵We thank Adam Lidz for carrying out this test for us.

dominates over pressure support in determining the scale of the power spectrum cutoff. There is some difference among the three density distributions when we impose a constant IGM temperature $T = 2 \times 10^4$ K (blue lines), which shows that some of the similarity for the other T - ρ relations may reflect the cancellation discussed in §4.3.4, where the distribution with a larger Jeans length has less high density gas to experience high thermal broadening. However, on the whole our results confirm the finding of McDonald (2003) that it is the instantaneous T - ρ relation (at the epoch of observation) rather than the detailed gas thermal history (and thus pressure history) that determines the $P_F(k)$ cutoff.

4.4.3. FLUX DECREMENT AUTOCORRELATION FUNCTIONS

The flux decrement autocorrelation function,

$$\xi_{\text{auto}}(\Delta v) \equiv \frac{\langle D(v)D(v + \Delta v) \rangle}{\langle D \rangle^2}, \quad (4.11)$$

is a commonly used tool for characterizing the Ly α forest. While technically the one-dimensional flux power spectrum and flux autocorrelation functions codify the same information ($P_F(k)$ is just the one-dimensional Fourier transform of ξ_{auto}), the flux autocorrelation function is often easier to describe both observationally and from simulations because its definition does not depend on information from all scales. Furthermore, as cross-correlation functions are more typically used to describe information in closely paired lines of sight than cross-power spectra, it

is important for us to understand the effects of pressure and temperature on the autocorrelation function before examining paired sightlines (§ 4.4.6).

Figure 4.15 plots normalized flux decrement autocorrelation functions at $z = 2.4, 3.0,$ and 4.0 . We normalize $\xi_{\text{auto}} = 1$ at the smallest scales to highlight differences in the turnover scale of the correlation function rather than differences in normalization. The fiducial and low-resolution simulations have nearly identical ξ_{auto} , while the H4 simulation has a noticeably larger coherence scale. However, if we impose the fiducial T - ρ relation on the H4 gas, then ξ_{auto} is nearly identical to that of the fiducial simulation. Conversely, imposing the H4 T - ρ on the fiducial simulation yields nearly the same ξ_{auto} as the H4 simulation.⁶

While these results suggest that the effects of pressure are small compared to those of thermal broadening, the right-hand panels of Figure 4.15 show that ξ_{auto} is different for the H4 gas, fiducial gas, and fiducial dark matter if we impose a flat $T = 2 \times 10^4$ K on all particles. In this case, the higher pressure distribution exhibits a larger coherence scale, especially at high redshifts. Thus, the similarity of the fiducial and H4 distributions with the same imposed T - ρ , seen in the left-hand panels, arises partly from the counter-balancing effects of T_0 and the changes in the distribution of gas densities discussed in § 4.3.4 (see Figure 4.8).

⁶If we impose the fiducial (H4) T - ρ relation on the fiducial (H4) simulation, instead of using the simulation temperatures themselves, then the change in ξ_{auto} is negligible.

4.4.4. FLUX DECREMENT PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTIONS

The flux decrement probability distribution function (PDF) is a potentially powerful tool for probing the IGM, both by itself and as a means of adding constraints to other statistical measures such as the flux power spectrum (Rauch et al. 1997; Weinberg 1999; Gaztañaga & Croft 1999; Nusser & Haehnelt 2000; Desjacques & Nusser 2005; Desjacques et al. 2007). In particular, Bolton et al. (2008) have recently used the Ly α forest flux distribution as measured by Kim et al. (2007) to suggest that the temperature-density relation at $z \sim 3$ is *inverted* ($\alpha < 0$ in equation 4.6), with low-density gas at higher temperature than higher density gas. While the differences owing to changes in the T - ρ relation are not as extreme as those in $P_F(k)$ or ξ_{auto} , the flux decrement PDF can potentially be measured to much higher accuracy using the same number of sightlines. On the other hand, the PDF is sensitive to continuum fitting, while on small scales $P_F(k)$ is not (on large scales continuum fitting can be problematic even for $P_F(k)$; e.g., Kim et al. 2004). Furthermore, high-resolution spectra are needed to accurately measure the PDF (Viel et al. 2004; Tytler et al. 2004). Since high-resolution spectra will always exist in smaller numbers than low-resolution spectra, it should be noted that the PDF is also potentially sensitive to sample variance, the explanation Kim et al. (2007) suggest for the $\sim 30\%$ difference between their $z \sim 3$ PDF and the one measured by McDonald et al. (2000) on a very similar data set.

Figure 4.16 shows the linear flux decrement PDF, i.e., $p(D)$, where $p(D)\Delta D$ is the number of pixels in a bin of width ΔD divided by the total number of pixels. In Figure 4.17 we show for a larger set of models the logarithmic PDF, $p(\log D)$, which allows better visual discrimination in the range $0.1 < D < 0.5$. The shape of the PDF changes radically with redshift as the mean flux decrement changes; physically, this change is driven by the mean density dropping as $(1+z)^3$. However, as all the models at a given redshift are normalized to the same $\langle D \rangle$, the effects of T - ρ changes on the *mean* absorption are removed. Though for visual clarity we do not plot the PDFs from the 2×144^3 particle simulation, the low resolution and fiducial PDFs differ by ~ 1 – 5% ; this difference is much smaller than the typical model differences in Figures 4.16 and 4.17.

Thermal broadening reduces the number of transparent ($D \approx 0$) pixels, while pressure support increases the number of pixels at extreme flux decrements (for visual clarity, we do not plot the dark matter and non-thermally broadened PDFs). At all redshifts, the spectra generated from the full H4 simulation have more pixels with mid-range flux decrements, i.e. relative to the fiducial simulation, the H4 simulation produces fewer opaque pixels and fewer transparent pixels. This is as expected, since higher pressure smooths the gas distribution and higher temperature leads to greater thermal broadening. However, the fiducial simulation with the imposed H4 T - ρ has fewer saturated pixels than the H4 simulation itself, and more pixels with $D \approx 0.6$ – 0.8 . This surprising result highlights the sometimes complicated interplay

between the density distribution and the T - ρ relation. The fiducial simulation has more high overdensity gas (Figure 4.8), but because this gas is at high temperature (with $T \propto [1 + \delta]^{0.6}$), thermal broadening converts narrow, fully saturated features to broader, moderately saturated ones.

The slope of the T - ρ relation has a direct impact on the flux PDF, independent of thermal broadening, because it affects the mapping from density contrast to flux. Equation (4.9) gives $\tau_{\text{HI}} \propto (1 + \delta)^{2-0.7\alpha}$, so $\tau_{\text{HI}} \propto (1 + \delta)^{1.6}$ for our fiducial and H4 relations (with $\alpha \approx 0.6$) and $\tau_{\text{HI}} \propto (1 + \delta)^2$ for our flat, $T = 2 \times 10^4$ K relation ($\alpha = 0$). Imposing a constant T substantially alters the PDFs of both the fiducial and H4 simulations (blue curves in Figure 4.17), with the greater sensitivity of τ_{HI} to $(1 + \delta)$ leading to more saturated pixels and fewer mid-range pixels. The two simulations have significantly different PDFs, which with constant thermal broadening must arise from effects of pressure on the gas density distribution. In contrast to the power spectrum and flux correlation function, thermal broadening and pressure support have comparable impact on the flux PDF, and they interact in complex ways. This different behavior arises because the PDF responds directly to the full overdensity distribution and its mapping to flux, while the power spectrum and correlation function measure the variance of this distribution as a function of scale.

4.4.5. SPECTRA OF PAIRED SIGHTLINES

Before delving into statistical measures of the transverse Ly α forest, it will be instructive to first consider the underlying physical structures. In Figure 4.5, we show a small section of the fiducial simulation at $z = 2.4$, where brighter regions correspond to higher H I densities. The three sightlines in Figure 4.5 give rise to the top, middle, and bottom green spectra at $z = 2.4$ in the left-hand panel of Figure 4.9. Figure 4.9 shows how pairs of spectra become more dissimilar as their transverse separation, Δr , increases, and how this dissimilarity differs between the fiducial and H4 simulations. Spectral features remaining coherent over large scales correspond to physical structures that are parallel to the plane of the sky (see, e.g., the structures at $400 < v < 600 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), while spectral features disappearing from one sightline to the next correspond to physical structures that are more parallel to the line of sight (see, e.g., the features at $v < 300 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). In general, the H4 spectra remain more similar than the fiducial ones as Δr increases; we aim to determine to what extent this relatively higher coherence owes to pressure support rather than to the fact that the H4 spectra are individually inherently smoother because they have more thermal broadening than the fiducial spectra.

4.4.6. CROSS-CORRELATION FUNCTIONS

A common method for studying the transverse structure of the IGM is to look at the flux decrement cross-correlation function,

$$\xi_{\text{cross}} \equiv \frac{\langle D_1(v)D_2(v + \Delta v) \rangle}{\langle D \rangle^2}, \quad (4.12)$$

where $D \equiv 1 - F = 1 - \exp(-\tau)$ and the two sightlines are separated by some Δr (Miralda-Escudé et al. 1996; Rollinde et al. 2003). At $\Delta r = 0$, ξ_{cross} is just the auto-correlation function. The cross-correlation functions for the $z = 2.4$ fiducial and H4 simulations at a range of Δr are shown in the left-hand panels of Figure 4.18. At small Δr and Δv , the gas in the fiducial simulation has a higher ξ_{cross} than the gas in the H4 simulation because the smoother gas distribution has less rms density fluctuation. At larger Δr and Δv , the H4 gas has a higher ξ_{cross} owing to its greater coherence, as is visually evident in Figure 4.9. To quantify this relative change, $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$ for the same selection of Δr is plotted in the right-hand panels of Figure 4.18. Although in real space $\xi_{\text{cross}}(\Delta r) = \xi_{\text{auto}}(H\Delta r)$, in velocity space redshift distortions preferentially suppress the auto-correlation function relative to the cross-correlation function, causing $\xi_{\text{cross}} > \xi_{\text{auto}}$ for some regions of parameter space (McDonald & Miralda-Escudé 1999; Marble et al. 2008b). The hotter, higher pressure, H4 simulation has a higher relative coherence (larger $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$) at small Δv than the colder fiducial simulation.

We compare a wider range of models in Figure 4.19, where we plot $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$ as a function of Δr at $\Delta v = 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at $z = 2.4$; this corresponds to taking a slice at $\Delta v = 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ in the right-hand panels of Figure 4.18. To elucidate whether the H4 gas is more strongly correlated because it has higher pressure, or because hotter gas has more thermal broadening and therefore less small-scale structure, we also look at a range of T - ρ relations and overdensity fields. In this and in several of the following figures the line type (solid, dashed, or dotted) corresponds to the adopted overdensity field, either the gas overdensities from the fiducial simulation (solid lines), the gas overdensities from the H4 simulation (dashed lines) or the dark matter overdensities from the fiducial simulations. The line color corresponds to the adopted equation of state, i.e. the T - ρ relation, either the artificial fit to the relation from the fiducial simulation (green lines), the fit to the relation from the H4 simulation (red lines), or assuming a constant temperature of $T = 2 \times 10^4 \text{ K}$ (blue lines).

In Figure 4.19, the three choices for the overdensity field clearly separate into three distinct groups, with the highest-pressure H4 gas having the most transverse coherence and the zero-pressure dark matter having the least. Even non-thermally broadened spectra (which we have not plotted to avoid visual confusion) show the same relative decrease in coherence with increase in transverse separation as other spectra with the same underlying gas distributions. Within each overdensity group, $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$ increases with increasing thermal broadening (e.g., the imposed H4 T - ρ

relation yields higher $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$ at all Δr than imposing the fiducial T - ρ). However, lowering the resolution leads to offsets from the fiducial case by about the same amount as imposing different T - ρ relations. The same trends are seen at $z = 2, 3$, and 4, as shown in Figure 4.20. In general, we find this delineation is clearer at $10 \lesssim \Delta v \lesssim 30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ than at $\Delta v = 0$ or at larger velocity separations. The stark separation by overdensity distribution of the normalized cross-correlation function as a function of transverse separation is a clear sign that pressure plays an important role in the transverse structure of the Ly α forest.

A common use for the flux decrement cross-correlation function is to measure the anisotropy in the Ly α forest caused by line-of-sight velocity distortions (Coppolani et al. 2006; D’Odorico et al. 2006), such as for the Alcock & Paczynski (1979) test (Hui et al. 1999; McDonald & Miralda-Escudé 1999). In Figure 4.21, we compare $\xi_{\text{cross}}(\Delta v = 0, \Delta r)$ to the autocorrelation function at the same scale, $\xi_{\text{auto}}(H\Delta r)$, at $z = 2.4$; higher values indicate higher levels of anisotropy. As in Figure 4.19, the models separate into groups of overdensity, and the differences between our low-resolution and fiducial cases are comparable with imposing different T - ρ relations on the fiducial gas. Figure 4.22 shows the same statistic for a smaller set of models at $z = 2, 3$, and 4. As mentioned above, in real space $\xi_{\text{cross}}(\Delta r) = \xi_{\text{auto}}(H\Delta r)$, but in (observed) velocity space, redshift distortions introduce anisotropy (Marble et al. 2008b). Because thermal broadening is an inherently one-dimensional anisotropic phenomenon, higher thermal broadening leads to higher anisotropy; we see this

effect for each overdensity distribution in Figures 4.21 and 4.22. Pressure, on the other hand, is a three-dimensional inherently isotropic phenomenon: higher pressure therefore leads to less anisotropy, as we see from comparing the results for the dark matter, fiducial, and H4 overdensity fields. For $H\Delta r \lesssim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ ($\Delta\theta \lesssim 10''$), the impact of thermal broadening on anisotropy is generally smaller than the impact of pressure.

4.4.7. CONDITIONAL FLUX PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTIONS

The structure of one-point flux probability distribution function (PDF) depends on both the thermal history and current thermal state of the gas, leading to a complex relationship between the effects of pressure support and thermal broadening on the PDF (§ 4.4.4). On the other hand, the interpretation of the conditional probability distribution function between paired sightlines (Miralda-Escudé et al. 1997) is relatively straightforward. For example, if for strongly absorbed pixels with $0.8 \leq D_1 < 1.0$, the pixels separated by Δv on a sightline Δr away are more strongly absorbed than randomly expected, then this might be a signature of strong transverse coherence and thus a large Jeans length. In Figure 4.23 we plot the flux decrement difference probability distributions, $p(D_2 - D_1)$, for $\Delta v = 0$ and $\Delta r = 150 h^{-1} \text{ kpc}$ and several bins of D_1 , for the fiducial, H4, and low resolution gas at $z = 2.4$. By looking at the PDF of the decrement differences, we can easily quantify the similarity of flux decrement pairs. The more strongly the distribution

peaks around $D_2 = D_1$, the more coherent are the transverse structures. While the differences between the two simulations are not dramatic, the H4 model is consistently more strongly peaked around $D_2 = D_1$, with a stronger signature at low D_1 . For most choices of D_1 , this difference is much more pronounced than the difference between the fiducial and low-resolution simulations, indicating that our 288^3 particle simulations give robust results for this statistic.

In §4.4.4 we showed that the flux decrement PDFs for each of these T - ρ relations are fairly distinct, so some of the model differences in $p(D_2 - D_1)$ could reflect differences in the underlying flux PDFs. We can remove this effect by converting from flux decrement D to pixel rank $R \equiv p(< D)$, the fraction of pixels with a flux decrement lower than D . Of course, a fully successful model should reproduce the observed PDF, but here we wish to focus on transverse coherence and, therefore, remove any differences in the PDF caused by different temperature-density relations. Figure 4.24 shows that spectra generated from the H4 gas have rank difference distributions more strongly peaked around $R_2 - R_1 = 0$ than spectra from the lower pressure, fiducial gas spectra. Changing the imposed temperature-density relation has less effect on the distributions than changing the underlying gas distribution, implying that (as expected) pressure rather than thermal broadening accounts for the larger transverse coherence. In general, the larger coherence appears at all redshifts, but it weakens with increasing Δr . Non-thermally broadened spectra (not shown) have broader $R_2 - R_1$ distributions, so thermal broadening does play

some role in transverse coherence. As with previous statistics, however, the lower resolution spectra differ from the fiducial case by about as much as spectra generated from different imposed T - ρ relations. Figure 4.25 presents the $z = 2.4$ predictions in greater detail for the fiducial and H4 gas only, plotting five ranges of R_1 and comparing $\Delta v = 0$ to $\Delta v \sim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The models are most easily distinguished at small Δv and at small Δr .

In general, the slope of the temperature-density relation is much more difficult to observationally constrain than T_0 because most methods for measuring the T - ρ relation are sensitive to only a limited range of τ_{HI} and hence $1 + \delta$. Because (up to saturation) we can limit ourselves to a particular range of optical depth and thus $1 + \delta$ when using *conditional* rank distributions, it might be possible to use this technique to constrain the slope of the temperature-density relation. We cannot test this possibility using our current simulations because the fiducial and H4 temperature-density relations have similar slopes at all redshifts (see Table 4.1).

4.5. CONCLUSIONS

We have investigated the relative importance of pressure support and thermal broadening in determining the longitudinal structure of the Lyman- α forest. Our main results come from comparing two SPH simulations with identical initial conditions but different photoionization heating rates, which produce a factor of

~ 2.3 difference in the temperature of diffuse IGM gas. We have imposed different temperature-density relations on the simulation outputs to isolate physical effects, extracted spectra from the dark matter distribution to extend our investigation to the pressureless case, and compared the fiducial simulation (2×288^3 particles) to a lower resolution simulation (2×144^3) to quantify numerical resolution effects.

Equation (4.3) shows that the Hubble flow across the Jeans scale is generally of the same magnitude as thermal broadening ($H\lambda_J \sim \sigma_{\text{th}}$). However, the IGM is an expanding, inhomogeneous medium evolving in the potential of a non-linear dark matter distribution, so the Jeans length is at best an approximate description of the scale imposed by gas pressure support. It is therefore difficult to know without detailed simulations whether thermal broadening or pressure support will dominate the structure of the forest. A related question is the meaning of the density contrast δ in the fluctuating Gunn-Peterson approximation (equation 4.9). In principle, this should be the density of the gas that is absorbing Ly α photons, but analyses of early SPH simulations found that Ly α forest spectra created from the (pressureless) dark matter distribution were remarkably similar to those created from the (pressure supported) gas distribution (e.g., Croft et al. 1998). However, the relatively low resolution of those simulations (a mass resolution that is ~ 60 times lower than our fiducial simulation here) raised the possibility that both sets of spectra were artificially broadened to the numerical resolution limit. We investigate this issue more confidently here because the initial particle spacing of our 288^3

simulations, $43 h^{-1}$ kpc comoving, is far below the typical Jeans length at IGM overdensities, $\lambda_J \sim 800 h^{-1}$ kpc comoving, and because our 144^3 simulation allows a direct resolution test.

In broad brush, our conclusions are that thermal broadening dominates over pressure support in determining the visual appearance and statistical properties of the Ly α forest along the line of sight, but that differences in gas pressure do have a noticeable effect. The widths of absorption features are typically set by Hubble flow across the absorbing structure, though thermal broadening does smooth out small scale corrugations to create coherent features (see Fig. 4.6). Once we include thermal broadening, the spectra created from dark matter distributions are similar to those created from the gas, even though the effects of pressure support on the gas density field are readily discernible. Thus, one can drastically change the Jeans scale without drastically changing the forest. However, dark matter spectra are visually and statistically distinguishable from gas spectra, more so than in the earlier generation of lower resolution SPH simulations.

Turning to individual statistics, we find that thermal broadening sets the turnover scale of the one-dimensional flux power spectrum, with the fiducial gas, H4 gas, and dark matter distributions producing similar power spectra if one imposes the fiducial or H4 T - ρ relation on all three. Similar conclusions hold for the coherence scale of the flux decrement autocorrelation function. However, in both cases, the weak impact of pressure support partly owes to a cancellation effect

that arises with a sloped T - ρ relation: a higher pressure distribution has more “Jeans broadening,” but it has less thermal broadening because there is less high overdensity, high temperature gas. When we impose a constant IGM temperature of $T = 2 \times 10^4$ K, the differences among the three cases are more noticeable, though they are still small compared to the effects of thermal broadening. For the flux decrement probability distribution function, thermal broadening and pressure support have effects of comparable magnitude, though thermal broadening is still somewhat more important.

Our 144^3 and 288^3 simulations yield similar results for all our statistics. The resolution effects are larger at $z = 4$ than at lower redshifts, where they have a small but noticeable impact on all the statistics. For most purposes, the resolution of our 144^3 simulations (in a $12.5 h^{-1}$ Mpc comoving volume) is adequate.

Though it is a stronger player than pressure support in setting the scale of the longitudinal Ly α forest, thermal broadening is an inherently one-dimensional phenomenon. Because pressure acts in three dimensions, it dominates in setting the *transverse* coherence of the Ly α forest across neighboring sightlines. Growing samples of binary quasars with separations of $\Delta\theta \lesssim 10''$ now make it possible to probe the expected Jeans scale (Hennawi et al. 2006, 2009). The closely paired Lyman- α forest sightlines from such quasar pairs are ideal for studying the small-scale transverse structure of the intergalactic medium. We have shown using a set of smoothed particle hydrodynamic simulations with different equations of state

that the coherence of transverse structure at these scales is determined primarily by the level of pressure support, i.e. the Jeans length, of the absorbing gas and is relatively insensitive to the amount of thermal broadening along the line of sight. Given the surprisingly high temperatures implied by single-sightline analyses (see discussion in §4.1), it would be valuable to investigate the thermal state of the IGM by this largely independent method.

Flux correlation functions (measured by, e.g., Rollinde et al. 2003; Coppolani et al. 2006; D’Odorico et al. 2006; Marble et al. 2008a) and the two-point distributions of flux decrements or pixel ranks can all be used to distinguish among gas distributions with different temperatures like the fiducial and H4 models considered here. Because the redshift ranges and pair separations will be dictated by the specifics of the available data sample, we provide in the form of electronic tables our simulated spectra along paired lines of sight from the two simulations, which can be used to generate predictions tailored to a particular data sample. These samples of spectra are described in §4.2 and the caption to Table 4.1. We caution that the finite size of our simulation volume could cause statistical fluctuations and systematic effects on our predictions, especially at large Δr and Δv ; we will investigate this point in future work with larger simulations. The large increase in known quasar pairs, the ability of large telescopes to measure Lyman- α absorption spectra of relatively faint background sources, which have a high surface density on the sky, and the massive quasar sample expected from the Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic

Survey (Schlegel et al. 2009) will change the Ly α forest from a one-dimensional phenomenon to a three-dimensional phenomenon, opening new opportunities to constrain cosmology and the physics of the diffuse intergalactic medium.

Fig. 4.1.— Distribution of 1% of the gas particles for the fiducial simulation in the temperature-density plane at $z = 3$. In subsequent analyses, we use either the simulation temperatures themselves or one of the three plotted $T-\rho$ relations (*dashed lines*).

Fig. 4.2.— Distribution of particles in the temperature-overdensity plane for the fiducial simulation at $z = 2.4$, with three imposed temperature-density relations overplotted as labelled, as well as the temperature and overdensity distributions for the fiducial and H4 simulations. The hotter H4 gas is preferentially less dense than the lower pressure fiducial gas and pressureless dark matter.

Fig. 4.3.— A comparison of the temperature-density relation evolution from simulations (*dashed lines*), calculations using equation (4.5) (*points*), and observations (*shaded regions*). The shaded region corresponds to the $1-\sigma$ error region from McDonald et al. (2001), with the orange lines indicating the best-fit relations at each redshift. (There are two such lines for $z = 3$ and 2.4 because McDonald et al. used simulations at two different redshifts to compare to these observations.) At $z = 3$, the dashed pink and black lines are the same as the dashed pink and gold lines, respectively, in Fig. 4.1.

Fig. 4.4.— A $125 h^{-1}$ kpc thick slice (*left*) and a $125 \times 125 h^{-1}$ kpc comoving region (*right*) of the fiducial simulation at $z = 3$ with gas particles (*red*), dark matter particles (*black*), and star particles (*blue*) all shown. The five green lines (*left*) denote sightlines referred to in subsequent figures.

Fig. 4.5.— A $12.5 \times 1 \times 1 h^{-1}$ Mpc comoving section of the fiducial simulation, in H I density, with $-8 < \log n_{\text{HI}} < 0$ (note that the aspect ratio has not been preserved). The three green sightlines are separated by $100 h^{-1}$ kpc comoving; at $z = 2.4$, corresponding to a projected separation of $4.9''$.

Fig. 4.6.— Physical quantities and Ly α forest spectra along four of the sightlines labelled in Figure 4.4; velocity $v = 0$ corresponds to the top of Figure 4.4. Shown in real space are the temperature (*black, bottom*), the neutral hydrogen fraction (*blue, bottom*), the H I number density (*purple, middle*), the gas overdensity (*black, middle*), and the dark matter overdensity (*cyan, middle*). The bars separating the top and middle panels show the effects of peculiar velocities when transitioning from real space to the observed flux transmission with (*top, black*) and without (*top, grey*) thermal broadening. See § 4.3.3 for more details.

Fig. 4.7.— Temperature (*top*) and density (*bottom*) evolution for gas particles in a $2.5 \times 2.5 \times 0.05 h^{-1} \text{Mpc}$ comoving slice at $z = 3$ in the fiducial (*left*) and H4 (*right*) simulations. The temperature scale runs logarithmically from from $\log T = 3.5$ (*black/dark blue*) to $\log T = 5.5$ (*yellow/white*). The density scale runs from $\log(\rho_{\text{gas}}/\bar{\rho}_{\text{gas}}) \equiv \log(1 + \delta) = -1.3$ (*black*) to $\log(1 + \delta) = 1.3$ (*green*).

Fig. 4.8.— Distributions of gas overdensities at $z = 3$ in the fiducial (*solid histogram*) and H4 (*dashed*) simulations, as well as the dissipationless dark matter (*dotted*) in the fiducial simulation.

Fig. 4.9.— Comparison of spectra along the sightlines labelled in Figure 4.4, isolating different physical effects. Top left: full effects of thermal broadening, thermal history and resolution are shown. Top right: effects of thermal broadening are isolated. Bottom left: effects of pressure support are isolated. Bottom right: effects of pressure support and different samplings of the underlying overdensity distribution are isolated. See § 4.4.1 for details.

Fig. 4.10.— Sample paired lines of sight at $z = 2.4$ separated by $\Delta r = 50, 100, 150, 200,$ and $250 h^{-1} \text{ kpc}$ comoving, from top to bottom, with the fiducial simulation on the left and the H4 simulation on the right. Within each column, the black spectra are the same ($r = 0$). The top, middle, and bottom green spectra correspond to the three green sight lines in Fig. 4.5, with $v = 0$ corresponding to the left-hand side of Fig. 4.5.

Fig. 4.11.— The 1-D flux power spectrum at $z = 4.0$ with the fiducial simulation in black, the H4 simulation in pink, and the lower-resolution simulation in grey. For reference, we also show the flux power spectrum in the absence of thermal broadening for the fiducial gas (*green*) and the H4 gas (*purple*), as well as the observed flux power spectrum from McDonald et al. (2001, *squares*) and Croft et al. (2002, *triangles*).

Fig. 4.12.— The same as Figure 4.11 but at $z = 3.0$.

Fig. 4.13.— The same as Figure 4.11 but at $z = 2.4$.

Fig. 4.14.— The 1-D flux power spectrum at $z = 3$ for fiducial gas (*solid lines*), H4 gas (*dashed lines*), and fiducial dark matter (*dotted lines*) with fiducial (*brown*), H4 (*red*), and flat (*blue*) imposed temperature-density relations.

Fig. 4.15.— *Left*: Normalized flux decrement autocorrelation functions, $\xi_{\text{auto}} \equiv \langle D(v)D(v + \Delta v) \rangle / \langle D \rangle^2$, at $z = 2.4, 3.0$, and 4.0 . The black curve with error bars shows results for the fiducial simulation, while the pink and grey lines show results for the H4 and low-resolution simulations, respectively. Red and mustard lines show, respectively, the fiducial gas with the H4 T - ρ relation imposed and the H4 gas with the fiducial T - ρ . The green line shows the fiducial gas with no thermal broadening. *Right*: Normalized ξ_{auto} , for the fiducial gas (*light blue*), H4 gas (*bright blue*), and fiducial dark matter (*dark blue*), all with an imposed temperature of $T = 2 \times 10^4$ K.

Fig. 4.16.— Flux decrement probability distributions in linear bins of D at $z = 2.4, 3,$ and 4 for the fiducial and H4 simulations, with (*black* and *pink*) inherent temperatures and imposed H4 (*red*) and fiducial (*mustard*) T - ρ relations, respectively. The points at $z = 2.4$ and 3 are included to show the $p(D)$ in the most transparent (*left*) and opaque (*right*) bins.

Fig. 4.17.— Flux decrement probability distributions in logarithmic bins of D at $z = 2.4, 3,$ and 4 for the fiducial gas distribution, with inherent temperatures (*black*), at low resolution (*grey*), and with imposed H4 $T-\rho$ (*red*). Also shown are the imposed H4 gas distribution with inherent temperatures (*pink*), with the imposed fiducial $T-\rho$ (*mustard*), as well as both the fiducial and H4 gas distributions with an imposed flat $T = 2 \times 10^4$ K (*light blue* and *bright blue*, respectively). The points are included to show the $p(D)$ in the final (most opaque) bin.

Fig. 4.18.— The cross-correlation function $\xi_{\text{cross}} \equiv \langle D_1(v)D_2(v+\Delta v) \rangle / \langle D \rangle^2$ (left) and $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$ (right) for the fiducial (top) and H4 (bottom) simulations for six different transverse separations $\Delta r = 50, 100, 150, 200,$ and $250 h^{-1} \text{kpc}$ comoving. Note that the vertical scale in the left panels does not extend to 0.

Fig. 4.19.— Normalized cross-correlation functions, $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$, as a function of the transverse separation Δr for $\Delta v = 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at $z = 2.4$. The line type (solid, dashed, or dotted) denotes the adopted overdensity field and the line color the adopted T - ρ relation (see § 4.2 for details). The thick black tickmark denotes $\Delta r = H\Delta v$.

Fig. 4.20.— Normalized cross-correlation functions, $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$, as a function of the transverse separation Δr for $\Delta v = 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at $z = 4, 3,$ and 2 , from top to bottom. The models are denoted as in Fig. 4.19. The thick black tickmark denotes $\Delta r = H\Delta v$.

Fig. 4.21.— Normalized cross-correlation functions showing the anisotropy of the Ly α forest, $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$, as a function of $\Delta v = H\Delta r$, at $z = 2.4$. The models are denoted as in Fig. 4.19

Fig. 4.22.— Normalized cross-correlation functions showing the anisotropy of the Ly α forest, $\xi_{\text{cross}}/\xi_{\text{auto}}$, as a function of $\Delta v = H\Delta r$, at $z = 4, 3,$ and 2 . The models are denoted as in Fig. 4.19

Fig. 4.23.— Flux decrement difference probability distributions, $p(D_2 - D_1)$ v. $(D_2 - D_1)$, at $z = 2.4$, for $\Delta v = 0$ and $\Delta r = 150$. The three columns show $D_1 \in [0.2, 0.4]$ (*left*), $D_1 \in [0.4, 0.6]$ (*middle*), and $D_1 \in [0.8, 1.0]$ (*right*), with fiducial in black, H4 in purple (*dotted*), and the low resolution simulation in grey.

Fig. 4.24.— Probability distributions for differences in flux decrement rank, $p(R_2 - R_1)$ vs. $(R_2 - R_1)$ for $\Delta v = 0$, $0.4 \leq R_1 \leq 0.6$, and $z = 4, 3$, and 2.0 (top to bottom). The three columns show comoving transverse separations $\Delta r = 100, 200$, and $300 h^{-1} \text{kpc}$ (left to right). Regardless of the imposed temperature-density relation (indicated by line color), the H4 gas (*dotted lines*) is more strongly peaked around $R_2 = R_1$ than the fiducial gas (*solid lines*) because the hotter gas has longer Jeans lengths and thus higher transverse coherence.

Fig. 4.25.— Probability distributions for differences in flux decrement rank, $p(R_2 - R_1)$ v. $(R_2 - R_1)$ for $\Delta r = 100, 200,$ and $300 h^{-1} \text{ kpc}$ comoving and $\Delta v = 0$ and 20 km s^{-1} as labelled, for a range of R_1 at $z = 2.4$. The H4 gas (*purple, dotted*) is more strongly peaked around $R_2 = R_1$ than the fiducial gas (*black, solid*) because the hotter gas has longer Jeans lengths and thus a higher transverse coherence.

z	$\langle D \rangle$	observed T_0 [K]	observed α	fiducial T_0 [K]	fiducial α	H4 T_0 [K]	H4 α	$\Delta\theta$ at $100 h^{-1}$ kpc
4.0	0.525 ± 0.012	17400 ± 3900	0.43 ± 0.45	11700	0.54	28200	0.55	3.9''
3.0	0.316 ± 0.023	18300 ± 1800 or 18400 ± 2100	0.33 ± 0.26 0.29 ± 0.30	11000	0.57	25000	0.57	4.4''
2.4	0.182 ± 0.021	17400 ± 1900 or 19200 ± 2000	0.52 ± 0.14 0.51 ± 0.14	10000	0.56	23000	0.57	4.9''
2.0	0.144 ± 0.024	17700	0.32 ± 0.30	8913	0.56	21380	0.57	5.4''

Note. — Observed mean flux decrements $\langle D \rangle \equiv \langle 1 - e^{-\tau} \rangle$ at $z = 2.4, 3$, and 4 are from McDonald et al. (2000); the $z = 2$ measurement is from Faucher-Giguère et al. (2008) without correcting for metal absorption. The observed temperature-density relations ($T = T_0[1 + \delta]^\alpha$) at $z = 2.4, 3$, and 4 are from McDonald et al. (2001), with the $z \sim 2$ measurement from Ricotti et al. (2000).

Table 4.1. Mean flux decrements and temperature-density relations

CHAPTER 5

MODELING A TWO-PHASE MEDIUM IN SPH

5.1. INTRODUCTION

Two-temperature media are common in the context of galaxy formation and evolution. Cold gas is observed flowing out of galaxies that should have hot gaseous halos (e.g., Martin 2005). Conversely, simulations have recently indicated that gas can accrete onto lower-mass halos without shock-heating first (Kereš et al. 2005, 2009). Likewise, satellites falling into larger halos can have their gas stripped as they orbit in the potential well. On smaller scales, cold clouds that eventually become sites for star formation may form from thermal instability in the interstellar medium. While state-of-the-art cosmological or galaxy-scale hydrodynamic simulations may be able to fully resolve some of these examples, in many others they cannot. Therefore while it is crucial that simulations correctly follow the orbit of cold gas clumps in hot background, we must also question how well simulations handle discontinuous thermal structures at low resolution. As a first step, in this Chapter, we investigate the simple case of hydrostatic equilibrium of a cold spherical blob in a hot ambient

medium as modeled in smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) codes with two formulations of the equation of motion.

The treatment of cold gas orbiting in hot halos in cosmological simulations can have profound impacts on statistics as basic as the galaxy stellar mass function (Oppenheimer et al. 2009). A long-standing problem in galaxy evolution is the “over cooling” of gas in galaxies leading to the over-production of stars in halos at all masses. Star formation feedback that either heats or expels gas from galaxies is the prime suspect for reducing the efficiency of star formation at low masses. Simulations, however, cannot currently achieve the required number of particles to directly resolve the underlying physical processes in generating a galaxy-scale outflow. Recipes have therefore been developed to try to capture this “sub-grid” physics. A popular such feedback recipe in Gadget-2 (Springel 2005) is to have gas particles that are eligible for star formation (i.e., particles with densities $> \rho_{\text{SF, thresh}}$) also have some probability that they will instead be ejected from the galaxy as a “wind” particle. In order for this process to actually drive an outflow and to obtain numerically convergent results, wind particles must temporarily not be allowed to interact hydrodynamically with their surroundings. Though turning hydrodynamics “off” is somewhat physically motivated by a multiphase ISM that cannot be directly modeled at the current simulation resolutions, the ejected particle still represents a single fluid element in this treatment (Springel & Hernquist 2003). However, since gas properties in the SPH formalism are calculated by averaging over a finite

number of $\gg 1$ particles, it is unclear whether or not moving individual particles is numerically treated by the simulation in the way that accurately represents the physics on which this recipe was based. Furthermore, because the particles are hydrodynamically de-coupled from their surroundings, they are still cold ($T \sim 10^4$ K) once hydrodynamics is turned back on for them; thus their subsequent evolution in the galaxy's hot ($T \sim 10^6$ – 10^7 K) halo is an extreme low-resolution case of the treatment of a two-phase medium in SPH. This is especially disconcerting as Oppenheimer et al. (2009) has found that a large fraction late-time star formation in low-mass halos is from gas that was previously ejected as winds; since winds are metal-enriched therefore cool faster than primordial accreted gas, this re-accreted gas is extremely efficient at forming stars and therefore has a significant impact on the morphology of the galaxy mass function. It is, however, unclear to what extent this behavior is physical or simply a side-effect of how star formation feedback is modeled in SPH. It is with these low-resolution cases in mind that we set up our idealized test simulations.

There is an extensive literature on the successes and shortcomings of SPH codes, usually in the context of handling fluid mixing and thermal instabilities as compared to Eulerian grid-based codes. A recurring theme is that SPH cannot correctly treat Kelvin-Helmholtz or Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities because of the sharp density discontinuities involved (e.g., Agertz et al. 2007; Read et al. 2009); a gap on the order of the smoothing length will form at the boundary (Ritchie & Thomas

2001; Okamoto et al. 2003). At face-value this is expected since SPH calculates densities—and thus pressure gradients, etc.—by averaging over a given number of neighboring particles. Thus a truly discontinuous density change can never be fully resolved in SPH. Moreover, this “feature” can have drastic implications for overcooling of cold gas (and thus star formation) in galaxies (Pearce et al. 1999; Tittley et al. 2001; Marri & White 2003).

We evolve idealized initial conditions consisting of a cold blob in a hot ambient medium with two formulations of the equation of motion in SPH; specifically, as outlined in §5.2, we use the publicly available¹ Gadget-2.0.4 (Springel 2005) and the modified “rpSPH” version suggested by Abel (2010). In §5.3 we describe the hydrostatic case, with our fiducial initial conditions outlined in §5.3.1 and variations in resolution, initial pressure difference, and blob size described in §5.3.2–5.3.4. Finally, we discuss the ways in which rpSPH is an improvement and the ways in which it fails in §5.3.5. All simulations are purely adiabatic with no gravity.

5.2. THE MOMENTUM EQUATION AND RPSPH

The goal of SPH codes is to solve the Navier-Stokes equations by discretizing the fluid into “particles” (Lucy 1977; Gingold & Monaghan 1977). Of these equations, the momentum equation is most important for understanding question of

¹<http://www.mpa-garching.mpg.de/gadget/>

hydrostatic equilibrium since it's the one that cares about pressure gradients. In the absence of gravity and viscosity,

$$\frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = -\frac{\vec{\nabla}P}{\rho}, \quad (5.1)$$

where \vec{v} is the fluid velocity, P is the pressure, and ρ is the density; because SPH is inherently Lagrangian, we are working in a frame that moves with the fluid. There are two ways to discretize equation (5.1): either directly calculate the pressure gradient $\vec{\nabla}P$ between each pair of particles, or instead appeal to the chain rule and note that $(\vec{\nabla}P)/\rho = \vec{\nabla}(P/\rho) + (P/\rho^2)\vec{\nabla}\rho$ (Monaghan 1992). Most SPH formalisms use the second, symmetrized, version (see also Hernquist & Katz 1989); in Gadget-2, the momentum equation is expressed as

$$\frac{d\vec{v}_i}{dt} = -\sum_{j=1}^N m_j \left[f_i \frac{P_i}{\rho_i^2} \nabla_i W_{ij}(h_i) + f_j \frac{P_j}{\rho_j^2} \nabla_i W_{ij}(h_j) \right], \quad (5.2)$$

where W is the kernel function and h_i is the smoothing length for particle i with $W_{ij}(h) = W(|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|, h)$ (Springel & Hernquist 2002). The f_i terms describe the change in density with smoothing length, i.e.,

$$f_i = \left[1 + \frac{h_i}{3\rho_i} \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial h_i} \right]^{-1}. \quad (5.3)$$

While formally the summation in equation (5.2) is over all N particles in the simulation, since $W_{ij} = 0$ for $|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j| > h$, the only relevant particles are the N_{ngb} neighbor particles.

Abel (2010) points out that equation (5.2) is somewhat unsavory: if two particles i and j have exactly equal pressures $P_i = P_j$ but are at different densities $\rho_i \neq \rho_j$, then there will be a force repelling the two particles. He suggests that instead the equation of motion should read

$$\frac{d\vec{v}_i}{dt} = - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \left[\frac{P_j - P_i}{\rho_j^2} \nabla_i W_{ij}(h_i) \right], \quad (5.4)$$

which is close to a direct discretization of equation (5.1). Equation (5.4), however, is asymmetric; it therefore does not conserve momentum. Abel claims that this formulation is more robust with respect to Gadget-2’s leapfrog time integration scheme than the symmetrized version proposed by Morris (1996), where

$$\frac{d\vec{v}_i}{dt} = - \sum_{j=1}^N m_j \left[\frac{P_j - P_i}{\rho_i \rho_j} \nabla_i W_{ij}(h_i) \right]. \quad (5.5)$$

In comparison to the native Gadget-2 formulation, we therefore adopt Abel’s “relative pressure SPH” (rpSPH) scheme rather than the Morris one. Abel suggests two possible modifications to Gadget-2; we have tested both versions and only discuss here the one that we found to be more robust in all cases.

5.3. HYDROSTATIC EQUILIBRIUM

5.3.1. FIDUCIAL INITIAL CONDITIONS

Our fiducial initial conditions are for a 10^4 K spherical blob embedded in a 10^6 K ambient medium with densities set so that $(\rho T)_{\text{amb},i} = (\rho T)_{\text{blob},i}$. (Technically, we should set $(\rho T/\mu)_{\text{amb},i} = (\rho T/\mu)_{\text{blob},i}$, where μ is the mean molecular weight, but since all of our simulations are purely adiabatic, μ is equal everywhere and at all times.) The blob is comprised of $N_{\text{blob}} = 17255$ particles and has an initial radius of $R_{\text{blob}} = 7$ kpc; this setup has 12.8 typical blob particle smoothing lengths and 2.8 typical ambient particle smoothing lengths across the diameter of the blob. We take $N_{\text{ngb}} = 33 \pm 2$ and evolve the initial conditions with Gadget-2.0.4.

We choose to sample the underlying density distribution by gridding the background and placing particles randomly within each grid cell. As shown in Figure 5.1, this method gives a tighter initial density distribution than Poisson initial conditions, but is noisier than if the particles are placed at the grid cell centers. A gridded background, however, leads to the undesired side effect of spherical blobs becoming somewhat cubical due to interactions with the background medium. Regardless, we find that the mean behaviors discussed here are insensitive to the initial sampling method of the underlying density distribution.

This setup leads to a density discontinuity that is not necessarily what would arise naturally in an astrophysical simulation, even in the “high-resolution” case of a single cold particle in a hot halo. However, the tests on this setup will still be instructive for constructing and analyzing future simulations.

Figure 5.2 shows how pressure (ρT) varies with time for this fiducial case. There are two immediately obvious features: first, the blob develops large-scale oscillations. Second, at late times, the blob is over-pressured relative to the ambient medium. Furthermore, at large blob radii, there is a steep pressure gradient, yet the blob does not expand. Outside of the blob, there is a gap, a thin shell, and then a smaller gap of ambient particles; the large gap is on the order of the typical h_{sml} of the ambient particles, as has been found in previous studies (e.g., Agertz et al. 2007). We find this late-time qualitative behavior for a range of resolutions and initial density and pressure ratios, though there are quantitative variations.

5.3.2. DEPENDENCE ON RESOLUTION: N_{blob}

Our fiducial blob is well-resolved, but settles to a steady-state in which it is over-pressured relative to its surroundings. In astrophysical applications, however, many fewer particles would be used to “resolve” such a cold cloud. We therefore investigate here how the evolution of the blob’s pressure structure depends on N_{blob} . Figure 5.3 shows $\log(\rho T)$ as a function of radius for $N_{\text{blob}} \sim 128$ to $N_{\text{blob}} \sim 32000$. In

Figure 5.4, we quantify the pressure difference $\Delta \log(\rho T) = \log(\rho T)_{\text{blob}} - \log(\rho T)_{\text{amb}}$ as a function of time for these six N_{blob} . We define the “blob” as particles with $T < 0.9T_{\text{amb},i}$ and $\rho > 5\rho_{a,i}$; the blob pressure is then taken to be the mean ρT for all particles with $r < 0.5 \max(\text{radius of all blob particles})$. (Agertz et al. 2007 use a threshold density that depends on the initial blob density; we do not because we would like to study cases in which the initial blob density is far from equilibrium.) The ambient ρT is the mean ρT for all particles that were initially in the ambient medium whose distance to the center of the blob is more than $R_{\text{blob}} + \min(\text{distance to blob center for closest ambient particle})$; this is to avoid the gap and shell around the blob seen in the previous figures.

Less-well resolved blobs become more over-pressured than ones with higher N_{blob} , with the $N_{\text{blob}} = 135$ case settling to a pressure 0.6 dex above the ambient medium. While larger N_{blob} does lead to less over-pressured blobs, this is a case of diminishing returns: the highest-resolution, $N_{\text{blob}} = 33551$, case has only marginally smaller $\Delta \log(\rho T)$ than the fiducial case which has N_{blob} that is twice as small. Furthermore, the blob oscillations take longer to damp out at higher N_{blob} , and while to first order the oscillation period is set by the blob sound-crossing time, it is longer at higher resolutions. After nearly 20 sound-crossing times (not plotted), the higher resolution blobs have still not settled to a steady-state.

5.3.3. DEPENDENCE ON INITIAL OVER/UNDER-PRESSURE

Figure 5.5 shows how $\Delta \log(\rho T)$ depends on the initial pressure differential. In addition to the fiducial $(\rho T)_{\text{blob},i} = (\rho T)_{\text{amb},i}$ case, we also consider an over-pressured $\rho_{\text{blob},i} = 10\rho_{\text{blob},eq}$ and an under-pressured $\rho_{\text{blob},i} = 0.1\rho_{\text{blob},eq}$ case; the initial blob and ambient temperatures are always the same as in the fiducial case. In all cases the final solution is that of an over-pressured blob, but the asymptotic $\Delta \log(\rho T)$ depends on the initial conditions, with the initially under-pressured blob reaching smaller $\Delta \log(\rho T)$ than the initially over-pressured blob. The oscillation amplitude for the fiducial blob is smaller than in either of the two other cases.

5.3.4. DEPENDENCE ON BLOB RADIUS: SURFACE TENSION

To test the hypothesis of numerical surface tension driving the blob over-pressure, we consider in Figure 5.6 the dependence of $\Delta \log(\rho T)$ on R_{blob} . While ΔP does increase with decreasing blob size, the scaling does not imply a constant surface tension (i.e., $\Delta P \not\propto R_{\text{blob}}^{-1}$).

5.3.5. SUCCESSES AND FAILURES OF rpSPH

We turn now to the fiducial case evolved with rpSPH. We find that in order for the code to not crash, more neighbors are needed. (Abel 2010 used $N_{\text{ngb}} = 128$.) We

find that, if evolved for long enough, rpSPH always crashes, even with $N_{\text{ngb}} = 128$. Figure 5.7 shows temperature-coded snapshots at $t = 4$ in Gadget-2 and rpSPH for $N_{\text{ngb}} = 33$ and 128. In rpSPH, the blob dissipates, the entire box heats up, and the blob obtains a net momentum.

Nonetheless, in Figure 5.8 shows $\Delta \log(\rho T)$ as a function of time for the fiducial case evolved with Gadget-2 and rpSPH and $N_{\text{ngb}} = 33, 64,$ and 128. The larger N_{ngb} is, the less well resolved the blob and density discontinuity are, and therefore the more over-pressured the final state is. For the $N_{\text{ngb}} = 128$ case, rpSPH is able to evolve the code further than the line drawn, but the blob has disintegrated fully by this point (i.e., no particles in the box match the density and temperature criteria listed above). Even for $N_{\text{ngb}} = 256$ (not plotted), the blob evaporates. Numerical surface tension is clearly not a problem in rpSPH.

The lack of momentum conservation in rpSPH is related to why the code crashes at late times. The box achieves a large net momentum, and the average temperature increases significantly. Shortly before crashing, there are numerous particles with $T \gg 10^{10}$ K. This happens even if a uniform density, constant temperature static medium is evolved with $N_{\text{ngb}} = 256$. Figure 5.10 shows the “final” temperature distributions in Gadget-2 and rpSPH for three choices of N_{ngb} ; the rpSPH outputs are the last ones before the code crashes. Even though all of the particles start at $T = 10^6$ K, they have heated significantly. The final x -component of the particle

velocities are shown in Figure 5.11; when the rpSPH crashes, the typical particle velocity is slightly greater than the sound speed of the medium.

Fig. 5.1.— Fiducial initial conditions with density sampled with Poisson, random-in-cells, and grid at $t = 0$ (*top*) and $t \sim 1$ Gyr (*bottom*). In this and subsequent figures, the shaded regions correspond to the 1- and 2- σ dispersions in moving bins of r ; blob particles are shown in red and ambient particles are shown in grey.

Fig. 5.2.— Example time sequence of the fiducial case evolved with Gadget-2.

Fig. 5.3.— Resolution test: vary N_{blob} at fixed $R_{\text{blob}} \sim 6.9$ kpc and $N_{\text{ngb}} = 33 \pm 2$ at $t = 5t_{\text{cross}}$. Errorbars show smoothing lengths.

Fig. 5.4.— Difference in pressure of the blob and ambient medium as a function of time and N_{blob} .

Fig. 5.5.— Difference in pressure of the blob and ambient medium as a function of time and $(\rho T)_i/(\rho T)_{\text{eq}}$.

Fig. 5.6.— Difference in pressure of the blob and ambient medium as a function of time, $R_{\text{blob},i}$, and $\rho_{\text{blob}}/\rho_{\text{amb}}$ for Gadget-2 and rpSPH.

Fig. 5.7.— Snapshots at $t = 4$ in Gadget-2 (*left*) and rpSPH (*right*) with $N_{\text{ngb}} = 33$ (*top*) and 128 (*bottom*), with colors corresponding to $\log T = 3$ (blue) to 7 (white).

Fig. 5.8.— Difference in pressure of the blob and ambient medium as a function of time and N_{ngb} for Gadget-2 and rpSPH.

Fig. 5.9.— the blob in rpSPH disintegrates before the code crashes. in Gadget2, the blob mass remains constant. Interestingly, the mass loss for the $N_{\text{ngb}} = 33$ and 64 particle cases trace each other until the 33 particle one crashes, but not so for 128 neighbors. Right panel is for $N_{\text{ngb}} = 64 \pm 2$ for all cases.

Fig. 5.10.— Distribution of temperatures at late times in Gadget-2 and rpSPH. All particles start at 10^6 K; the rpSPH histograms correspond to the last outputs before the code crashes. The lower N_{ngb} rpSPH simulations have smaller mean temperatures at “late times” because they crash sooner than the higher N_{ngb} ones, and thus have less time to heat.

Fig. 5.11.— Distribution of temperatures at late times in Gadget-2 and rpSPH. All particles start with $v = 0$; the rpSPH histograms correspond to the last outputs before the code crashes. The lower N_{ngb} rpSPH simulations have more peaked v_x distributions at “late times” because they crash sooner than the higher N_{ngb} ones, and thus have less time to gain momentum.

APPENDIX A

THE NUCLEOSYNTHETIC YIELD AND INSTANTANEOUS RECYCLED FRACTION

As shown in Equation (3.18), the nucleosynthetic yield is

$$y = \frac{\dot{M}_{\text{new metals}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{recy}}} \frac{\dot{M}_{\text{recy}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}} = \frac{\dot{M}_{\text{new metals}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $\dot{M}_{\text{new metals}}$ is the rate of metal (i.e., oxygen) production from Type II supernovae and \dot{M}_{SFR} is the current star formation rate. Though \dot{M}_{recy} depends on the star formation history (i.e., the number of old stars), the yield only depends on the star formation history over the previous $\sim 10^7$ years, i.e., the lifetime of stars that produce oxygen. We show in Figure A.1 how y varies in time for different choices of star formation history, IMF, and metallicity based on the “B” series Type II supernovae yields from Woosley & Weaver (1995). The Chabrier (2003b) IMF is shown in red and blue, and the Kroupa (2001) IMF is shown in orange and green; both are integrated from 0.08 to $100M_{\odot}$. We apply the Woosley & Weaver supernova yields to bins of stellar mass that match at the midpoints between the model masses; we extrapolate the $40M_{\odot}$ models to $100M_{\odot}$. The effects of metallicity ($Z = Z_{\odot}$, red

and orange; $Z = 0.1Z_{\odot}$, blue and green) are subdominant to the effects of the IMF. Different line types represent different star formation rates as a function of time, as denoted in the top-left panel. We take stellar lifetimes to be the main sequence lifetime, $\tau_{\text{MS}} = \tau_{\odot}(m/M_{\odot})^{-\beta} = (10^{10} \text{ yr})(m/M_{\odot})^{-2.5}$, where m is the mass of the star. At the end of its lifetime, a star returns a gas mass of $m - m_{\text{remnant}}$ to the ISM, where $m_{\text{remnant}} = m_{\text{ns}} = 2.0M_{\odot}$ for $8 > m > 11M_{\odot}$ and $m_{\text{remnant}} = m_{\text{wd}} = 0.6M_{\odot}$ for $m < 8M_{\odot}$; for stars more massive than $11M_{\odot}$, we take the ejected mass to be that calculated by Woosley & Weaver (1995). All recycled mass is taken to be from stars that have been formed since $t = 0$, i.e., we assume that there are no stars at $t = 0$ that will eject mass into the ISM. This analysis implicitly assumes that all gas is well-mixed at all times. The sharp features in the top-right and the bottom two panels are due to our simple stellar evolution model. The feature at $\sim 10^6$ yr arises from the lifetime of $40M_{\odot}$ stars; stars with $m > 40M_{\odot}$ are assumed to have the same yields as $40M_{\odot}$ stars. The feature at $\sim 2.5 \times 10^7$ yr is caused by the lifetime of $11M_{\odot}$ stars: stars with $m < 11M_{\odot}$ are assumed to not explode as Type II supernovae and thus not produce oxygen. (Also, $m = 11M_{\odot}$ is the mass boundary where the remnant mass is taken to be m_{ns} instead of being calculated by Woosley & Weaver.)

The top-right panel of Figure A.1 shows the instantaneous (oxygen) metallicity of ejected gas, Z_{ej} ; this decreases with time because stars with $m < 11M_{\odot}$ do not produce oxygen but still recycle gas to the ISM. The decrease in Z_{ej} before 2.5×10^7 yr reflects the fact higher mass stars produce relatively more oxygen

than low-mass stars. We take $Z_{\text{ej,max}} = 0.15$, though considering the contribution of all Type II supernovae, $Z_{\text{ej,max}}$ could plausibly be in the range 0.1–0.2. The instantaneous recycled gas fraction, f_{recy} , is plotted in the bottom-left panel. Though f_{recy} varies continuously with time, its change is slight, and depends strongly on the IMF, slightly on the star formation history, and negligibly on the metallicity. We therefore take $f_{\text{recy}} = 0.2$ in our models; varying this between 0.1 and 0.4 has a negligible impact on our results, especially compared to the theoretical uncertainties in $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ and the nucleosynthetic yield. The nucleosynthetic yield, y , is shown in the bottom-right panel of Figure A.1. The strong variations with time seen with both Z_{ej} and f_{recy} are largely gone due to the cancellation of \dot{M}_{ejecta} . Since the production of oxygen only lags the star formation rate by $\lesssim 2.5 \times 10^7$ yr, the yield is effectively constant after the initial generation of Type II supernovae explode; if the star formation rate varies strongly over this timescale (e.g., the dotted and short-dashed lines), then a slight deviation in y can be seen. However, even in these extreme circumstances, the dependence on y for $t \gtrsim 2.5 \times 10^7$ yr is small compared to the uncertainties from the IMF. On the other hand, if the star formation history is extremely bursty (e.g., varying by several orders of magnitude) on the scales of 10 Myr (not plotted for clarity), then the instantaneous $\dot{M}_{\text{new oxygen}}$ and \dot{M}_{SFR} will *not* closely track one another; a galaxy with such a pathological star formation history could develop an observed Z_{g} that is much higher than what is generically understood to be the nucleosynthetic yield.

In a similar calculation, Finlator & Davé (2008) let both the IMF (Salpeter 1955 and Chabrier 2003b) and the Type II supernova yields (Woosley & Weaver 1995; Chieffi & Limongi 2004; Portinari et al. 1998) vary; they found that uncertainties in the models allow for $0.008 < y < 0.021$. We adopt $y = 0.015$, which is in the middle of the range given by Finlator & Davé. This yield is somewhat lower than found for Woosley & Weaver models for the Chabrier IMF (our adopted IMF), but we find that larger values of y are more difficult to reconcile with the observed gas fractions (§3.4).

The nucleosynthetic yield y is more commonly seen expressed in terms of a “closed box” model (Searle & Sargent 1972; Matteucci 2002; Tremonti et al. 2004; Dalcanton 2007). In the closed box model, the total mass of the system, $M_{\text{tot}} = M_{\text{g}} + M_{\text{*}}$, is a constant; thus, the gas fraction decreases as the stellar mass increases. If instantaneous recycling is also assumed, then as the gas fraction decreases, the metallicity increases according to

$$Z_{\text{g}} = y \ln(1/\mu_{\text{g}}), \tag{A.2}$$

which to first order and for large F_{g} , is equivalent to equation (3.27) with $\zeta_{\text{w}} = \zeta_{\text{a}} = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$.

Finally, we note that the maximum Z_{g} reached for the Kewley & Ellison mass-metallicity relations (Figure 3.1) ranges from 0.002 to 0.012. A comparison

between $\max(Z_g)$ and y might be able to set interesting constraints on either the nucleosynthetic yield y (specifically, the Type II supernova yields, modulo the IMF) or on the overall normalization of the mass-metallicity relation as given by different $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$ indicators (see §3.2.1). This implies that, e.g., the Tremonti et al. (2004) mass-metallicity relation is inconsistent with models for which $y < 0.012$. More generally, a generic massive galaxy with a low gas fraction and a deep potential well (and thus plausibly ineffective winds) is expected to have a metallicity Z_g that approaches y ; if by $z = 0$ this is indeed generically the case, then such an analysis would favor smaller values of y and higher normalizations of $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H})$.

Fig. A.1.— Nucleosynthetic yields y (bottom-right), Z_{ej} (top-right), and instantaneous recycled fractions f_{recy} (bottom-left) as a function of time for different star formation histories (line type, upper-left panel), IMFs (Chabrier 2003a,b, red and blue; Kroupa 2001, orange and green), and metallicities (blue and green, $Z = 0.1Z_{\odot}$; red and orange, $Z = Z_{\odot}$).

APPENDIX B

OUTFLOWS, INFLOWS, AND STAR FORMATION: GETTING THE GAS MASSES

As shown in §3.3.1,

$$\dot{M}_g = \dot{M}_{\text{acc}} - \dot{M}_{\text{SFR}} + \dot{M}_{\text{recy}} - \dot{M}_w \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$= \dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}(\eta_a - 1 + f_{\text{recy}} - \eta_w), \quad (\text{B.2})$$

and

$$\frac{dM_g}{dM_\star} = \frac{\eta_a - \eta_w - 1 + f_{\text{recy}}}{1 - f_{\text{recy}}} = F_g(1 - \gamma). \quad (\text{B.3})$$

In §3.4 we assumed an F_g - M_\star relation existed and that as galaxies evolve they remain on such a relation. Here we consider, for a given η_w , what implications such a relation has on the gas accretion rate and how efficiently galaxies are able to turn this accreted gas into stars. The above equations imply that the gas inflow and outflow rates must be balanced by

$$\eta_a - \eta_w = (1 - f_{\text{recy}})F_g(1 - \gamma) - f_{\text{recy}} + 1. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Thus, for a given combination of η_w and F_g , we can uniquely determine $\eta_a \equiv \dot{M}_{\text{acc}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$, i.e., the efficiency with which a galaxy turns its accreted gas into stars. For example, if the star formation rate is higher than the accretion rate ($\log \eta_a < 0$), then the galaxy is forming stars more quickly than it is accreting gas, i.e. it is very efficient at forming stars. We plot $\log \eta_a$ for the no wind, $\eta_w = [70 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}}$, and $\eta_w = ([70 \text{ km s}^{-1}]/v_{\text{vir}})^2$ cases as a function of stellar mass in the upper-left panel of Figure B.1 for the total gas fraction relation (see Table 3.3 and Figure 3.2). Strikingly, η_a always decreases significantly with increasing mass—even in the absence of winds (solid blue line). This behavior follows directly from the steepness of the gas fraction relation (equation B.4). When outflows that preferentially remove gas from low-mass galaxies ($\eta_w \propto v_{\text{vir}}^{-1}$, green dashed line; v_{vir}^{-2} , red dotted line) are taken into account, η_a likewise increases and steepens to compensate. Therefore, while winds may affect how star-formation efficiency varies as a function of galaxy mass, they are not necessary to explain the trend, implying that additional physics is at play.

This analysis does not entirely reveal what drives the η_a - M_* relation. However, the nature of η_a can be unraveled by appealing to \dot{M}_{SFR} and \dot{M}_{acc} from independent sources. For example, as shown in Figure B.2, the median specific star formation rate (SSFR, \dot{M}_{SFR}/M_*) in SDSS DR4 star-forming galaxies decreases with increasing M_* , though there is large scatter in the SSFR at fixed M_* . We consider here three

scalings for how the SSFR may vary with M_* . The median SSFR of SDSS DR4 star-forming galaxies can be fit with a power law

$$\text{med}(\log[\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}/M_*]) \approx -9.83 - 0.12(\log[M_*/M_\odot] - 10), \quad (\text{B.5})$$

as shown as a histogram in the right panel of Figure 2.13 and the black solid line in Figure B.2. A physically-motivated way to have the SSFR to decrease with mass is to postulate that it is proportional to the total gas fraction, μ_g . The blue dashed line shows $\mu_g \times 4 \times 10^{-10}$ yr for the total gas fractions, while the purple dashed line shows $\mu_g \times 1 \times 10^{-9}$ yr for the SDSS gas fractions (note that the SDSS gas fractions were derived largely from these same \dot{M}_{SFR} and thus this is a somewhat degenerate comparison). Finally, we consider a constant SSFR, $\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}/M_* = 2 \times 10^{-10}$ yr ($\log[\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}/M_*] = -9.7$ in Figure B.2).

Using extended Press-Schechter theory, Neistein et al. (2006) parameterize the baryonic accretion rate onto halos by

$$\dot{M}_{\text{acc, tot}} = 7.23 \left(\frac{M_{\text{halo}}}{10^{12} M_\odot} \right)^{1.15} \left(\frac{f_b}{0.181} \right) (1+z)^{2.25} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}, \quad (\text{B.6})$$

where $f_b \equiv \Omega_b/\Omega_m$. Genel et al. (2008) find a similar accretion rate of dark matter onto halos in the Millineum Simulation, which implies a baryonic accretion rate of

$$\dot{M}_{\text{acc, tot}} = 6.34 \left(\frac{M_{\text{halo}}}{10^{12} M_\odot} \right)^{1.07} \left(\frac{f_b}{0.181} \right) (1+z)^{2.2} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

These accretion rates are for matter being accreted into the *halo*, not the galaxy, and can be safely considered as upper limits to \dot{M}_{acc} .

The range of $\dot{M}_{\text{acc,tot}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$ allowed between these two \dot{M}_{acc} models and three SSFRs (constant, solid; $\propto \mu_{\text{g}}$, dashed; SDSS median, dotted) are plotted in the top-right panel of Figure B.1. At low stellar masses, $M_{\star} \propto M_{\text{halo}}^{0.5}$ (equation 3.31 and Figure 3.3), which when combined with the nearly linear mass-dependence of the accretion rate with halo mass, provides $\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}} \sim M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\star} \sim M_{\star}^{-0.5}$, which is the approximate trend found at $M_{\star} \lesssim 10^{10}M_{\odot}$. Equations (B.6) and (B.7) state that the overall “efficiency” of mass accretion $\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}/M_{\text{halo}}$ is roughly constant with halo mass. Therefore, although the host halos of lower mass galaxies accrete a proportionally equal baryon mass, they are less capable at converting this gas into stars. At high masses, however, the opposite is true: galaxies become more efficient at converting accreted gas into stars. For $M_{\star} \gtrsim 10^{10}M_{\odot}$, $M_{\star} \propto M_{\text{halo}}^{0.5}$ (equation 3.31), implying $\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}} \sim M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\star} \sim M_{\star}$, which is close to the observed $\eta_{\text{a}}-M_{\star}$ slope at high masses. This combined double mass-dependent behaviour of η_{a} with stellar mass produces the characteristic “U” shape observed in Figure B.1.

The Neistein et al. and Genel et al. estimates of $\dot{M}_{\text{acc,tot}}$ are for baryonic accretion into the halo. However, only a fraction of this infalling gas may be usable for star formation; for example, if this onfalling gas is shock-heated as it is accreted, then it will neither be detected in H I+H₂ observations nor contribute towards star formation (since we are sensitive to η_{a} rather than $\dot{M}_{\text{acc,tot}}$ proper, the gas

participating in star formation is relevant). Therefore, to better characterize the fraction of gas that is accreted “cold”—and therefore able to further cool and form stars—we combine the estimates of \dot{M}_{acc} , \dot{M}_{SFR} , and η_{a} , defining this cold fraction as

$$f_{\text{cold}} \equiv \eta_{\text{a}} \frac{\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}}{\dot{M}_{\text{acc, tot}}}, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

where $\dot{M}_{\text{acc, tot}}$ and \dot{M}_{SFR} are generally defined. For illustrative purposes, we let $\dot{M}_{\text{acc, tot}}$ be defined as in equations (B.6) and (B.7). Note that to be physical, $0 \leq f_{\text{cold}} \leq 1$. The lower-left panel of Figure B.1 shows how f_{cold} varies with different η_{w} scalings, assuming the median SDSS SSFRs, while the lower-right panel shows how f_{cold} depends on the SSFR in the absence of winds.

There are several interesting behaviors in the lower panels of Figure B.1 worth noting. First, the morphology of $f_{\text{cold}}(M_{\star})$ is fairly robust against variations in the SSFR and η_{w} : it is roughly constant, perhaps with a slight rise, for $\log M_{\star} \lesssim 10.5$, i.e., below about M^* , and then drops precipitously at higher masses. Physically, this is a restatement of galaxies with masses near M^* being more efficient at turning gas accreted by their halos into stars, relative to either more or less massive galaxies (Shankar et al. 2006; Guo et al. 2009).

Second, $f_{\text{cold}}(M_{\star}) \sim 1$ for low-mass galaxies. At face value, this would imply that all the accreting gas is available for star formation. This closely resembles so-called “cold-mode” accretion scenario in which gas falling into lower mass

halos along filaments do not experience significant shock-heating, thereby easily accreting onto the central galaxy (Dekel & Birnboim 2006; Kereš et al. 2005, 2009; Dutton et al. 2010b). At higher masses, on the other hand, accreting gas may be shock-heated and subsequently unable to cool and contribute to star formation. Despite this neat picture, however, we find it intriguing that $f_{\text{cold}}(M_{\star})$ is so close to unity at low masses. Figure 3.2 clearly shows that $M_{\star} + M_{\text{g}}$ in these same galaxies falls short of accounting for all of the baryons in the halo by at least a factor of two. Thus, a large part of the accreted baryons must be removed from the halo via strong winds, even if the star formation is reasonably inefficient in these galaxies, possibly induced by a particularly strong supernova feedback efficiency.

Finally, Figure B.3 builds on this analysis to show the star formation efficiency, traditionally-defined as $\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}/M_{\text{g}}$, as a function of stellar mass for the total cold gas fractions and the three choices of SSFR. In all cases, star formation is more efficient in more massive galaxies: they are forming more stars per unit gas (though see Schiminovich et al. 2010). Several previous analyses of the mass-metallicity relation have suggested that a varying star formation efficiency with galaxy mass is required in order to reproduce the mass-metallicity relation (e.g., Brooks et al. 2007; Calura et al. 2009). Figure B.3 shows that this condition is implicitly passed as long as gas fractions are decreasing with galaxy mass and star formation rates vary reasonably with stellar mass, as is observed for $z = 0$ galaxies. We note, however,

that with proper choices of ζ_w , the mass-metallicity relation is *theoretically* able to be reproduced with a constant F_g and therefore constant star formation efficiency.

Fig. B.1.— Gas accretion rates, star formation rates, and cold gas accretion fractions as a function of stellar mass with varying outflows and specific star formation rates. All panels assume the total cold gas fractions described in § 3.2.2. Panel (a) shows how η_a varies according to equation (B.4) for different η_w models: no wind (solid blue), a momentum-driven scaling (green dashed), and an energy-driven scaling (red dotted). In all cases, high mass galaxies accrete less gas per unit star formation than less massive galaxies. Panel (b) shows the expected range in $\dot{M}_{\text{acc,tot}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$ between the Neistein et al. (2006) and Genel et al. (2008) \dot{M}_{acc} models (shaded regions) and with three scalings of \dot{M}_{SFR}/M_* with stellar mass: constant (blue), $\propto \mu_g$ (green), and the median values from SDSS (red). These $\dot{M}_{\text{acc,tot}}/\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}$ are qualitatively similar at low masses to the η_a shown in panel (a), but increase rapidly at high masses. Panels (c) and (d) show the ratio f_{cold} of these two estimates, with varying η_w and the SDSS SSFRs and with varying the SSFR and no winds, respectively.

Fig. B.2.— Specific star formation rates. The shaded regions 1- and 2- σ dispersions in running bins of $\log M_*$ of the aperture-corrected specific star formation rates from SDSS (Brinchmann et al. 2004); the black solid line is a power-law fit to median (equation B.5). The purple dashed is the SDSS $\mu_g \times 1 \times 10^{-9}$ yr and blue dashed line is the total $\mu_g \times 4 \times 10^{-10}$ yr; these offsets imply a star formation timescale of 1–2.5 Gyr. The shaded regions are dotted lines are constant \dot{M}_{SFR} .

Fig. B.3.— Star formation efficiency $\dot{M}_{\text{SFR}}/M_{\text{g}}$ as a function of M_{\star} , taking M_{g} to be the total cold gas masses (thick lines, §3.2.2) and $M_{\text{g}} = 0.5M_{\star}$ (thin lines) and three choices of the specific star formation rate: constant (solid blue lines), $\propto \mu_{\text{g}}$ (dashed green lines), and the median values from SDSS (dotted red lines). In all cases, a steeply decreasing $F_{\text{g}} - M_{\star}$ relation is required for the star formation efficiency to increase with stellar mass.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Abel, T. 2010, ArXiv e-prints

Adelman-McCarthy, J. K., Agüeros, M. A., Allam, S. S., Allende Prieto, C., Anderson, K. S. J., Anderson, S. F., Annis, J., Bahcall, N. A., Bailer-Jones, C. A. L., Baldry, I. K., Barentine, J. C., Bassett, B. A., Becker, A. C., Beers, T. C., Bell, E. F., Berlind, A. A., Bernardi, M., Blanton, M. R., Bochanski, J. J., Boroski, W. N., Brinchmann, J., Brinkmann, J., Brunner, R. J., Budavári, T., Carliles, S., Carr, M. A., Castander, F. J., Cinabro, D., Cool, R. J., Covey, K. R., Csabai, I., Cunha, C. E., Davenport, J. R. A., Dilday, B., Doi, M., Eisenstein, D. J., Evans, M. L., Fan, X., Finkbeiner, D. P., Friedman, S. D., Frieman, J. A., Fukugita, M., Gänsicke, B. T., Gates, E., Gillespie, B., Glazebrook, K., Gray, J., Grebel, E. K., Gunn, J. E., Gurbani, V. K., Hall, P. B., Harding, P., Harvanek, M., Hawley, S. L., Hayes, J., Heckman, T. M., Hendry, J. S., Hindsley, R. B., Hirata, C. M., Hogan, C. J., Hogg, D. W., Hyde, J. B., Ichikawa, S.-i., Ivezić, Ž., Jester, S., Johnson, J. A., Jorgensen, A. M., Jurić, M., Kent, S. M., Kessler, R., Kleinman, S. J., Knapp, G. R., Kron, R. G., Krzesinski, J., Kuropatkin, N., Lamb, D. Q., Lampeitl, H., Lebedeva, S., Lee, Y. S., Leger, R. F., Lépine, S., Lima, M., Lin, H., Long, D. C., Loomis, C. P., Loveday, J., Lupton, R. H., Malanushenko, O., Malanushenko, V., Mandelbaum, R., Margon, B., Marriner, J. P., Martínez-Delgado, D., Matsubara, T., McGehee, P. M., McKay, T. A., Meiksin, A., Morrison, H. L., Munn, J. A., Nakajima, R., Neilsen, Jr., E. H., Newberg, H. J., Nichol, R. C., Nicinski, T., Nieto-Santisteban, M., Nitta, A., Okamura, S., Owen, R., Oyaizu, H., Padmanabhan, N., Pan, K., Park, C., Peoples, J. J., Pier, J. R., Pope, A. C., Purger, N., Raddick, M. J., Re Fiorentin, P., Richards, G. T., Richmond, M. W., Riess, A. G., Rix, H.-W., Rockosi, C. M., Sako, M., Schlegel, D. J., Schneider, D. P., Schreiber, M. R., Schwobe, A. D., Seljak, U., Sesar, B., Sheldon, E., Shimasaku, K., Sivarani, T., Smith, J. A., Snedden, S. A., Steinmetz, M., Strauss, M. A., SubbaRao, M., Suto, Y., Szalay, A. S., Szapudi, I., Szkody, P., Tegmark, M., Thakar, A. R., Tremonti, C. A., Tucker, D. L., Uomoto, A., Vanden Berk, D. E., Vandenberg, J., Vidrih, S., Vogeley, M. S., Voges, W., Vogt, N. P., Wadadekar, Y., Weinberg, D. H., West, A. A., White, S. D. M., Wilhite, B. C., Yanny, B., Yocum, D. R., York, D. G., Zehavi, I., & Zucker, D. B. 2008, *ApJS*, 175, 297

Adelman-McCarthy, J. K., Agüeros, M. A., Allam, S. S., Anderson, K. S. J., Anderson, S. F., Annis, J., Bahcall, N. A., Baldry, I. K., Barentine, J. C., Berlind, A., Bernardi, M., Blanton, M. R., Boroski, W. N., Brewington, H. J., Brinchmann, J., Brinkmann, J., Brunner, R. J., Budavári, T., Carey, L. N., Carr, M. A., Castander, F. J., Connolly, A. J., Csabai, I., Czarapata, P. C., Dalcanton, J. J., Doi, M., Dong, F., Eisenstein, D. J., Evans, M. L., Fan, X., Finkbeiner, D. P., Friedman, S. D., Frieman, J. A., Fukugita, M., Gillespie, B., Glazebrook, K., Gray, J., Grebel, E. K., Gunn, J. E., Gurbani, V. K., de Haas, E., Hall, P. B., Harris, F. H., Harvanek, M., Hawley, S. L., Hayes, J., Hendry, J. S., Hennessy, G. S., Hindsley, R. B., Hirata, C. M., Hogan, C. J., Hogg, D. W., Holmgren, D. J., Holtzman, J. A., Ichikawa, S.-i., Ivezić, Ž., Jester, S., Johnston, D. E., Jorgensen, A. M., Jurić, M., Kent, S. M., Kleinman, S. J., Knapp, G. R., Kniazev, A. Y., Kron, R. G., Krzesinski, J., Kuropatkin, N., Lamb, D. Q., Lampeitl, H., Lee, B. C., Leger, R. F., Lin, H., Long, D. C., Loveday, J., Lupton, R. H., Margon, B., Martínez-Delgado, D., Mandelbaum, R., Matsubara, T., McGehee, P. M., McKay, T. A., Meiksin, A., Munn, J. A., Nakajima, R., Nash, T., Neilsen, Jr., E. H., Newberg, H. J., Newman, P. R., Nichol, R. C., Nicinski, T., Nieto-Santisteban, M., Nitta, A., O'Mullane, W., Okamura, S., Owen, R., Padmanabhan, N., Pauls, G., Peoples, J. J., Pier, J. R., Pope, A. C., Pourbaix, D., Quinn, T. R., Richards, G. T., Richmond, M. W., Rockosi, C. M., Schlegel, D. J., Schneider, D. P., Schroeder, J., Scranton, R., Seljak, U., Sheldon, E., Shimasaku, K., Smith, J. A., Smolčić, V., Snedden, S. A., Stoughton, C., Strauss, M. A., SubbaRao, M., Szalay, A. S., Szapudi, I., Szokody, P., Tegmark, M., Thakar, A. R., Tucker, D. L., Uomoto, A., Vanden Berk, D. E., Vandenberg, J., Vogeley, M. S., Voges, W., Vogt, N. P., Walkowicz, L. M., Weinberg, D. H., West, A. A., White, S. D. M., Xu, Y., Yanny, B., Yocum, D. R., York, D. G., Zehavi, I., Zibetti, S., & Zucker, D. B. 2006, *ApJS*, 162, 38

Agertz, O., Moore, B., Stadel, J., Potter, D., Miniati, F., Read, J., Mayer, L., Gawryszczak, A., Kravtsov, A., Nordlund, Å., Pearce, F., Quilis, V., Rudd, D., Springel, V., Stone, J., Tasker, E., Teyssier, R., Wadsley, J., & Walder, R. 2007, *MNRAS*, 380, 963

Alcock, C. & Paczynski, B. 1979, *Nature*, 281, 358

Aller, L. H. & Greenstein, J. L. 1960, *ApJS*, 5, 139

Assef, R. J., Kochanek, C. S., Brodwin, M., Brown, M. J. I., Caldwell, N., Cool, R. J., Eisenhardt, P., Eisenstein, D., Gonzalez, A. H., Jannuzi, B. T., Jones, C., McKenzie, E., Murray, S. S., & Stern, D. 2008, *ApJ*, 676, 286

Axon, D. J. & Taylor, K. 1978, *Nature*, 274, 37

Baes, M., Buyle, P., Hau, G. K. T., & Dejonghe, H. 2003, *MNRAS*, 341, L44

- Baldry, I. K., Glazebrook, K., Brinkmann, J., Ivezić, Ž., Lupton, R. H., Nichol, R. C., & Szalay, A. S. 2004, *ApJ*, 600, 681
- Baldwin, J. A., Phillips, M. M., & Terlevich, R. 1981, *PASP*, 93, 5
- Barkana, R. & Loeb, A. 2001, *Phys. Rep.*, 349, 125
- Barnes, J. E. & Hernquist, L. 1992, *ARA&A*, 30, 705
- . 1996, *ApJ*, 471, 115
- Bechtold, J., Crotts, A. P. S., Duncan, R. C., & Fang, Y. 1994, *ApJ*, 437, L83
- Bernardi, M., Shankar, F., Hyde, J. B., Mei, S., Marulli, F., & Sheth, R. K. 2010, *MNRAS*, 436
- Bertone, S. & White, S. D. M. 2006, *MNRAS*, 367, 247
- Bethe, H. A. 1939, *Physical Review*, 55, 434
- Bi, H. & Davidsen, A. F. 1997, *ApJ*, 479, 523
- Blumenthal, G. R., Faber, S. M., Primack, J. R., & Rees, M. J. 1984, *Nature*, 311, 517
- Bolton, J. S., Viel, M., Kim, T.-S., Haehnelt, M. G., & Carswell, R. F. 2008, *MNRAS*, 386, 1131
- Boomsma, R., Oosterloo, T. A., Fraternali, F., van der Hulst, J. M., & Sancisi, R. 2008, *A&A*, 490, 555
- Boselli, A., Boissier, S., Cortese, L., & Gavazzi, G. 2008, *ApJ*, 674, 742
- Bresolin, F. 2006, *ArXiv Astrophysics e-prints*
- . 2007, *ApJ*, 656, 186
- Brinchmann, J., Charlot, S., White, S. D. M., Tremonti, C., Kauffmann, G., Heckman, T., & Brinkmann, J. 2004, *MNRAS*, 351, 1151
- Bromm, V., Coppi, P. S., & Larson, R. B. 2002, *ApJ*, 564, 23
- Brooks, A. M., Governato, F., Booth, C. M., Willman, B., Gardner, J. P., Wadsley, J., Stinson, G., & Quinn, T. 2007, *ApJ*, 655, L17
- Bryan, G. L. & Norman, M. L. 1998, *ApJ*, 495, 80
- Burbidge, E. M., Burbidge, G. R., Fowler, W. A., & Hoyle, F. 1957, *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 29, 547

- Calura, F. & Menci, N. 2009, ArXiv e-prints
- Calura, F., Pipino, A., Chiappini, C., Matteucci, F., & Maiolino, R. 2009, *A&A*, 504, 373
- Cardelli, J. A., Clayton, G. C., & Mathis, J. S. 1989, *ApJ*, 345, 245
- Catinella, B., Schiminovich, D., Kauffmann, G., Fabello, S., Wang, J., Hummels, C., Lemonias, J., Moran, S. M., Wu, R., Giovanelli, R., Haynes, M. P., Heckman, T. M., Basu-Zych, A. R., Blanton, M. R., Brinchmann, J., Budavári, T., Gonçalves, T., Johnson, B. D., Kennicutt, R. C., Madore, B. F., Martin, C. D., Rich, M. R., Tacconi, L. J., Thilker, D. A., Wild, V., & Wyder, T. K. 2010, *MNRAS*, 403, 683
- Cen, R., Miralda-Escudé, J., Ostriker, J. P., & Rauch, M. 1994, *ApJ*, 437, L9
- Chabrier, G. 2003a, *PASP*, 115, 763
- . 2003b, *ApJ*, 586, L133
- Charlton, J. C., Anninos, P., Zhang, Y., & Norman, M. L. 1997, *ApJ*, 485, 26
- Chevalier, R. A. & Clegg, A. W. 1985, *Nature*, 317, 44
- Chieffi, A. & Limongi, M. 2004, *ApJ*, 608, 405
- Cid Fernandes, R., Mateus, A., Sodré, L., Stasińska, G., & Gomes, J. M. 2005, *MNRAS*, 358, 363
- Coles, P. & Jones, B. 1991, *MNRAS*, 248, 1
- Conroy, C., Gunn, J. E., & White, M. 2009, *ApJ*, 699, 486
- Conroy, C. & Wechsler, R. H. 2009, *ApJ*, 696, 620
- Conselice, C. J., Rajgor, S., & Myers, R. 2008, *MNRAS*, 386, 909
- Cooper, M. C., Tremonti, C. A., Newman, J. A., & Zabludoff, A. I. 2008, *MNRAS*, 390, 245
- Coppolani, F., Petitjean, P., Stoehr, F., Rollinde, E., Pichon, C., Colombi, S., Haehnelt, M. G., Carswell, B., & Teyssier, R. 2006, *MNRAS*, 370, 1804
- Cox, T. J., Jonsson, P., Primack, J. R., & Somerville, R. S. 2006, *MNRAS*, 373, 1013
- Crain, R. A., Eke, V. R., Frenk, C. S., Jenkins, A., McCarthy, I. G., Navarro, J. F., & Pearce, F. R. 2007, *MNRAS*, 377, 41

- Croft, R. A. C., Weinberg, D. H., Bolte, M., Burles, S., Hernquist, L., Katz, N., Kirkman, D., & Tytler, D. 2002, *ApJ*, 581, 20
- Croft, R. A. C., Weinberg, D. H., Katz, N., & Hernquist, L. 1997, *ApJ*, 488, 532
- . 1998, *ApJ*, 495, 44
- Croft, R. A. C., Weinberg, D. H., Pettini, M., Hernquist, L., & Katz, N. 1999, *ApJ*, 520, 1
- Croton, D. J., Springel, V., White, S. D. M., De Lucia, G., Frenk, C. S., Gao, L., Jenkins, A., Kauffmann, G., Navarro, J. F., & Yoshida, N. 2006, *MNRAS*, 365, 11
- Crotts, A. P. S. & Fang, Y. 1998, *ApJ*, 502, 16
- Dalcanton, J. J. 2007, *ApJ*, 658, 941
- Davé, R., Hernquist, L., Katz, N., & Weinberg, D. H. 1999, *ApJ*, 511, 521
- Dekel, A. & Birnboim, Y. 2006, *MNRAS*, 368, 2
- Dekel, A. & Silk, J. 1986, *ApJ*, 303, 39
- Dekel, A. & Woo, J. 2003, *MNRAS*, 344, 1131
- Delahaye, F. & Pinsonneault, M. H. 2006, *ApJ*, 649, 529
- Dellenbusch, K. E., Gallagher, III, J. S., & Knezek, P. M. 2007, *ApJ*, 655, L29
- Denicoló, G., Terlevich, R., & Terlevich, E. 2002, *MNRAS*, 330, 69
- Desjacques, V. & Nusser, A. 2005, *MNRAS*, 361, 1257
- Desjacques, V., Nusser, A., & Sheth, R. K. 2007, *MNRAS*, 374, 206
- Di Matteo, T., Springel, V., & Hernquist, L. 2005, *Nature*, 433, 604
- Diemand, J., Kuhlen, M., & Madau, P. 2007, *ApJ*, 667, 859
- Dinshaw, N., Impey, C. D., Foltz, C. B., Weymann, R. J., & Chaffee, F. H. 1994, *ApJ*, 437, L87
- D’Odorico, V., Viel, M., Saitta, F., Cristiani, S., Bianchi, S., Boyle, B., Lopez, S., Maza, J., & Outram, P. 2006, *MNRAS*, 372, 1333
- Draine, B. T. & Lee, H. M. 1984, *ApJ*, 285, 89
- Dutton, A. A., Conroy, C., van den Bosch, F. C., Prada, F., & More, S. 2010a, *ArXiv e-prints*

- Dutton, A. A., van den Bosch, F. C., & Dekel, A. 2010b, MNRAS, 608
- Ebeling, H., Edge, A. C., Bohringer, H., Allen, S. W., Crawford, C. S., Fabian, A. C., Voges, W., & Huchra, J. P. 1998, MNRAS, 301, 881
- Ellison, S. L., Patton, D. R., Simard, L., & McConnachie, A. W. 2008a, ApJ, 672, L107
- . 2008b, AJ, 135, 1877
- Ellison, S. L., Songaila, A., Schaye, J., & Pettini, M. 2000, AJ, 120, 1175
- Erb, D. K. 2008, ApJ, 674, 151
- Erb, D. K., Shapley, A. E., Pettini, M., Steidel, C. C., Reddy, N. A., & Adelberger, K. L. 2006a, ApJ, 644, 813
- Erb, D. K., Steidel, C. C., Shapley, A. E., Pettini, M., Reddy, N. A., & Adelberger, K. L. 2006b, ApJ, 646, 107
- Faber, S. M., Willmer, C. N. A., Wolf, C., Koo, D. C., Weiner, B. J., Newman, J. A., Im, M., Coil, A. L., Conroy, C., Cooper, M. C., Davis, M., Finkbeiner, D. P., Gerke, B. F., Gebhardt, K., Groth, E. J., Guhathakurta, P., Harker, J., Kaiser, N., Kassin, S., Kleinheinrich, M., Konidaris, N. P., Kron, R. G., Lin, L., Luppino, G., Madgwick, D. S., Meisenheimer, K., Noeske, K. G., Phillips, A. C., Sarajedini, V. L., Schiavon, R. P., Simard, L., Szalay, A. S., Vogt, N. P., & Yan, R. 2007, ApJ, 665, 265
- Fan, X., Carilli, C. L., & Keating, B. 2006, ARA&A, 44, 415
- Fan, X., Narayanan, V. K., Lupton, R. H., Strauss, M. A., Knapp, G. R., Becker, R. H., White, R. L., Pentericci, L., Leggett, S. K., Haiman, Z., Gunn, J. E., Ivezić, Ž., Schneider, D. P., Anderson, S. F., Brinkmann, J., Bahcall, N. A., Connolly, A. J., Csabai, I., Doi, M., Fukugita, M., Geballe, T., Grebel, E. K., Harbeck, D., Hennessy, G., Lamb, D. Q., Miknaitis, G., Munn, J. A., Nichol, R., Okamura, S., Pier, J. R., Prada, F., Richards, G. T., Szalay, A., & York, D. G. 2001, AJ, 122, 2833
- Fan, X., Strauss, M. A., Schneider, D. P., Becker, R. H., White, R. L., Haiman, Z., Gregg, M., Pentericci, L., Grebel, E. K., Narayanan, V. K., Loh, Y., Richards, G. T., Gunn, J. E., Lupton, R. H., Knapp, G. R., Ivezić, Ž., Brandt, W. N., Collinge, M., Hao, L., Harbeck, D., Prada, F., Schaye, J., Strateva, I., Zakamska, N., Anderson, S., Brinkmann, J., Bahcall, N. A., Lamb, D. Q., Okamura, S., Szalay, A., & York, D. G. 2003, AJ, 125, 1649
- Fang, Y., Duncan, R. C., Crofts, A. P. S., & Bechtold, J. 1996, ApJ, 462, 77

- Faucher-Giguère, C.-A., Prochaska, J. X., Lidz, A., Hernquist, L., & Zaldarriaga, M. 2008, *ApJ*, 681, 831
- Ferrarese, L. 2002, *ApJ*, 578, 90
- Finlator, K. & Davé, R. 2008, *MNRAS*, 385, 2181
- Firmani, C., Avila-Reese, V., & Rodriguez-Puebla, A. 2009, ArXiv e-prints
- Fischer, J. & Dopita, M. 2005, *ApJ*, 619, 340
- Fruchter, A. S., Levan, A. J., Strolger, L., Vreeswijk, P. M., Thorsett, S. E., Bersier, D., Burud, I., Castro Cerón, J. M., Castro-Tirado, A. J., Conselice, C., Dahlen, T., Ferguson, H. C., Fynbo, J. P. U., Garnavich, P. M., Gibbons, R. A., Gorosabel, J., Gull, T. R., Hjorth, J., Holland, S. T., Kouveliotou, C., Levay, Z., Livio, M., Metzger, M. R., Nugent, P. E., Petro, L., Pian, E., Rhoads, J. E., Riess, A. G., Sahu, K. C., Smette, A., Tanvir, N. R., Wijers, R. A. M. J., & Woosley, S. E. 2006, *Nature*, 441, 463
- Furlanetto, S. R. & Oh, S. P. 2008, *ApJ*, 682, 14
- Garcia-Appadoo, D. A., West, A. A., Dalcanton, J. J., Cortese, L., & Disney, M. J. 2009, *MNRAS*, 394, 340
- Garnett, D. R. 2002, *ApJ*, 581, 1019
- Garnett, D. R. & Shields, G. A. 1987, *ApJ*, 317, 82
- Gaztañaga, E. & Croft, R. A. C. 1999, *MNRAS*, 309, 885
- Genel, S., Genzel, R., Bouché, N., Sternberg, A., Naab, T., Schreiber, N. M. F., Shapiro, K. L., Tacconi, L. J., Lutz, D., Cresci, G., Buschkamp, P., Davies, R. I., & Hicks, E. K. S. 2008, *ApJ*, 688, 789
- Gingold, R. A. & Monaghan, J. J. 1977, *MNRAS*, 181, 375
- Gnedin, N. Y. & Hui, L. 1998, *MNRAS*, 296, 44
- Goldsmith, D. W., Habing, H. J., & Field, G. B. 1969, *ApJ*, 158, 173
- Grebel, E. K., Gallagher, III, J. S., & Harbeck, D. 2003, *AJ*, 125, 1926
- Grimes, J. P., Heckman, T., Aloisi, A., Calzetti, D., Leitherer, C., Martin, C. L., Meurer, G., Sembach, K., & Strickland, D. 2009, *ApJS*, 181, 272
- Grimes, J. P., Heckman, T., Hoopes, C., Strickland, D., Aloisi, A., Meurer, G., & Ptak, A. 2006, *ApJ*, 648, 310

- Gu, Q., Zhao, Y., Shi, L., Peng, Z., & Luo, X. 2006, *AJ*, 131, 806
- Gunn, J. E. & Gott, J. R. I. 1972, *ApJ*, 176, 1+
- Gunn, J. E. & Peterson, B. A. 1965, *ApJ*, 142, 1633
- Guo, Q., White, S., Li, C., & Boylan-Kolchin, M. 2009, ArXiv e-prints
- Haardt, F. & Madau, P. 2001, in *Clusters of Galaxies and the High Redshift Universe Observed in X-rays*, ed. D. M. Neumann & J. T. V. Tran
- Heckman, T. M. 2003, in *Revista Mexicana de Astronomia y Astrofisica*, vol. 27, Vol. 17, *Revista Mexicana de Astronomia y Astrofisica Conference Series*, ed. V. Avila-Reese, C. Firmani, C. S. Frenk, & C. Allen, 47–55
- Heckman, T. M., Armus, L., & Miley, G. K. 1990, *ApJS*, 74, 833
- Heckman, T. M., Lehnert, M. D., Strickland, D. K., & Armus, L. 2000, *ApJS*, 129, 493
- Hennawi, J. F., Myers, A. D., Shen, Y., Strauss, M. A., Djorgovski, S. G., Fan, X., Glikman, E., Mahabal, A., Martin, C. L., Richards, G. T., Schneider, D. P., & Shankar, F. 2009, ArXiv e-prints
- Hennawi, J. F., Strauss, M. A., Oguri, M., Inada, N., Richards, G. T., Pindor, B., Schneider, D. P., Becker, R. H., Gregg, M. D., Hall, P. B., Johnston, D. E., Fan, X., Burles, S., Schlegel, D. J., Gunn, J. E., Lupton, R. H., Bahcall, N. A., Brunner, R. J., & Brinkmann, J. 2006, *AJ*, 131, 1
- Hernquist, L. & Katz, N. 1989, *ApJS*, 70, 419
- Hernquist, L., Katz, N., Weinberg, D. H., & Miralda-Escudé, J. 1996, *ApJ*, 457, L51+
- Hinshaw, G., Weiland, J. L., Hill, R. S., Odegard, N., Larson, D., Bennett, C. L., Dunkley, J., Gold, B., Greason, M. R., Jarosik, N., Komatsu, E., Nolte, M. R., Page, L., Spergel, D. N., Wollack, E., Halpern, M., Kogut, A., Limon, M., Meyer, S. S., Tucker, G. S., & Wright, E. L. 2009, *ApJS*, 180, 225
- Hoopes, C. G., Heckman, T. M., Salim, S., Seibert, M., Tremonti, C. A., Schiminovich, D., Rich, R. M., Martin, D. C., Charlot, S., Kauffmann, G., Forster, K., Friedman, P. G., Morrissey, P., Neff, S. G., Small, T., Wyder, T. K., Bianchi, L., Donas, J., Lee, Y.-W., Madore, B. F., Milliard, B., Szalay, A. S., Welsh, B. Y., & Yi, S. K. 2007, *ApJS*, 173, 441
- Hopkins, P. F., Hernquist, L., Cox, T. J., Di Matteo, T., Robertson, B., & Springel, V. 2006, *ApJS*, 163, 1

- Hopkins, P. F., Hernquist, L., Cox, T. J., Dutta, S. N., & Rothberg, B. 2008, *ApJ*, 679, 156
- Hoyle, F. 1954, *ApJS*, 1, 121
- Hubble, E. P. 1926, *ApJ*, 64, 321
- Hui, L. & Gnedin, N. Y. 1997, *MNRAS*, 292, 27
- Hui, L. & Haiman, Z. 2003, *ApJ*, 596, 9
- Hui, L., Stebbins, A., & Burles, S. 1999, *ApJ*, 511, L5
- Jaunsen, A. O., Rol, E., Watson, D. J., Malesani, D., Fynbo, J. P. U., Milvang-Jensen, B., Hjorth, J., Vreeswijk, P. M., Ovaldsen, J.-E., Wiersema, K., Tanvir, N. R., Gorosabel, J., Levan, A. J., Schirmer, M., & Castro-Tirado, A. J. 2008, *ApJ*, 681, 453
- Kant, I. 1755, *Allgemeine Naturgeschichte und Theorie des Himmels*, ed. Kant, I.
- Karachentsev, I. D. 2005, *AJ*, 129, 178
- Katz, N., Weinberg, D. H., & Hernquist, L. 1996, *ApJS*, 105, 19
- Kauffmann, G., Heckman, T. M., White, S. D. M., Charlot, S., Tremonti, C., Brinchmann, J., Bruzual, G., Peng, E. W., Seibert, M., Bernardi, M., Blanton, M., Brinkmann, J., Castander, F., Csábai, I., Fukugita, M., Ivezić, Z., Munn, J. A., Nichol, R. C., Padmanabhan, N., Thakar, A. R., Weinberg, D. H., & York, D. 2003, *MNRAS*, 341, 33
- Kauffmann, G., White, S. D. M., & Guiderdoni, B. 1993, *MNRAS*, 264, 201
- Kennicutt, Jr., R. C. 1998, *ApJ*, 498, 541
- Kennicutt, Jr., R. C., Bresolin, F., & Garnett, D. R. 2003, *ApJ*, 591, 801
- Kereš, D., Katz, N., Fardal, M., Davé, R., & Weinberg, D. H. 2009, *MNRAS*, 395, 160
- Kereš, D., Katz, N., Weinberg, D. H., & Davé, R. 2005, *MNRAS*, 363, 2
- Kewley, L. J., Brown, W. R., Geller, M. J., Kenyon, S. J., & Kurtz, M. J. 2007, *AJ*, 133, 882
- Kewley, L. J. & Dopita, M. A. 2002, *ApJS*, 142, 35
- Kewley, L. J. & Ellison, S. L. 2008, *ApJ*, 681, 1183
- Kewley, L. J., Geller, M. J., & Barton, E. J. 2006a, *AJ*, 131, 2004

- Kewley, L. J., Groves, B., Kauffmann, G., & Heckman, T. 2006b, MNRAS, 372, 961
- Kim, T., Viel, M., Haehnelt, M. G., Carswell, R. F., & Cristiani, S. 2004, MNRAS, 347, 355
- Kim, T.-S., Bolton, J. S., Viel, M., Haehnelt, M. G., & Carswell, R. F. 2007, MNRAS, 382, 1657
- Kobayashi, C., Springel, V., & White, S. D. M. 2007, MNRAS, 376, 1465
- Kobulnicky, H. A. & Kewley, L. J. 2004, ApJ, 617, 240
- Kollmeier, J. A., Miralda-Escudé, J., Cen, R., & Ostriker, J. P. 2006, ApJ, 638, 52
- Köppen, J., Weidner, C., & Kroupa, P. 2007, MNRAS, 375, 673
- Kroupa, P. 2001, MNRAS, 322, 231
- Lara-López, M. A., Cepa, J., Bongiovanni, A., Pérez García, A. M., Ederoclite, A., Castañeda, H., Fernández Lorenzo, M., Póvic, M., & Sánchez-Portal, M. 2010, ArXiv e-prints
- Larson, R. B. 1974, MNRAS, 169, 229
- . 1985, MNRAS, 214, 379
- Lee, H., Skillman, E. D., Cannon, J. M., Jackson, D. C., Gehrz, R. D., Polomski, E. F., & Woodward, C. E. 2006, ApJ, 647, 970
- Lee, J. C., Salzer, J. J., & Melbourne, J. 2004, ApJ, 616, 752
- Lequeux, J., Peimbert, M., Rayo, J. F., Serrano, A., & Torres-Peimbert, S. 1979, A&A, 80, 155
- Leroy, A. K., Walter, F., Brinks, E., Bigiel, F., de Blok, W. J. G., Madore, B., & Thornley, M. D. 2008, AJ, 136, 2782
- Lidz, A., Faucher-Giguere, C. ., Dall’Aglío, A., McQuinn, M., Fechner, C., Zaldarriaga, M., Hernquist, L., & Dutta, S. 2009, ArXiv e-prints
- Loeb, A. & Peebles, P. J. E. 2003, ApJ, 589, 29
- Lokas, E. L. & Mamon, G. A. 2001, MNRAS, 321, 155
- Lucy, L. B. 1977, AJ, 82, 1013
- Lynds, R. 1971, ApJ, 164, L73+

- Maiolino, R., Nagao, T., Grazian, A., Cocchia, F., Marconi, A., Mannucci, F., Cimatti, A., Pipino, A., Ballero, S., Calura, F., Chiappini, C., Fontana, A., Granato, G. L., Matteucci, F., Pastorini, G., Pentericci, L., Risaliti, G., Salvati, M., & Silva, L. 2008, *A&A*, 488, 463
- Mannucci, F., Cresci, G., Maiolino, R., Marconi, A., & Gnerucci, A. 2010, *ArXiv e-prints*
- Marble, A. R., Eriksen, K. A., Impey, C. D., Bai, L., & Miller, L. 2008a, *ApJS*, 175, 29
- Marble, A. R., Eriksen, K. A., Impey, C. D., Oppenheimer, B. D., & Davé, R. 2008b, *ApJ*, 675, 946
- Margutti, R., Chincarini, G., Covino, S., Tagliaferri, G., Campana, S., Della Valle, M., Filippenko, A. V., Fiore, F., Foley, R., Fugazza, D., Giommi, P., Malesani, D., Moretti, A., & Stella, L. 2007, *A&A*, 474, 815
- Marri, S. & White, S. D. M. 2003, *MNRAS*, 345, 561
- Martin, C. L. 2005, *ApJ*, 621, 227
- Martin, C. L. & Bouché, N. 2009, *ApJ*, 703, 1394
- Matteucci, F. 2002, *ArXiv Astrophysics e-prints*
- Matteucci, F. & Francois, P. 1992, *A&A*, 262, L1
- McDonald, P. 2003, *ApJ*, 585, 34
- McDonald, P. & Miralda-Escudé, J. 1999, *ApJ*, 518, 24
- McDonald, P., Miralda-Escudé, J., Rauch, M., Sargent, W. L. W., Barlow, T. A., & Cen, R. 2001, *ApJ*, 562, 52
- McDonald, P., Miralda-Escudé, J., Rauch, M., Sargent, W. L. W., Barlow, T. A., Cen, R., & Ostriker, J. P. 2000, *ApJ*, 543, 1
- McDonald, P., Seljak, U., Burles, S., Schlegel, D. J., Weinberg, D. H., Cen, R., Shih, D., Schaye, J., Schneider, D. P., Bahcall, N. A., Briggs, J. W., Brinkmann, J., Brunner, R. J., Fukugita, M., Gunn, J. E., Ivezić, Ž., Kent, S., Lupton, R. H., & Vanden Berk, D. E. 2006, *ApJS*, 163, 80
- McDonald, P., Seljak, U., Cen, R., Shih, D., Weinberg, D. H., Burles, S., Schneider, D. P., Schlegel, D. J., Bahcall, N. A., Briggs, J. W., Brinkmann, J., Fukugita, M., Ivezić, Ž., Kent, S., & Vanden Berk, D. E. 2005, *ApJ*, 635, 761
- McGaugh, S. S. 1991, *ApJ*, 380, 140

- . 2005, *ApJ*, 632, 859
- McKee, C. F. & Ostriker, J. P. 1977, *ApJ*, 218, 148
- McQuinn, M., Lidz, A., Zaldarriaga, M., Hernquist, L., Hopkins, P. F., Dutta, S., & Faucher-Giguère, C.-A. 2009, *ApJ*, 694, 842
- McWilliam, A. 1997, *ARA&A*, 35, 503
- Meiksin, A. & White, M. 2001, *MNRAS*, 324, 141
- Michel-Dansac, L., Lambas, D. G., Alonso, M. S., & Tissera, P. 2008, *MNRAS*, 386, L82
- Mihos, J. C. & Hernquist, L. 1996, *ApJ*, 464, 641
- Miralda-Escude, J. 1993, *MNRAS*, 262, 273
- Miralda-Escudé, J., Cen, R., Ostriker, J. P., & Rauch, M. 1996, *ApJ*, 471, 582
- Miralda-Escudé, J., Rauch, M., Sargent, W. L. W., Barlow, T. A., Weinberg, D. H., Hernquist, L., Katz, N., Cen, R., & Ostriker, J. P. 1997, in *Structure and Evolution of the Intergalactic Medium from QSO Absorption Line System*, ed. P. Petitjean & S. Charlot, 155–+
- Miralda-Escudé, J. & Rees, M. J. 1994, *MNRAS*, 266, 343
- Monaghan, J. J. 1992, *ARA&A*, 30, 543
- Montuori, M., Di Matteo, P., Lehnert, M. D., Combes, F., & Semelin, B. 2010, *ArXiv e-prints*
- More, S., van den Bosch, F. C., Cacciato, M., Skibba, R., Mo, H. J., & Yang, X. 2010, *ArXiv e-prints*
- Morris, J. P. 1996, *Publications of the Astronomical Society of Australia*, 13, 97
- Moster, B. P., Somerville, R. S., Maulbetsch, C., van den Bosch, F. C., Maccio', A. V., Naab, T., & Oser, L. 2009, *ArXiv e-prints*
- Murray, N., Quataert, E., & Thompson, T. A. 2005, *ApJ*, 618, 569
- Navarro, J. F., Frenk, C. S., & White, S. D. M. 1996, *ApJ*, 462, 563
- Neistein, E., van den Bosch, F. C., & Dekel, A. 2006, *MNRAS*, 372, 933
- Nusser, A. & Haehnelt, M. 2000, *MNRAS*, 313, 364

- Okamoto, T., Jenkins, A., Eke, V. R., Quilis, V., & Frenk, C. S. 2003, MNRAS, 345, 429
- Oppenheimer, B. D., Davé, R., Kereš, D., Fardal, M., Katz, N., Kollmeier, J. A., & Weinberg, D. H. 2009, ArXiv e-prints
- Overzier, R. A., Heckman, T. M., Kauffmann, G., Seibert, M., Rich, R. M., Basu-Zych, A., Lotz, J., Aloisi, A., Charlot, S., Hoopes, C., Martin, D. C., Schiminovich, D., & Madore, B. 2008, ApJ, 677, 37
- Pearce, F. R., Jenkins, A., Frenk, C. S., Colberg, J. M., White, S. D. M., Thomas, P. A., Couchman, H. M. P., Peacock, J. A., Efstathiou, G., & The Virgo Consortium. 1999, ApJ, 521, L99
- Peebles, P. J. E. 1993, Principles of physical cosmology, ed. Peebles, P. J. E.
- Pettini, M. & Pagel, B. E. J. 2004, MNRAS, 348, L59
- Pizagno, J., Prada, F., Weinberg, D. H., Rix, H., Pogge, R. W., Grebel, E. K., Harbeck, D., Blanton, M., Brinkmann, J., & Gunn, J. E. 2007, AJ, 134, 945
- Portinari, L., Chiosi, C., & Bressan, A. 1998, A&A, 334, 505
- Press, W. H., Teukolsky, S. A., Vetterling, W. T., & Flannery, B. P. 1992, Numerical Recipes in C (Cambridge University Press: Cambridge)
- Prochaska, J. X., Bloom, J. S., Chen, H.-W., Hurley, K. C., Melbourne, J., Dressler, A., Graham, J. R., Osip, D. J., & Vacca, W. D. 2004, ApJ, 611, 200
- Rauch, M. 1998, ARA&A, 36, 267
- Rauch, M., Miralda-Escude, J., Sargent, W. L. W., Barlow, T. A., Weinberg, D. H., Hernquist, L., Katz, N., Cen, R., & Ostriker, J. P. 1997, ApJ, 489, 7
- Read, J. I., Hayfield, T., & Agertz, O. 2009, ArXiv e-prints
- Recchi, S., Calura, F., & Kroupa, P. 2009, A&A, 499, 711
- Rees, M. J. & Ostriker, J. P. 1977, MNRAS, 179, 541
- Reisenegger, A. & Miralda-Escude, J. 1995, ApJ, 449, 476
- Ricotti, M., Gnedin, N. Y., & Shull, J. M. 2000, ApJ, 534, 41
- Ritchie, B. W. & Thomas, P. A. 2001, MNRAS, 323, 743
- Rollinde, E., Petitjean, P., Pichon, C., Colombi, S., Aracil, B., D'Odorico, V., & Haehnelt, M. G. 2003, MNRAS, 341, 1279

- Rubin, V. C., Burstein, D., Ford, Jr., W. K., & Thonnard, N. 1985, *ApJ*, 289, 81
- Rupke, D. S., Veilleux, S., & Sanders, D. B. 2002, *ApJ*, 570, 588
- Rupke, D. S. N., Veilleux, S., & Baker, A. J. 2008, *ApJ*, 674, 172
- Russell, S. C. & Dopita, M. A. 1990, *ApJS*, 74, 93
- Salpeter, E. E. 1955, *ApJ*, 121, 161
- . 1964, *ApJ*, 140, 796
- Salucci, P., Lapi, A., Tonini, C., Gentile, G., Yegorova, I., & Klein, U. 2007, *MNRAS*, 378, 41
- Samui, S., Subramanian, K., & Srianand, R. 2008, *MNRAS*, 385, 783
- Sargent, W. L. W., Young, P. J., Boksenberg, A., & Tytler, D. 1980, *ApJS*, 42, 41
- Savaglio, S., Glazebrook, K., Le Borgne, D., Juneau, S., Abraham, R. G., Chen, H.-W., Crampton, D., McCarthy, P. J., Carlberg, R. G., Marzke, R. O., Roth, K., Jørgensen, I., & Murowinski, R. 2005, *ApJ*, 635, 260
- Sawala, T., Scannapieco, C., Maio, U., & White, S. 2010, *MNRAS*, 402, 1599
- Schaye, J. 2001, *ApJ*, 559, 507
- Schaye, J., Aguirre, A., Kim, T., Theuns, T., Rauch, M., & Sargent, W. L. W. 2003, *ApJ*, 596, 768
- Schaye, J., Theuns, T., Leonard, A., & Efstathiou, G. 1999, *MNRAS*, 310, 57
- Schaye, J., Theuns, T., Rauch, M., Efstathiou, G., & Sargent, W. L. W. 2000, *MNRAS*, 318, 817
- Schiminovich, D., Catinella, B., Kauffmann, G., Fabello, S., Wang, J., Hummels, C., Lemonias, J., Moran, S. M., Wu, R., Giovanelli, R., Haynes, M. P., Heckman, T. M., Basu-Zych, A. R., Blanton, M. R., Brinchmann, J., Budavari, T., Goncalves, T., Johnson, B. D., Kennicutt, R. C., Madore, B. F., Martin, C. D., Rich, M. R., Tacconi, L. J., Thilker, D. A., Wild, V., & Wyder, T. K. 2010, *ArXiv e-prints*
- Schlegel, D., White, M., & Eisenstein, D. 2009, in *Astronomy, Vol. 2010, AGB Stars and Related Phenomena* *astro2010: The Astronomy and Astrophysics Decadal Survey*, 314–+
- Schmidt, M. 1959, *ApJ*, 129, 243

- Schneider, P., Kochanek, C. S., & Wambsganss, J. 2006, *Gravitational Lensing: Strong, Weak and Micro* (Gravitational Lensing: Strong, Weak and Micro: , Saas-Fee Advanced Courses, Volume 33. ISBN 978-3-540-30309-1. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 2006)
- Searle, L. & Sargent, W. L. W. 1972, *ApJ*, 173, 25
- Shankar, F., Lapi, A., Salucci, P., De Zotti, G., & Danese, L. 2006, *ApJ*, 643, 14
- Silk, J. 1968, *ApJ*, 151, 459
- . 1977, *ApJ*, 211, 638
- Silk, J. & Rees, M. J. 1998, *A&A*, 331, L1
- Slipher, V. M. 1917, *Lowell Observatory Bulletin*, 3, 59
- Socrates, A., Davis, S. W., & Ramirez-Ruiz, E. 2008, *ApJ*, 687, 202
- Songaila, A. & Cowie, L. L. 1996, *AJ*, 112, 335
- Spitoni, E., Calura, F., Matteucci, F., & Recchi, S. 2010, *ArXiv e-prints*
- Spoon, H. W. W. & Holt, J. 2009, *ApJ*, 702, L42
- Springel, V. 2005, *MNRAS*, 364, 1105
- Springel, V. & Hernquist, L. 2002, *MNRAS*, 333, 649
- . 2003, *MNRAS*, 339, 289
- Stanek, K. Z., Gnedin, O. Y., Beacom, J. F., Gould, A. P., Johnson, J. A., Kollmeier, J. A., Modjaz, M., Pinsonneault, M. H., Pogge, R., & Weinberg, D. H. 2006, *Acta Astronomica*, 56, 333
- Strickland, D. K. & Heckman, T. M. 2007, *ApJ*, 658, 258
- . 2009, *ApJ*, 697, 2030
- Strickland, D. K. & Stevens, I. R. 2000, *MNRAS*, 314, 511
- Struck, C., Hancock, M., Smith, B. J., Appleton, P. N., Charmandaris, V., & Giroux, M. 2008, in *IAU Symposium*, Vol. 244, *IAU Symposium*, ed. J. Davies & M. Disney, 231–234

- Tegmark, M., Strauss, M. A., Blanton, M. R., Abazajian, K., Dodelson, S., Sandvik, H., Wang, X., Weinberg, D. H., Zehavi, I., Bahcall, N. A., Hoyle, F., Schlegel, D., Scoccimarro, R., Vogeley, M. S., Berlind, A., Budavari, T., Connolly, A., Eisenstein, D. J., Finkbeiner, D., Frieman, J. A., Gunn, J. E., Hui, L., Jain, B., Johnston, D., Kent, S., Lin, H., Nakajima, R., Nichol, R. C., Ostriker, J. P., Pope, A., Scranton, R., Seljak, U., Sheth, R. K., Stebbins, A., Szalay, A. S., Szapudi, I., Xu, Y., Annis, J., Brinkmann, J., Burles, S., Castander, F. J., Csabai, I., Loveday, J., Doi, M., Fukugita, M., Gillespie, B., Hennessy, G., Hogg, D. W., Ivezić, Ž., Knapp, G. R., Lamb, D. Q., Lee, B. C., Lupton, R. H., McKay, T. A., Kunszt, P., Munn, J. A., O'Connell, L., Peoples, J., Pier, J. R., Richmond, M., Rockosi, C., Schneider, D. P., Stoughton, C., Tucker, D. L., vanden Berk, D. E., Yanny, B., & York, D. G. 2004, *Phys. Rev. D*, 69, 103501
- Theuns, T., Leonard, A., Efstathiou, G., Pearce, F. R., & Thomas, P. A. 1998, *MNRAS*, 301, 478
- Theuns, T., Schaye, J., & Haehnelt, M. G. 2000, *MNRAS*, 315, 600
- Tinsley, B. M. 1979, *ApJ*, 229, 1046
- Tittley, E. R., Pearce, F. R., & Couchman, H. M. P. 2001, *ApJ*, 561, 69
- Tonini, C., Lapi, A., Shankar, F., & Salucci, P. 2006, *ApJ*, 638, L13
- Tremonti, C. A., Heckman, T. M., Kauffmann, G., Brinchmann, J., Charlot, S., White, S. D. M., Seibert, M., Peng, E. W., Schlegel, D. J., Uomoto, A., Fukugita, M., & Brinkmann, J. 2004, *ApJ*, 613, 898
- Tully, R. B. & Fisher, J. R. 1977, *A&A*, 54, 661
- Tytler, D., Kirkman, D., O'Meara, J. M., Suzuki, N., Orin, A., Lubin, D., Paschos, P., Jena, T., Lin, W.-C., Norman, M. L., & Meiksin, A. 2004, *ApJ*, 617, 1
- Untertorn, C. T. & Ryden, B. S. 2008, *ApJ*, 687, 976
- Vale, A. & Ostriker, J. P. 2004, *MNRAS*, 353, 189
- van Zee, L., Salzer, J. J., Haynes, M. P., O'Donoghue, A. A., & Balonek, T. J. 1998, *AJ*, 116, 2805
- Veilleux, S., Cecil, G., & Bland-Hawthorn, J. 2005, *ARA&A*, 43, 769
- Viel, M., Becker, G. D., Bolton, J. S., Haehnelt, M. G., Rauch, M., & Sargent, W. L. W. 2008, *Physical Review Letters*, 100, 041304
- Viel, M. & Haehnelt, M. G. 2006, *MNRAS*, 365, 231

- Viel, M., Haehnelt, M. G., & Springel, V. 2004, MNRAS, 354, 684
- Viel, M., Matarrese, S., Mo, H. J., Haehnelt, M. G., & Theuns, T. 2002, MNRAS, 329, 848
- Wadsley, J. W., Stadel, J., & Quinn, T. 2004, New Astronomy, 9, 137
- Wallerstein, G. 1962, ApJS, 6, 407
- Walter, F., Brinks, E., de Blok, W. J. G., Bigiel, F., Kennicutt, R. C., Thornley, M. D., & Leroy, A. 2008, AJ, 136, 2563
- Weinberg, D. e. a. 1999, in Evolution of Large Scale Structure : From Recombination to Garching, ed. A. J. Banday, R. K. Sheth, & L. N. da Costa, 346–+
- Weinberg, D. H., Hernquist, L., Katz, N., Croft, R., & Miralda-Escudé, J. 1997a, in Structure and Evolution of the Intergalactic Medium from QSO Absorption Line System, ed. P. Petitjean & S. Charlot, 133–+
- Weinberg, D. H., Miralda-Escude, J., Hernquist, L., & Katz, N. 1997b, ApJ, 490, 564
- Weinberg, S. 1972, Gravitation and Cosmology: Principles and Applications of the General Theory of Relativity, ed. Weinberg, S.
- West, A. A., Garcia-Appadoo, D. A., Dalcanton, J. J., Disney, M. J., Rockosi, C. M., & Ivezić, Ž. 2009, AJ, 138, 796
- West, A. A., Garcia-Appadoo, D. A., Dalcanton, J. J., Disney, M. J., Rockosi, C. M., Ivezić, Ž., Bentz, M. C., & Brinkmann, J. 2010, AJ, 139, 315
- White, S. D. M. & Frenk, C. S. 1991, ApJ, 379, 52
- White, S. D. M. & Rees, M. J. 1978, MNRAS, 183, 341
- Whitmore, B. C., Chandar, R., Schweizer, F., Rothberg, B., Leitherer, C., Rieke, M., Rieke, G., Blair, W. P., Mengel, S., & Alonso-Herrero, A. 2010, AJ, 140, 75
- Wong, T. & Blitz, L. 2002, ApJ, 569, 157
- Woosley, S. E. & Weaver, T. A. 1995, ApJS, 101, 181
- Wyse, R. F. G. & Silk, J. 1985, ApJ, 296, L1
- Zaldarriaga, M., Hui, L., & Tegmark, M. 2001, ApJ, 557, 519
- Zaritsky, D., Kennicutt, Jr., R. C., & Huchra, J. P. 1994, ApJ, 420, 87
- Zel'Dovich, Y. B. 1970, A&A, 5, 84

Zhang, Y., Anninos, P., & Norman, M. L. 1995, ApJ, 453, L57+

Zwicky, F. 1956, Ergebnisse der exakten Naturwissenschaften, 29, 344

—. 1959, Handbuch der Physik, 53, 373